

The Baalbek Enigma

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Figure 1. The six surviving columns of the Temple of Jupiter at Baalbek. Lebanon. © Marco M. Vigato.

Abstract

Baalbek's temple complex in Lebanon presents an archaeological enigma due to the unmatched scale of its colossal temple ruins in a historically marginal town. The site features enormous architectural elements, including the famed *Trilithon* monoliths, each nearly 20 meters long and weighing over 800 tons, far exceeding the scale of typical Roman engineering. Conventional scholarship holds that Baalbek's temples were built in the early Roman Imperial period (1st–3rd centuries CE), but alternative interpretations propose a far more

ancient origin for the megalithic foundations. This paper critically examines evidence supporting greater antiquity, including archaeological findings of continuous habitation since the Neolithic and underlying Bronze Age structures, alongside geodetic alignments linking Baalbek with ancient sacred centers such as Giza and Heliopolis in Egypt. It also explores the site's religious and mythological significance over millennia. Medieval legends ascribe Baalbek's construction to King Solomon or even pre-diluvian civilizations, while its ancient name Heliopolis ("City of the Sun") attests to an enduring sacred status since at least the Hellenistic era. Synthesizing conventional and alternative viewpoints, the present research argues that construction of the Baalbek's megalithic complex may predate the Roman era, calling for a reassessment of its historical timeline in light of this evidence.

Introduction

The colossal ruins of Baalbek and the vast megalithic platform upon which its temples stand have fascinated and confounded scholars since the earliest European travelers began reporting their encounters with the ruined monuments of the East. From the outset, Baalbek presented itself as an anomaly – monumental in scale, yet curiously disconnected from the historical and urban context one would expect to justify such ambition.

These are the largest temple ruins in the entire Roman and Classical world, constructed with the largest stones ever employed in architecture anywhere on Earth. Herein lies the central enigma of Baalbek. Nowhere else in the Roman Empire was a project of comparable magnitude attempted. Not even Rome itself could rival the sheer scale, splendor, and richness of ornamentation displayed at Baalbek. And yet, Baalbek was never a major political capital, nor a key commercial or caravan hub comparable to other prominent cities of the region. Documentary evidence for a pre-Roman Baalbek is strikingly sparse. The site appears to emerge from relative obscurity only in the first century BCE, flourishes briefly through the late fourth century CE, and then once again fades into obscurity.

By the early Middle Ages, the identity of Baalbek's original builders had dissolved into legend. Medieval chroniclers attributed its construction to the biblical King Solomon, imagining the site as a palace built for the Queen of Sheba. Others pushed its origins further back still, to an age so remote that the

ruins were thought to predate the Great Flood itself – vestiges of a lost civilization erased by a primordial catastrophe.

Since the first German excavations at Baalbek at the turn of the twentieth century, significant progress has been made toward understanding the chronology and construction history of the temple complex. Few ancient monuments have attracted such sustained scholarly attention or generated so extensive a body of literature. Yet, paradoxically, as academic understanding has deepened, Baalbek has also become a focal point for speculative and alternative interpretations, ranging from lost civilizations to extraterrestrial intervention.

This study seeks to reassess the age and construction sequence of the Baalbek temples through three complementary perspectives. First, a historical and mythological approach examines ancient literary sources, documentary evidence, and the enduring traditions surrounding the site's origins. Second, an archaeological perspective reviews more than a century of systematic excavation and research, beginning with the German campaigns of 1898–1905. Third, an engineering and technological analysis evaluates the practical feasibility of the various hypotheses proposed to explain the transport and placement of the colossal stones.

Part I analyzes the principal historical and literary sources relating to Baalbek and its Sanctuary of Jupiter, arguing that the site functioned as an important cult center long before the Roman imperial period and was integrated into a broader network of Near Eastern sanctuaries through precise geodetic relationships.

Part II presents the main architectural elements of the Baalbek temple complex and reconstructs their likely construction sequence in light of the most recent archaeological findings.

Part III examines a number of alternative claims regarding the chronology of the sanctuary, with particular attention to the unresolved problem of megalith transportation and other anomalies that challenge the prevailing academic consensus.

Finally, Part IV offers some preliminary conclusions and proposes a revised construction sequence that supports a pre-Roman origin for the megalithic platform and enclosure walls of Baalbek, while acknowledging unresolved questions and outlining directions for future research.

Part I – Prehistoric Origins

A Brief history of Baalbek

Figure 2. Map of modern-day Lebanon with location of the city of Baalbek.

The ruins of Baalbek are located in the fertile Bekaa Valley of eastern Lebanon, about 85 km northeast of Beirut and 75 kilometers north of Damascus, at an altitude of 1150 meters above sea level¹. Known in Greco-Roman times as Heliopolis (“City of the Sun”), it was the site of the largest religious complex in the Roman Empire. Yet its history stretches back much further: archaeological excavations in the Jupiter Temple’s forecourt have uncovered the remnants of an ancient *tell* (occupational mound) with an extremely long occupation sequence stretching back to the Neolithic period². Very little is known of the history of Baalbek before the Roman period, when it was elevated by Augustus to the rank of Roman Colony under the name *Colonia Julia Augusta Felix Heliopolitana* in 16 BCE.

It is possible that construction of the grand Temple of Jupiter Heliopolitanus started soon thereafter and continued almost without interruption for the

¹ UNESCO World Heritage Center, On-line resource: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/294/>, last accessed January 8th, 2026.

² Margarethe Van Ess, Klaus Rheidt (2014), *Baalbek - Heliopolis: 10.000 Jahre Stadtgeschichte*, Berlin: Verlag Philipp von Zabern.

following three centuries. Ultimately, the Temple of Jupiter became one of the largest temples in the classical world, perhaps only surpassed by the temple of Hadrian at Cyzicus. Today six of its giant Corinthian columns (out of an original 54) still tower 20 meters high above the site, dominating the skyline for miles all around.

The adjacent Temple of Bacchus, slightly smaller but exceptionally well-preserved; built in the mid-2nd century CE, remains one of the best-preserved Roman temples to have survived from antiquity. A smaller round Temple of Venus (early 3rd century) once graced the complex's outskirts, and coins attest to a now-lost Temple of Mercury on a nearby hill.

At its height in the 2nd and 3rd centuries CE, Baalbek's sanctuary drew reverence across the empire, competing with other important near-Eastern sanctuaries such as Jerusalem, Palmyra, and Damascus.

With the rise of Christianity, the pagan temples gradually fell into disuse. In the late 4th or early 5th century, a Byzantine Basilica church was built within the temple precinct. By 634 CE, Baalbek fell to the Arab armies and its ancient name was revived (appearing as *Ba'labakk* on early Islamic coins³). Under the Umayyads, a mosque was established in the town (likely on the site of the former Roman forum). The vast temple compound, too, was repurposed as a fortress during the Middle Ages, suffering greatly in the following centuries from both warfare and natural events. Stones from the derelict temples were reused to strengthen the fortifications, especially in Crusader and Mamluk times when Baalbek – often called *al-Qalaa* (“the Fortress”) – served as a strategic stronghold protecting the route from the Mediterranean coast to Damascus.

Even in ruins, Baalbek inspired awe, giving rise to innumerable legends concerning the temple's builders and antiquity. Thus, the 6th century Chronicle of Malalas attributed the temple's construction to King Solomon, believing only a miraculous builder could have erected it. Later legends went further, ascribing Baalbek's first construction to biblical figures like Cain or giants under Nimrod, reflecting the popular view that the colossal megalithic platform upon which the temples later stood must belong to a primeval age long preceding the Romans.

³ Wolfgang Schulze (2022), “The Standing Caliph coins of Ba'labakk”, in *Studia Numismatica et Islamica in Honorem Lutz Ilisch*, Berlin: Wasmuth & Zohlen Verlag, pp. 78-95.

Baalbek – The Epigraphic Sources

Alternative researchers have often pointed to the seeming absence of Roman or contemporaneous literary sources on the construction of the Baalbek temple complex as evidence of its pre-Roman origin.

In this respect, it is essential to distinguish between the construction of the temples themselves – whose Roman origin is firmly established on stylistic grounds – and the construction of the megalithic platform and enclosure walls upon which those temples rest.

With regard to the construction of the Temples of Jupiter and Bacchus themselves, the relative scarcity of epigraphic evidence may plausibly be explained as the consequence of a *damnatio memoriae*, should responsibility for their dedication have lain with a “disgraced” emperor such as Nero or Domitian. That this may indeed have been the case is suggested by a graffito inscribed at the top of a column drum and dated to 60 CE⁴, which appears to indicate that construction of the Temple of Jupiter began under Nero and was subsequently completed, perhaps during the reign of Domitian. Further support for this hypothesis is provided by the peg holes visible on several surviving pediment blocks of the Temple of Jupiter. These holes would originally have held large bronze letters forming a dedicatory inscription. The presence of a second set of peg holes on the same blocks strongly suggests that this inscription was altered in antiquity, consistent with the deliberate erasure or replacement of an earlier imperial dedication following an official act of *damnatio memoriae*⁵.

The *Chronicle of Malalas*, generally dated to the seventh century CE, attributes the construction of the temples of Baalbek to Antoninus Pius (138-161 CE), although the passage in question likely refers only to the Temple of Bacchus. Coins from the reign of Septimius Severus (193-211 CE) depict the completed temple standing on a fully finished podium, whereas two completed temples appear on coins dating to the reign of emperor Valerian (253-260 CE)⁶.

⁴ IGLS 2733.

⁵ Holger Wienholz (2014), “Geschichte Baalbecks in römischer Zeit”, in M. Van Ess and K. Rheidt (Editors), *Baalbek: 10,000 Jahre Stadtgeschichte*, 2014, cit., p. 151.

⁶ Theodore Mionnet (1822), *Description de Medailles Antiques, Grecques Et Romaines*, vol. V, Paris, p. 304.

Figure 3. Coin from the reign of Septimius Severus (193-211 CE) depicting the temple of Heliopolis (Baalbek). Inscription on front: SEVERVS PIVS AVG. Back: O M H / COL HEL [Iovi Optimo Maximo Heliopolitano]. Courtesy: Onlinesammlung der Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin: [2355436](https://www.smb.museum/numismatik/objekt/2355436).

Figure 4. Coin from the reign of Valerian (253-260 CE), showing the two completed temples of Jupiter and Bacchus. Inscription on front: IMP CAES P LIC VALERIANVS AVG. Back: COL HEL [Colonia Heliopolis]. Courtesy: Classical Numismatic Group, <https://www.cngcoins.com/Coin.aspx?CoinID=44885>

A 6th century document, known as the *Oracle of Baalbek*, part of an anonymous apocalyptic composition written in Greek, contains a further reference to the building of the temples of Baalbek under three kings, Antiochus, Tiberius and Gaius (Caligula), saying that these kings “built up” or, perhaps, “rebuilt” the temples of Heliopolis and the altars of Lebanon⁷.

Neither source makes any explicit distinction between the temples and the underlying platform, suggesting that the construction of the monumental

⁷ Paul. J. Alexander (1967), *The Oracle of Baalbek. The Tiburtine Sybil in Greek Dress*, Washington D.C., Dumbarton Oaks, p. 13, 25 and 43-4.

sanctuary unfolded over several centuries, from the first century BCE to the third century CE.

Baalbek: The Mystery of a Name

Baalbek, the modern name of the site, does not appear until the 5th century CE, when it was first used in a Syriac manuscript of the *Theophany* of Eusebius of Caesarea⁸. For much of the Hellenistic and Roman period, the city was known instead as *Heliopolis*, the “City of the Sun”.

Many have seen in the name *Baalbek* a very ancient semitic place name that only resurfaced in late antiquity to replace the “official” name of Heliopolis imposed by its Greek and Roman rulers. According to Biblical scholar Richard C. Steiner, the origins of the site were Phoenician or Canaanite, as were also the cults practiced at Baalbek⁹.

The precise origin of the name Baalbek (rendered as *B'lbk* in ancient Syriac) remains uncertain. The frequently cited derivation from Baal (“Lord”) and Bekaa (“Valley”), yielding the meaning “Lord of the Valley,” is almost certainly a false etymology and should be abandoned. A more plausible explanation derives the name from the Phoenician *Ba'al Nebeq*, meaning “Lord of the Source”¹⁰, or alternatively from a contraction of the divine names Baal and Bacchus, reflected in the form *Ba'alabakku*¹¹.

Other authors have attempted to link the name of Baalbek with Biblical place names such as *Baalath* (1 Kgs 9:18), *Baal Gad* (Josh 11:17) and *Bikath Aven* (Amos, 1:5), with little to support their theses¹².

Biblical and Semitic linguistics scholar Richard C. Steiner has proposed five distinct Semitic toponyms by which the site may have been known in antiquity. The successive use of these names appears to mirror the rise and fall of Canaanite religion in the region, spanning from the Bronze Age through the Byzantine period. These five toponyms include: (1) *Mbk Nhrm* (Source of the Two Rivers), (2) *Nw't'qb* (Valley of Idolatry), (3) *ykb l'b* (Baal of Weeping),

⁸ Richard C. Steiner (2009), “On the Rise and Fall of Canaanite Religion at Baalbek: A Tale of Five Toponyms,” *Journal of Biblical Literature*, vol. 128, no. 3 (Fall 2009): 507-525, p. 509.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Jona Lendering, “Baalbek, Ras Al-Ain”. On-line resource: <https://www.livius.org/articles/place/heliopolis-baalbek/baalbek-photos/baalbek-ras-al-ain/>, last accessed January 29, 2026.

¹¹ Richard C. Steiner (2009), cit., p. 508

¹² Ibid., p. 507

(4) *ykb Ny* (Spring of Weeping), and (5) *Bvlbk/ Ba'alabakku* (Baal-Bacchus). Taken together, these names appear to reflect a persistent association with fertility-related rituals, water cults, and cycles of death and renewal that characterized the religious landscape of the ancient Near East from the Bronze Age onward.¹³

Figure 5. Artist's impression of a cylinder seal from Mari (2340–2159 BCE). El is enthroned on a mountain. From both sides, rivers flow, as in the Ugaritic poems. Courtesy: פּטמי-עליון. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:A_cylinder_seal_from_Mari_with_a_divine_scene_of_order_and_chaos.jpg

Of particular interest is the first toponym, *Mbk Nhrm* (“Source of the Two Rivers”). This place name is attested as early as the second millennium BCE in Ugaritic texts from the Baal Cycle, where it is associated with the abode of the god El. Additional support for this interpretation comes from an Akkadian cylinder seal from Mari, dated to the third millennium BCE, which depicts the god El enthroned upon a mountain, positioned above the source of two rivers. If this imagery indeed represents El’s dwelling, it implies a spatial hierarchy in which the god’s abode was conceived as an elevated, terrestrial locus, while the “source of the two rivers” lay below, within a subterranean cavern beneath the mountain. As Steiner remarks:

“Baalbek was a natural center for the upper part of the Beqa’a, being located at its highest level, at the source of two important rivers. The two rivers in question are Lebanon’s greatest rivers, the Litani and the Asi (Orontes), which, according to Ellen Churchill Semple, “rise in a swampy, indeterminate watershed

¹³ *Ibid.*, pp. 507-8

near Baalbek at an altitude of 3,500 feet...A more appropriate setting for the abode of gods who represented such material phenomena as rain and tempest, fertility and growth, would be difficult to imagine. Situated near the highest point of the Beqa'a, controlling the watershed between the Orontes River to the north, and the Leontes River to the south, Baalbek combined aspects of a city in a plain with that of a high place, and was thus predestined to become a center of religious worship”¹⁴.

The cult of El appears to have persisted at Baalbek well into the Roman period, when it was assimilated into the cult of Jupiter. A deity named Connaros, closely identifiable with the Canaanite El, is attested in several Roman-period oracular inscriptions from Baalbek. As noted by Richard C. Steiner:

“Connaros is believed to be the epithet of El found in Phoenician 'l qn 'rs ('El, creator or possessor of the earth'), Hittite dEl-ku-ni-ir-ša, or Aramaic 'l qwnr”¹⁵.

This enduring association of Baalbek with El further lends context to early Near Eastern conceptions of the god's dwelling as a liminal, semi-subterranean realm. In this light, references in the Epic of Gilgamesh to the abode of the gods being located in the Forest of Cedars may be understood as mythological allusions to the mountains of Lebanon.

A comparable conception of the abode of the Most High appears in the apocryphal Book of Enoch, where the dwelling-place of YHWH is described in terms strikingly reminiscent of the monumental architecture of Baalbek. In Chapter 14, Enoch recounts his arrival at a walled precinct identified as the dwelling of the Most High, offering the following description – here rendered in modern language by Christian and Barbara Joy o'Brien:

“And I went in, until I reached a wall which seemed to be made of glistening, white stone; it was illuminated by bright lights, and I became frightened. I went in between these bright lights and approached a large house which, similarly, was built of glistening stone. The walls of the house were of interlaced stone blocks, and all these were wholly snow-white, and the ground was covered in snow. And the roof was silhouetted against the stars and the

¹⁴ Ibid., p. 509

¹⁵ Ibid., pp.511-12

brightness of the lights, and round about were fiery sentinels and heavenly rain. And a flaming fire surrounded the walls, and its doors were ablaze with fire.” (1 Enoch 14:9–12 PP¹⁶)

The imagery of a fortified enclosure composed of immense, interlocking stone blocks surrounding a central elevated structure bears a clear resemblance to the outer megalithic enclosure at Baalbek, with the tower-like *Podium I* at its center. The repeated emphasis on the white color and crystal-like appearance of the stone may further be understood as a reference to the luminous nummulitic limestone employed in the sanctuary’s monumental architecture.

In this context, it appears significant that throughout the Persian and early Hellenistic periods Baalbek appears to have been described – and perhaps even defined – by reference to a walled enclosure. The place name *Paradeisos*, or *Trip Paradeisos*, has long been associated with Baalbek, owing to its proximity to the sources of two major rivers, the Orontes and the Leontes (modern Litani). In the Achaemenid Persian context, a *paradeisos* denoted a formally enclosed space, typically surrounding a garden, palace, or royal estate.

Strabo (*Geography*, 16:2.9) and Pliny the Elder (*Natural History*, 5:82) both refer to a locality called *Paradeisos* situated near the source of the Orontes. This may correspond to the enigmatic *Trip Paradeisos*, likewise located near the headwaters of the Orontes and identified by Diodorus Siculus (*Library of History*, 8. 39.1–7) as the site where the treaty bearing the same name was concluded – an agreement that determined the initial division of Alexander the Great’s empire among the Diadochi¹⁷.

It is possible that *Paradeisos* or *Trip Paradeisos* was the name by which Baalbek was known during much of the Persian and early Hellenistic periods, and that this designation continued to be used alongside Heliopolis until at least the early Roman period, as attested by Strabo and Pliny.

Egyptian Connections

It was only in the late Hellenistic period that the city now known as Baalbek acquired the name *Heliopolis*. Such a portentous designation – literally

¹⁶ Translated and paraphrased by Christian and Barbara Joy o’Brien (1999), *The Genius of the Few*, Gloucester: Dianthus Publishing, p. 105.

¹⁷ Mehmet Fatih Yavuz (2011), “A Persian Paradeisos in Byzantion?”, in Hamdi Şahin, Erkan Konyar, Gürkan Ergin, *Studies Presented to Mehmet and Nesrin Özseit*, Sunan & Inan Kiraç Research Institute on Mediterranean Civilizations, pp. 411-22,

the “City of the Sun” – can scarcely have been applied to an insignificant village. Rather, it points to the growing prominence of Baalbek in the Hellenistic period and suggests the presence of an already well-established cult center of at least regional importance.

The possibility of a connection between Baalbek and the Egyptian Heliopolis is further suggested by a passage in Lucian’s *De Dea Syria*, in which the temple and rituals of Baalbek are explicitly described as “Egyptian.” Lucian writes:

“The Phoenicians have another temple, not Assyrian, but Egyptian, which came to Phoenicia from Heliopolis. I have not seen it, but it too is large and ancient.” (Lucian, *De Dea Syria*, 5)¹⁸

Although brief, this testimony is of particular interest for it reflects the ancient connection – whether historical or purely symbolic – of Baalbek with Egypt.

Baalbek and King Solomon

During the Middle Ages, a powerful association emerged between Baalbek and the biblical King Solomon, most likely arising from a misidentification of Baalbek with the biblical city of *Baalath*. As early as the sixth century CE, the Chronicle of Pseudo-Zachariah of Mitylene refers to Baalbek as:

“The Palace of Solomon...the city in the forest of Lebanon, as to which Scripture mentions that Solomon built it and stored arms in it.” (Pseudo-Zachariah, *Historia Ecclesiastica*, III: 5-6)¹⁹

This identification situates Baalbek squarely within a biblical and Solomonic landscape imagined to extend across the mountains of Lebanon.

A similar tradition appears in the writings of Pseudo-Dionysius of Tel-Mahre (8th Century CE), who describes Baalbek as:

“The City of the Sun, which is in Phoenicia, between the mountains of Lebanon and Senir...in it there was a great and

¹⁸ Ted Kaizer (2016), “Lucian on the Temple at Heliopolis”, *The Classical Quarterly*, Vol. 66 , Issue 1 , May 2016, pp. 273 – 285.

¹⁹ Sergey Minov (2010), “The Story of Solomon’s Palace at Heliopolis”, *Le Muséon* 123 (1-2), pp. 61-89.

*massive temple of idols, which, as people used to say, was one of those mighty constructions that Solomon had built*²⁰.

Such accounts reveal how the sheer scale and antiquity of Baalbek's ruins invited attribution to a legendary builder whose wisdom and power were thought commensurate with the monumentality of the site.

Gnostic Traditions

The region surrounding Baalbek also appears to have played a significant role in the Sethian Gnostic tradition from at least late antiquity, when it became associated with the mythical Mount *Seir* and the legendary Cave of Treasures. In the Gnostic treatise known as *The Cave of Treasures* (6th Century CE) we encounter the following account:

“And when Solomon was passing the outskirts of the mountain of Seir, he found there the altars that Pirzaki and Pirzami, and Yozdakar had built. These were those that Nimrod the giant sent to Balaam, the priest of the mountain, because he heard that he was familiar with the signs of the Zodiac. And when they were passing the outskirts of the mountain of Seir, they built there the altars to the Sun. And when Solomon saw it, he built there Heliopolis, the City of the Sun”. (*Cave of Treasures*, 35:18-21)²¹

The reference to three solar altars is striking and may plausibly echo the famous *Trilithon* of Baalbek, whose three colossal stones are the defining feature of the sanctuary's megalithic platform. Equally noteworthy is the text's placement of Mount *Seir* in close proximity to Baalbek. This may reflect a conflation with Mount Hermon, known as *Senir* among the Amorites, and long regarded as a liminal and sacred mountain in Near Eastern tradition²².

Arabic Legends

Medieval Arab authors would later repeat these local traditions linking Solomon and Baalbek, often embellishing them further, but preserving the core

²⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 67

²¹ *Ibid.*, p. 70

²² *Ibid.*, pp. 71-72

perception of the site as a place of immense antiquity whose origins were believed to lie beyond historical memory.

In the 12th Century CE, the Jewish traveler Benjamin of Tudela visited Baalbek and gave the following account of the city in his *Itinerary*:

*“Thence it is half a day’s journey to Baalbec, which is Baalath in the plains of Lebanon, and which Solomon built for the daughter of Pharaoh. The palace is built of large stones, each stone having a length of twenty cubits and a width of twelve cubits, and there are no spaces between the stones. It is said that Ashmedai alone could have put up this building”*²³.

In Islamic tradition, the earliest recorded association of Baalbek with Solomon appears in the works of the twelfth-century geographer Al-Idrisi. In his description of Baalbek and its monuments, al-Idrisi emphasizes both their extraordinary scale and the apparent permanence of their construction:

*“It contains remarkable monuments that due to their height as well as due to the stability of their construction deserve particular mention. We would like to speak about the two amphitheater buildings, one big and one small. It is said about the big one that it was built in the days of Solomon, son of David. And it is marvelous to behold. For its construction were used stones each of them ten cubit long; and one part of the building rests on columns of stunning height”*²⁴.

Comparable Arabic traditions likewise identified Baalbek with the palace said to have been built by Solomon for the Queen of Sheba, thereby assigning the origins of the site to an antiquity far more remote than the Roman period. The otherwise inexplicable construction of the temples and the movement of the enormous stones was attributed to the agency of *Jinns*, demons or spirits.

²³ Benjamin of Tudela, *Itinerary*, Trans. Marcus Nathan Adler, New York: Philip Feldheim, 1907, p. 49.

²⁴ As quoted in S. Minov (2010), “The Story of Solomon’s Palace at Heliopolis”, cit.

Built before the Flood

Figure 6. An early depiction of the ruins of Baalbek by Robert Wood (1717-1771). From the book: The Ruins of Balbec, otherwise Heliopolis in Cœlosyria, London: W. Pickering, 1757, plate XXIV.

As scholarly interest in Baalbek began to intensify in the nineteenth century, few authors expressed serious doubt about the legends surrounding the site or questioned the great antiquity traditionally ascribed to its ruins. When the Scottish traveler and diplomat David Urquhart visited Baalbek in 1860, he recorded a local tradition according to which the colossal temples had been constructed in three distinct phases. Upon asking the local emir, Hangar (Harfush), who had built the ruins, Urquhart expected to hear the familiar Solomonic legend. Instead, he was told:

“There have been three builders; the first was Sanoud, the second was (I have forgotten the name [sic]), and then came the Deluge; after that it was repaired by Solomon.”

Urquhart’s conclusion was that:

“The Builders of Baalbek must have been a people that had attained the highest pinnacle of power and science; and this region must have been the center of their dominion. We are perfectly acquainted with the nations that flourished here or around, and their works; they are the Assyrians, Chaldeans, Medes, Persians, Egyptians, Canaanites, and Jews. These complete the catalogue of ancient empires, and this work is none of theirs”²⁵.

According to oral traditions collected by Michel Alouf in his *History of Baalbek* (1890), Baalbek was widely regarded as one of the most ancient cities in the world. Its construction was sometimes attributed to Cain, said to have built the citadel as a place of refuge for himself and his descendants, after being cursed by God for the murder of his brother Abel. According to the 57th Maronite patriarch of Lebanon, Istifan al-Duwayhi (1630-1704):

“The fortress of Baalbek on Mount Lebanon is the most ancient building in the world; Cain, the son of Adam, built it in the year 133 of the Creation, during a fit of raving madness. He gave it the name of his son Enoch and peopled it with giants who were punished for their iniquities by the Flood”²⁶.

Other Arabic traditions, also reported by Alouf, identified Baalbek as the site where Nimrod erected his Tower of Babel. In one version of the legend, Nimrod – enraged by his failure to challenge God – attempted to ascend to heaven in a chariot drawn by four birds. This final, disastrous effort ended when the contraption fell upon Mount Hermon, where Nimrod’s mutilated body was discovered and buried. Another Arabic manuscript from Baalbek recounts that, after the Flood, Nimrod ruled over Lebanon and dispatched giants to rebuild the fortress of Baalbek, dedicating it to Baal, the solar deity of the Moabites:

Other traditions, still, associate Baalbek with the ascent of the prophet Elijah into heaven.

Taken together, these legends – however fantastical in content – are remarkable for their consistency in one respect: they unanimously place the origins of Baalbek in a primordial past, far preceding the Roman period.

²⁵ David Urquhart (1860), *The Lebanon (Mount Souria): A History and Diary*, London: Thomas Catley Newby, p. 369.

²⁶ Michel M. Alouf (1905), *History of Baalbek*, 7th Edition, Beirut: Imprimerie des Belles Lettres, p. 28.

Baalbek and the Lost Temple of Elagabal

Given the central role that Baalbek would later assume in late antique and medieval legends, the relative silence of Classical authors regarding its temples and the nature of the cult practiced there is all the more puzzling. One possible solution to this anomaly has been proposed by the historian Warwick Ball, who has suggested that the great sanctuary of Baalbek may in fact be identical with the otherwise elusive temple of Emesa²⁷.

The temple of Elagabal near Emesa was among the most important sanctuaries of antiquity and is attested in dozens of literary and historical sources. It was the center of a powerful meteoritic cult focused on a sacred black stone (baetyl). By the late second century CE, the priestly dynasty of Emesa had risen to extraordinary prominence. The emperor Septimius Severus (193-211 CE) married Julia Domna, a member of the Emesene royal house, and from this union was born Caracalla. Following Caracalla's assassination in 218 CE, another scion of the same dynasty, the fourteen-year-old Elagabalus, high priest of the sun god Elagabal (Latinized Heliogabalus), was proclaimed emperor in an army revolt orchestrated by his grandmother Julia Maesa.

Yet despite its immense wealth, prestige, and political influence, the temple of Emesa has never been located archaeologically. No trace of a sanctuary commensurate with its literary fame has been found in the city of Emesa (modern Homs, in Syria) itself. This absence is striking. Had such a colossal sanctuary – one rivaling those of Damascus, Palmyra, or Jerusalem – stood within the city, it is difficult to imagine that no vestiges would have survived. By contrast, the monumental sanctuary of Baalbek, one of the most colossal temple complexes of the ancient world, is almost entirely ignored by the Classical literary sources.

Might the solution of this long-standing paradox lie, as Warwick Ball suggests, in the possibility that the monumental sanctuary of Baalbek was none other than the lost temple of Elagabal, the supreme cult center of Emesene Baal?

²⁷ Warwick Ball (2000), *Rome in the East: The Transformation of an Empire*, London: Routledge, pp. 37-47.

Figure 7. Coin from the reign of Elagabalus (218-222 CE) depicting the temple of Emesene Baal as a giant decastyle temple. Courtesy: <https://www.coin.com/indexes/?find=242>

As Ball has observed, no ancient source explicitly states that the temple of Emesa was located within the city of Emesa itself. Rather, Classical authors frequently refer to it more vaguely as the “Temple of the Emesenes” or the “Temple of Emesene Baal,” language that allows for a sanctuary located within Emesene territory but outside the urban center.

Although in Roman times Baalbek was administratively dependent on the Colony of Berytus (modern Beirut in Lebanon), these merely jurisdictional aspects do not exclude the possibility that the temple of Baalbek was itself administered by the Emesene priesthood. Indeed, a Latin inscription from Baalbek explicitly names the Emesene king Sohaemus (54-73 CE), son of Sampsigeramus, as “Great King” and “Patron of the Colony”²⁸.

If Baalbek was indeed the lost temple of Elagabal, this identification would also illuminate the nature of the cults practiced there. The focus of the Emesene cult was a sacred black stone of meteoritic origin, carried in solemn processions from Emesa to the sanctuary of Elagabal. The name Elagabal derives from the Aramaic *’ēlāhā gābālā*, “Lord of the Mountain,” a title that closely recalls earlier Akkadian and Canaanite conceptions of the god El. It would be certainly more fitting that the temple of such a mountain god would be located in a place like Baalbek, on the highest point and near the watershed of the Bekaa Valley, than in an alluvial plain far from any mountains like the city of Emesa.

²⁸ Alberto González García (2013), “¿Fue Baalbek el Templo de Heliogábalo?: Nuevas Evidencias”, *El Futuro del Pasado*, n. 4, 2013, pp. 315-338

Elagabal was also identified in antiquity with the Sun, hence the Latinized form Heliogabalus. This solar aspect strengthens the connection with Baalbek-Heliopolis, the “City of the Sun,” and suggests continuity between earlier cults of El and the later Roman cult of Heliogabalus. In this perspective, the extraordinary scale and ambition of the Baalbek sanctuary may be explained not by Roman imperial caprice alone, but by the immense antiquity and religious prestige of a cult whose origins long predated the Roman monumentalization of the sanctuary.

Only the venerable antiquity and religious importance of the cult of El at Baalbek, later turned into that of Heliogabalus (Baal – Helios) in Roman times, could plausibly account for how a seemingly peripheral settlement – far from major trade routes and political centers – came to possess the largest and most colossal temples of the Classical world.

The mystery of Location

Can the very location of the Baalbek temple complex be evidence of its pre-Roman origins and connections with Egypt?

The siting of such an important sanctuary as Baalbek could hardly have been a product of chance. Baalbek lies in close proximity to the sources of the two most important rivers in the entire Levant, the Orontes and the Leontes (modern Litani), yet because of the uncertainty as to the exact location of the sources of the two rivers, even this explanation fails to satisfactorily explain why the temples were built just where they are.

There were certainly many more auspicious and convenient locations in the same area for the construction of a monumental sanctuary than the small and rather insignificant *tell* Baalbek.

Although recent excavations have demonstrated a continuous occupation sequence on the *tell* extending back more than 10,000 years into the Pre-Pottery Neolithic – roughly contemporary with Göbekli Tepe – there is no conclusive evidence that monumental structures or temples existed on the *tell* prior to the Hellenistic and Roman periods²⁹.

The limited Bronze Age architectural remains identified to date are modest in scale and, moreover, do not share the same orientation as the later sanctuary. A sloping wall, tentatively dated to the Iron Age or possibly the Hellenistic period,

²⁹ Margarethe Van Ess, Klaus Rheidt (2014), cit.

appears instead to belong to a fortification rather than to any cultic or monumental structure³⁰.

The *tell* itself was likely never more than a small, fortified settlement, approximately 100 meters in diameter – smaller, in fact, than the area now occupied by the Great Court of the Temple of Jupiter. It is difficult to see how such a modest village, scarcely distinguishable from many others in the Beqaa Valley, could by itself account for the decision to erect the largest temple complex of the Roman world at this precise location.

The Roman engineers responsible for the design of the Baalbek sanctuary were confronted with formidable technical challenges. In order to create a level forecourt measuring approximately 125 meters square in front of the temple, they first had to overcome the pronounced difference in elevation between the surrounding plain and the summit of the *tell*. Achieving this required the construction of colossal substructures whose volume ultimately exceeded that of the temple buildings themselves.

Compounding this difficulty was the inherently unstable nature of the ground beneath the sanctuary, composed of heterogeneous sedimentary layers overlying a heavily karstified bedrock. From an engineering perspective, the site was singularly ill-suited to monumental construction. By contrast, the Sheikh Abdallah hill immediately to the southeast would have provided a far more favorable location: its geology consists of stable, compact nummulitic limestone, and it lies closer to the known quarrying areas.

It was likely in response to these unfavorable foundation conditions that the builders resorted to the use of exceptionally large stone blocks, designed to stabilize the subsoil and, in some areas, to reach down to extraordinary depths so that the foundations could rest directly upon bedrock. Although no precise estimate exists for the total volume of stone employed in the foundations of the acropolis alone, even a conservative volumetric calculation suggests that it may well have exceeded 750,000 metric tons³¹.

³⁰ Daniel Lohmann (2017a), *Das Heiligtum des Jupiter Heliopolitanus in Baalbek*, Orient Archäologie, 38, Rahden, Westf., Verlag Marie Leidorf, pp. 111-117 and 143-144.

³¹ The platform of the Jupiter Temple measured approximately 95 meter wide by 115 long, with a height of 13 meters above ground and at least as much below ground, with a total volume of 284,050 cubic meters, equivalent to 766,000 metric tons assuming a specific weight of 2.7 tons/cubic meter for limestone. This is not including the substructures and foundations underneath the Great Court, which would certainly have elevated this figure above 1,000,000 metric tons – a volume comparable to many Egyptian pyramids.

This immense investment of material and labor is difficult to explain on purely practical grounds. Had a more suitable site been selected – only a few hundred meters to the south or east – much of this engineering effort could have been drastically reduced, if not avoided altogether. The decision to persist with such an unfavorable location therefore appears to have been informed eminently by sacred or symbolic considerations.

There is likewise no scholarly consensus regarding the reason for the anomalous orientation of the sanctuary with respect to true north. Neither the sanctuary nor its temples follow a cardinal north–south axis, nor do they align with any immediately recognizable astronomical markers such as solstitial sunrises or lunar standstills. Instead, the entire complex is oriented along a markedly unusual axis, approximately 12 degrees west of true north.

Figure 8. Satellite picture showing the orientation of the Baalbek temple complex with respect to the cardinal directions. After Carlotto, M. (2021)/ Apple Maps.

Figure 9. Orientation of the Baalbek temple complex 12 degrees west of true North. [1] Temple of Jupiter, [2] Megalithic enclosure wall (Podium 2), [3] Great Court, [4] Hexagonal Court. After Magli, G. (2016)

Various explanations have been proposed to account for this deviation. Among them, Giulio Magli of the Politecnico di Milano University has suggested a possible stellar alignment toward the rising of the Pleiades³². While intriguing, this hypothesis is inherently sensitive to the chronological framework adopted, owing to the effects of axial precession, and does not readily accommodate the protracted, multi-century construction history of the Jupiter sanctuary.

As such, the sanctuary's orientation remains unexplained, reinforcing the impression that its layout was governed by considerations no longer readily accessible through conventional archaeological or astronomical models.

Daniel Lohmann, author of one of the most recent and comprehensive architectural studies of the Baalbek temple complex, attributes the sanctuary's anomalous orientation to its alignment toward a nearby water reservoir marking the terminus of a Roman aqueduct³³.

This interpretation fails to account for the fact that several earlier structural elements on the *tell*, tentatively dated to the Iron Age or early Hellenistic period and therefore predating Roman intervention, appear to share the same anomalous orientation. The persistence of this alignment across different construction phases strongly suggests that it was inherited rather than imposed during the Roman period.

³² Giulio Magli (2016), "Archeoastronomy and the chronology of the temple of Jupiter at Baalbek", <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1606.05888>, last accessed January 9th, 2026.

³³ Lohmann (2017a), p. 153.

Moreover, it is difficult to conceive that the most monumental sanctuary of the Roman world would have been deliberately oriented toward a modest water reservoir situated at the base of an otherwise insignificant hillock. Such a utilitarian reference point seems wholly inadequate to explain an orientation that governed the layout of the entire sacred complex over several centuries, further reinforcing the impression that the sanctuary's alignment was dictated by earlier, non-Roman considerations whose significance has since been lost.

During the 1950s and 1960s, the Lebanese-Armenian archaeologist Haroutoune Kalayan proposed that the location of the Baalbek sanctuary was determined by the presence of a deep natural crevice along one side of the acropolis. This fissure, he argued, descended to the water table at a depth of approximately 50 meters below the ancient floor level and terminated in what he described as a small "rock-cut altar." Such a feature, Kalayan suggested, may have held ritual significance that predated the Roman monumental phase³⁴.

A closely comparable phenomenon is described in the third century CE by Lucian of Samosata in his account of another renowned Syrian sanctuary at Hierapolis Bambyke, located near the Euphrates River. According to Lucian, a deep crevice within the sanctuary was annually filled with offerings of seawater, a ritual commemorating the miraculous retreat of the waters following the Great Flood³⁵. The striking parallel between these accounts suggests that such chthonic fissures – linking the surface world to subterranean waters – formed part of a broader Near Eastern sacred tradition, in which natural geological features were imbued with profound cosmological and ritual meaning.

The precise location of this supposed crevice at Baalbek appears to have been lost following Haroutoune Kalayan's excavations and his brief description of the feature in a 1969 publication³⁶. It was not until 2008 that the feature was rediscovered and systematically investigated by members of the German–Lebanese expedition at Baalbek, bringing an end to a mystery that had persisted for nearly six decades³⁷. The results, however, proved far more prosaic than Kalayan's original interpretation: The excavations revealed a simple vertical well, most likely of Arabic or medieval date, descending to the expected depth

³⁴ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 140-143.

³⁵ Lucian, *De Dea Syria*, Ch. 13

³⁶ Haroutoune Kalayan (1969a), "Notes on the Heritage of Baalbeck and the Beka'a, in *Cultural Resources in Lebanon*, Beirut College for Women, p. 52.

³⁷ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 140-143

of approximately 50 meters and terminating in a water-filled karst cavity³⁸. No evidence was found for the rock-cut altar described by Kalayan, nor for any associated subterranean cult chambers. It remains possible that minor rock cuttings or preparatory features near the base of the well were interpreted by Kalayan as ritual installations³⁹. Indeed, it is doubtful whether Kalayan himself ever reached the bottom of the shaft, and he may instead have relied on reports provided by local workmen.

Nevertheless, it is difficult to explain how an archaeologist of Kalayan's experience could have mistaken a relatively conventional well for a natural crevice of profound cultic significance, allegedly serving as a conduit to a sacred subterranean water source beneath the sanctuary.

With Kalayan's crevice thus reduced to a relatively late water well, and in the absence of any evidence for the rock-cut altar or deep subterranean cult installations he envisaged, little remains of this hypothesis to account for either the choice of location or the anomalous orientation of the Baalbek temple complex. The question of why such an extraordinary sanctuary was established at this precise and technically problematic site therefore remains unresolved.

Might the ancient Greek name of the site – *Heliopolis* – provide a missing clue to this enduring puzzle? According to Macrobius (ca. 400 CE), the principal cult statue of Jupiter Heliopolitanus venerated at Baalbek was said to have been brought from the Egyptian Heliopolis during the reign of a pharaoh named *Senepos* – possibly to be identified with Snefru of the Fourth Dynasty (ca. 2613–2584 BCE)⁴⁰.

Egyptian Heliopolis was the capital of the Thirteenth Nome of Lower Egypt and the seat of one of antiquity's most venerable religious traditions. From Predynastic times onward it was associated with a meteoritic cult, reaching its

³⁸ According to Daniel Lohmann, the shaft begins with a square section measuring approximately 130 × 130 cm, lined with small masonry blocks and extending to a depth of roughly 30 meters. At this point, it cuts through a layer of massive stone blocks before continuing entirely within the natural bedrock. Lohmann does not address the origin or function of these large stone blocks. Their considerable depth suggests that they may form part of a substantial foundation, yet their location does not appear to correspond to any known architectural element of the sanctuary.

³⁹ Kalayan (1969a), p. 52

⁴⁰ Macrobius describes the principal cult statue at Baalbek as “*a bearded man, his right hand raised with a flame in the manner of a charioteer, and in the left he holds a thunderbolt and spikes*” (Saturnalia I.23.10–13). This iconography closely conforms to canonical Greco-Roman representations of Jupiter, strongly suggesting that the statue observed or reported by Macrobius was not the original cult image, but a later replacement, adapted to Roman religious conventions.

zenith during the Old Kingdom and continuing as a major center of learning well into the Late Period. It was the principal cult center of the sun god Ra, whose great temple housed the sacred Benben stone – a conical meteoritic object symbolizing creation and the emergence of the primeval mound. Today, little remains of this once-great sanctuary, much of it having vanished beneath the urban expansion of modern Cairo, save for a solitary obelisk standing as a silent witness to its former prominence.

If Warwick Ball's proposed identification of the Baalbek sanctuary with the temple of Emesene Baal is correct, then Baalbek itself may likewise have functioned as the center of a meteoritic cult. In that case, the name Heliopolis would not be a superficial Hellenistic affectation, but a deliberate evocation of a far older religious lineage – linking Baalbek to Egyptian solar theology.

What is particularly striking, however, is the apparent geodetic relationship linking Baalbek, Heliopolis, and the Great Pyramid of Giza. It can be demonstrated that the Temple of Jupiter at Baalbek lies almost exactly four degrees of latitude north and five degrees of longitude east of the Great Pyramid.

In the context of the long-assumed cultural and religious connections between Baalbek and Egyptian Heliopolis, this raises the possibility that the placement of the sanctuary was informed by a broader, large-scale geographical framework – one that extended far beyond local topography and Roman urban planning, and may instead reflect inherited cosmological or symbolic principles of much greater antiquity⁴¹.

Only at this particular latitude does the spatial relationship between the Great Pyramid of Giza and Baalbek yield an azimuth approaching 45 degrees. Significantly, an almost identical azimuth also links the Great Pyramid with the Sun Temple of Re at Heliopolis.

When plotted on a Mercator projection map, a straight line drawn from the Great Pyramid of Giza at an azimuth of 45 degrees intersects every meridian of longitude and every parallel of latitude at a constant angle, advancing in uniform

⁴¹ The coordinates of the Great Pyramid are 29.97197° N, 31.13414° E, while those of the Baalbek sanctuary are 34.00704° N, 36.20418° E. This places Baalbek 4.02787° north and 5.07004° east of Giza, corresponding to deviations of approximately 0.7 percent in latitude and 1.4 percent in longitude. When translated into linear distances, these discrepancies amount to roughly 765 meters in the north–south direction and 1,299 meters east–west, across a total separation of approximately 654.8 kilometers between the two sites

increments of one degree of latitude for every one degree of longitude . Such a line – projected northeastward from Giza – passes directly through Heliopolis, continues across the eastern Mediterranean near the ancient city of Tyre, and terminates at Baalbek. Extending this same line further to the northeast, it can be shown that Mount Ararat also lies close to its trajectory.

Figure 10. Alignment between the Great Pyramid of Giza, Heliopolis, Tyre and Baalbek. Courtesy: Google Earth.

Such a line may have been deliberately incorporated into the design of the Baalbek sanctuary itself, as its overall orientation – approximately 45 degrees east of true north – is echoed in the alignment of one of the facets of the hexagonal court. If this correspondence is intentional, it would imply that the planners of the Baalbek temple complex possessed a remarkably accurate understanding of terrestrial geometry, including reliable methods for determining latitude and longitude over very large distances.

Taken further, this possibility raises the provocative suggestion that Baalbek, together with the Great Pyramid of Giza and Heliopolis, may have functioned as reference points within a much broader geodetic framework – perhaps even as part of a systematic survey of the Near East conceived in deep antiquity.

If one assumes – purely as a working hypothesis – that this putative survey originally achieved perfect alignment between Giza and Baalbek, then the present deviation may be examined in light of continental drift. The current misalignment amounts to approximately 765 meters in the north–south direction and 1,299 meters east–west. Baalbek lies close to the major tectonic boundary separating the African Plate from the Arabian Plate, known as the Dead Sea Rift, itself a continuation of the Red Sea Rift and the African Rift Valley. Both plates are known to be migrating generally toward the north or north-northeast.

Estimating past plate motion is notoriously complex, and velocities are neither uniform nor constant over geological time. Modern GPS measurements indicate a relative plate motion of approximately 4–5 mm per year between the Lebanon and Anti-Lebanon ranges⁴², while the University of Tokyo’s plate motion calculator yields an absolute northward velocity of roughly 8 mm per year for the Arabian Plate at the latitude of Baalbek⁴³. Applied directly, such a rate would place the hypothetical original alignment at approximately 94,500 years before present. However, other datasets suggest that continental drift rates can vary widely, with values ranging from 2.5 to 7.5 cm per year⁴⁴. Using the upper bound of this range would instead place a perfect alignment closer to 10,000 years ago – coincident with the end of the last Ice Age and the onset of major cultural transformations across the Near East.

A further attempt to explain the sanctuary’s anomalous orientation has been advanced by researcher Mark Carlotto. In *Before Atlantis* (2021), Carlotto proposes that Baalbek’s axis – approximately 12 degrees west of true north, and lacking any obvious astronomical or cultural justification – may reflect orientation toward a former position of the North Pole, the so-called “Greenland Pole,” hypothesized to have been located at 79.5° N, 63.75° W. According to this model, Baalbek would be one of several dozen archaeological sites oriented toward this earlier pole position.

⁴² Francisco Gomez, Gebran Karam, Mohamad Khawlie, et al. (2007), “Global Positioning System measurements of strain accumulation and slip transfer through the restraining bend along the Dead Sea fault system in Lebanon”, *Geophysical Journal International*, Vol. 168, Issue 3, March 2007, pp. 1021–1028

⁴³ http://ofgs.aori.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~okino/rate_calc_new2021.cgi, last accessed January 9, 2026.

⁴⁴ Glenn Elert, *The Physics Factbook*, “Speed of the Continental Plates”, On-line resource: <https://hypertextbook.com/facts/1997/ZhenHuang.shtml>, last accessed January 9, 2026.

Figure 11. Orientation of Baalbek and Jerusalem Temple Mount (Western Wall) with respect to the Greenland pole (Courtesy: Mark Carlotto/ Apple Maps). Note the same anomalous orientation 12 degrees west of North.

Carlotto further notes that the Temple Mount in Jerusalem, oriented approximately 11.5 degrees west of north, would likewise have been cardinally aligned with the Greenland Pole between roughly 130,000 and 85,000 years ago. That the two largest megalithic temple platforms in the Near East – Baalbek and Jerusalem – should share such a similar anomalous orientation, while also displaying notable architectural parallels, including the use of immense stone blocks, is at the very least striking. Additional Lebanese sanctuaries, including the megalithic temples of Niha and Hosn Niha, reportedly exhibit comparable orientations. As Carlotto observes, this “*again raises the question of the extent to which Roman and earlier civilizations built over preexisting sites, preserving orientations that had long since lost their original cosmological referent*”⁴⁵.

Taken together, these observations suggest that the location and orientation of the Baalbek sanctuary were unlikely to have been accidental. Whether or not one accepts the more far-reaching implications of prehistoric global surveying or pole-shift models, the evidence points to a persistent pattern of inherited geodetic alignments. Baalbek appears to participate in a broader landscape of alignments linking major sacred sites characterized by megalithic architecture – relationships that remain difficult to reconcile with purely Roman or local explanations, and which may instead reflect a much older system of sacred geography whose underlying logic still eludes archaeological explanation.

While local traditions, mythic associations, and the very location and orientation of the Baalbek temple complex all point compellingly toward a pre-

⁴⁵ Mark Carlotto (2022), *Beyond Atlantis: Vestiges of the World’s Lost Civilizations*, p. 131.

Roman origin of the site, more than a century of archaeological investigation has yet to produce conclusive material evidence to substantiate this hypothesis. Since the first German excavations of 1898–1905, and despite the abundance of alternative theories, no unequivocal proof has emerged that securely dates the origins of the sanctuary itself to a period earlier than the Roman era.

If such evidence exists, it can only be sought through a careful and systematic examination of the sanctuary's long and complex construction history – above all, through a detailed analysis of the architectural stratification of the Jupiter sanctuary and its megalithic platform. Only by disentangling the successive building phases preserved within this extraordinary monument can the question of its origins be meaningfully addressed.

This will be the objective of the following section.

Part II – The Construction Sequence of the Temples

Figure 12. View of the temples of Baalbek with the Temple of Bacchus in the foreground. © Marco M. Vigato.

The Ruins of Baalbek

Rising from the fertile plain of the Beqaa Valley in eastern Lebanon, the ruins of Baalbek rank among the most extraordinary monumental complexes of the ancient world. Dominated by the colossal Temple of Jupiter, Baalbek preserves the largest temple ruins ever constructed in the Roman Empire and incorporates stone blocks of a size unmatched anywhere else in antiquity.

Archaeologically, Baalbek is best known for its Roman ruins, erected between the first century BCE and the late fourth century CE. Beneath their soaring columns and lavish sculptural decoration, however, lies a massive megalithic platform whose origin, construction sequence, age, and purpose remain a matter of intense scholarly debate.

The Jupiter sanctuary was the focal point of ancient Baalbek. It was arranged in a vast ceremonial layout: a grand stairway and Propylaea (monumental gate) led to a Hexagonal Forecourt, which opened onto the Great Court – an immense

plaza with altars – and finally the towering Temple of Jupiter itself. All were built on high stone platforms supported by massive, vaulted substructures, raising the sanctuary above the level of the surrounding plain. In particular, the podium of the Jupiter Temple was constructed with some of the largest building blocks ever hewn: a row of three megaliths known as the *Trilithon* forms part of the podium’s retaining wall, each block weighing on the order of 750–800 tons. How ancient builders quarried, transported, and lifted these stones is still not fully understood, contributing to Baalbek’s enduring mystery.

Equally impressive is the sheer scale of the complex: the sanctuary’s stone platform measured roughly 285 by 120 meters, making it larger than many imperial fora in Rome. This ambitious monumental design reflected the city’s growing importance as a pilgrimage center, where Jupiter Heliopolitanus was worshipped as a syncretic form of the Semitic sky-god *Baal*.

The First Archaeological Explorations (1898-1975)

Systematic study of Baalbek began in the modern era. European scholars and antiquarians visited from at least the 17th century, and by the mid-18th century detailed surveys of the ruins were being published – notably *The Ruins of Balbec* (1757) by Robert Wood, which provided the first measured drawings of the temples. In 1898, German Emperor Wilhelm II toured Baalbek and was so impressed that he sponsored a full-scale scientific excavation. The resulting German archaeological mission (1898–1905), led by architects Otto Puchstein and Theodor Wiegand, cleared vast amounts of rubble and conducted comprehensive studies of the temples’ construction phases. They aimed to document the site’s original state and even dismantled later additions (such as medieval and Byzantine modifications) to expose the ancient remains. By 1904 the excavations were largely complete, and although publication was delayed by World War I, Wiegand and his colleagues eventually produced a monumental three-volume report between 1921 and 1925, *Baalbek: Ergebnisse der Ausgrabungen*. This seminal work catalogued Baalbek’s architecture in detail and remains a foundation for all later research.

Under the French Mandate after World War I, excavation and restoration continued: French archaeologists Henri Seyrig, Paul Collart, and Pierre Coupel undertook conservation of the ruins in the 1920s–30s. In doing so, they discovered features that the Germans had missed – for example, beneath the Byzantine church debris they found two ancient altars (a “Monumental Altar” and a “Small Altar”) aligned with the Jupiter temple, evidence of the pre-

Christian cult center at the site. They also re-evaluated the architectural chronology, suggesting (based on stylistic details of the ornamentation) that the Temple of Jupiter was begun in the Augustan era (late 1st century BCE) rather than later, thus adjusting Wiegand's original timeline. The French archaeologists even raised a few fallen columns of the Great Court and repaired the Propylaea stairway – early examples of heritage restoration at Baalbek.

In the 1960s and 70s, Lebanese archaeologists from the Department of Antiquities conducted further excavations. Professor Haroutoune Kalayan, an engineer-archaeologist, led digs in various areas around the temple complex to explore previously neglected sectors. These salvage excavations uncovered a colonnaded portico and a small theatre on the periphery of the site, indicating the extent of the ancient city around the temples. Unfortunately, much of this work went unpublished, as efforts were cut short by the outbreak of the Lebanese Civil War in 1975. One outcome was Friedrich Ragette's book *Baalbek* (1980), a richly illustrated synthesis of the site's history and monuments. Ragette had worked closely with Kalayan before the war, incorporating some of Kalayan's insights into the book. His volume became a standard introduction, helping to keep scholarly attention on Baalbek during the war years when fieldwork had halted.

Recent Investigations (1997-Present)

Following the civil war, archaeological research at Baalbek resumed with international collaboration. In 1997, a Lebanese–German team (the German Archaeological Institute, DAI, in partnership with Lebanon's Directorate General of Antiquities) began new excavations and surveys. A major goal of the post-war research program, launched in 2001 under Dr. Margarete van Ess (DAI), was to investigate the origins and development of Baalbek's sanctuary – from its Bronze Age foundations to the Islamic/Ottoman period. This comprehensive approach has yielded important discoveries. Deep excavations and geomorphological studies have confirmed the presence of an ancient *tell* (occupation mound) beneath the Roman courts, with cultural layers going back to around 7000 BCE⁴⁶. Meanwhile, architectural historians have revisited Baalbek's construction techniques using modern technology. For example, recent studies by Daniel Lohmann and colleagues have examined the massive podium and platform of the Jupiter temple in detail, revealing new clues about its phased construction. Lohmann's work suggests that the podium's layout may

⁴⁶ Van Ess (2014), pp. 26-30.

preserve elements of an earlier temple or sanctuary⁴⁷. Intriguingly, he and others have noted parallels between Baalbek's masonry and King Herod's famous stone building projects at Jerusalem and in the Levant, hinting that the initial stage of the temple's podium could have been laid in the late first century BCE, before the site was fully incorporated into the Roman Empire⁴⁸. These hypotheses remain under debate, but they highlight unresolved questions about who conceived the megalithic platform and for what purpose. The German-Lebanese missions have also employed geophysical surveying and 3D modeling, not only to document the standing ruins but to test engineering possibilities for moving the giant blocks. In 2014, DAI researchers made a headline-grabbing discovery when they uncovered an even larger monolith in Baalbek's ancient quarry – a stone block measuring $19.6 \times 6 \times 5.5$ m and weighing an estimated 1,650 tons, the biggest ever found from antiquity⁴⁹. This prodigious block, intended for the temple podium but left unused (likely due to a flaw in the stone), dramatically illustrates the extraordinary ambitions and capabilities of Baalbek's builders.

Unresolved Questions

Despite over a century of research, scholars and independent researchers continue to debate the origin of the megalithic platform. No ancient texts definitively explain the rationale or techniques behind the *Trilithon's* construction; Roman engineers left no written record of how they achieved these feats. The result is an academic puzzle that inspires both rigorous investigation and imaginative theories. On the one hand, the prevailing archaeological view attributes the *Trilithon* and podium construction to the Roman (Julio-Claudian) era, noting that its drafted-margin stonework and construction style align with other Roman projects of the Augustan age. On the other hand, the sheer scale of the stones and certain anomalies in the podium design have led researchers to posit a multi-phase building history. Furthermore, engineering questions linger regarding how these blocks were moved from the quarry to the temple's site. Various hypotheses (from massive

⁴⁷ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 127-132.

⁴⁸ Daniel Lohmann (2011), "Master, look at the size of those stones! Look at the size of those buildings! 1 Analogies in Construction Techniques Between the Temples at Heliopolis (Baalbek) and Jerusalem", *Levant*, 43 (1), April 2011, pp. 38-50. See also Lohmann (2017a), pp. 146-152.

⁴⁹ Rachel Nuwer (2014), "The Largest Manmade Block Ever Was Just Discovered in Lebanon", *Smithsonian Magazine*, December 3, 2014. On-line resource: <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/largest-manmade-block-ever-carved-was-just-discovered-lebanon-180953518/>, last accessed January 30th, December 3, 2014. On-line resource: <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/largest-manmade-block-ever-carved-was-just-discovered-lebanon-180953518/>, last accessed January 30th, 2026.

earth ramps and rollers to sophisticated pulley systems) have been proposed, but none are definitively proven, leaving a gap in our understanding of ancient technology at Baalbek. Medieval legends attributed the construction to superhuman beings (giants or djinn), and even modern popular writers have speculated wildly on alien assistance or lost civilizations.

The Architecture of the Jupiter Sanctuary

Even today and from a distance, arriving from Beirut, one of the first sights that one catches of Baalbek are the six still standing columns of the Temple of Jupiter rising to a height of almost 40 meters above the surrounding plain (the columns themselves are 23 meters high, like an eight-story building).

The main Sanctuary of Jupiter at Baalbek rises upon a vast artificial platform with the enormous dimensions of 338 by 144 meters. The complex is organized into four principal architectural components, each of which will be examined in detail in the following sections: A monumental entrance gateway (*Propylaea*), the Hexagonal Forecourt, a large open colonnaded courtyard preceding the temple (*Great Court*), and the Temple of Jupiter itself.

Figure 13. Groundplan of the Baalbek temple complex after T. Wiegand (1921), *Baalbek: Ergebnisse der Ausgrabungen und Untersuchungen in den Jahren 1898 bis 1905, 1921-25*, vol. 1, plate 17.

Figure 14. Artist's reconstruction of the Baalbek temple complex in the late 2nd Century CE. After Jean-Claude Golvin, 2000.

The Propylaea

The Sanctuary of Jupiter is entered through a monumental set of *Propylaea*, flanked by massive towers and extending over a frontage of more than 72 meters. These propylaea originally opened onto a large semicircular plaza, theater-like in form, within which stood a substantial altar or colonnaded structure and several ancillary monuments, now preserved only at foundation level. Access to the acropolis today is provided by a modern stairway, replacing the ancient approach that was dismantled during the Middle Ages, when the sanctuary was converted into a fortress.

Already at the level of the propylaea, the sequence of distinct construction phases is clearly legible. The foundations rest upon enormous megalithic stone blocks, some exceeding five meters in length, while the upper portions of the gateway and the tower levels above the first floor are constructed from markedly smaller blocks, characterized by less precise jointing. This sharp contrast in masonry technique strongly suggests different construction phases.

Figure 15. The Propylaea of the temple of Jupiter, as seen from the East. © Marco M. Vigato. Notice the large megalithic stone blocks in the foundations of the west tower, compared to the smaller stones above.

The lower courses of the northeastern tower are particularly instructive. They take the form of a podium composed of a lower sloping section inclined at approximately 45 degrees, a vertical middle section, and an upper outward-sloping section, again set at roughly 45 degrees. This tripartite profile closely resembles the design of the megalithic podium of the Temple of Jupiter itself and shows how the megalithic podium might have looked like upon completion.

The façade of the propylaea was originally articulated by twelve monolithic columns of Aswan granite, with a wider central intercolumniation designed to carry a Syrian arch. Inscriptions on the bases of two columns record that their capitals were gilded on the occasion of the visit of Caracalla in 213 CE⁵⁰.

Notably, the upper stories and interior spaces of the towers appear to have remained unfinished, as evidenced by numerous blocks still bearing protective bosses intended for handling during transport.

⁵⁰ Lohmann (2017a), p. 194.

The Hexagonal Court

Figure 16. The hexagonal court of the temple of Jupiter, looking north. © Marco M. Vigato.

Immediately beyond the propylaea lies the Hexagonal Court, one of the most remarkable and architecturally distinctive elements of the Baalbek temple complex. Access from the propylaea was provided by a triple gateway, mirrored by a comparable gateway on the opposite side leading into the Great Court and the Temple of Jupiter beyond, creating a carefully staged processional sequence.

As with the propylaea, the foundation courses and first-story masonry of the Hexagonal Court are constructed from very large stone blocks, though with noticeably less precise cutting and jointing. Numerous reused Roman architectural elements are incorporated into these foundations, including an entablature block measuring approximately four meters in length. This extensive reuse indicates that the Hexagonal Court is a relatively late addition to the complex, most likely dating to the second or third century CE. There is further evidence to suggest that it replaced an earlier rectangular forecourt, which would account for the availability of large quantities of spolia.

Figure 17. Foundations of the Hexagonal Court with reused stone blocks (spolia) and large blocked up doorway leading into possible chamber inside the substructure. Notice the reused entablature block on the left. © Marco M. Vigato.

Several doorways – now blocked – once provided access to interior spaces within the courtyard platform at ground level. These rooms remain poorly understood, having never been systematically cleared or explored, and any reconstruction of their plan must therefore remain purely speculative⁵¹.

The upper-level courtyard was laid out as a precise hexagon, executed with exceptional care. It was originally surrounded by a colonnade of granite columns, now lost except for their pedestal sockets. The geometry of the inner court can nonetheless be reconstructed from the massive monolithic blocks that define its perimeter, each carved with a distinctive triple-stepped profile.

The hexagon is an exceedingly rare form in monumental architecture and, in the context of Baalbek, appears to be unique. For this reason, architectural historian Donald F. Brown proposed that the design may have carried astrological or cosmological significance (Brown, 1939)⁵². A suggestive parallel can be found in the now-destroyed Temple of Bel at Palmyra, where a ceiling relief depicted

⁵¹ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 68-70.

⁵² Donald F. Brown (1939), "The Hexagonal Court at Baalbek", *American Journal of Archaeology*, vol. 43, No. 2, University of Chicago Press, April-June 1939, p. 285.

a hexagonal arrangement of planetary deities distributed both around and within the geometric form. While such connections must be treated cautiously, they nevertheless point to the possibility that the Hexagonal Court embodied a specific planetary symbolism.

The Great Court

Figure 18. View of the Great Court of the Jupiter Sanctuary, with the small altar in the foreground. © Marco M. Vigato.

Passing through the second gateway at the western end of the Hexagonal Court, one enters the Great Court of the Jupiter sanctuary. This vast square precinct, measuring approximately 120 by 125 meters, formed the ceremonial heart of the sanctuary and constituted the principal setting for its ritual and cultic activities. During the Roman period, the court was enclosed on three sides by an imposing colonnade of 186 monolithic columns fashioned from pink Aswan granite. The western side of the court was instead dominated by the monumental stairway ascending to the decastyle façade of the Temple of Jupiter, creating a powerful axial focus that culminated the carefully choreographed processional sequence of the sanctuary.

Excavations conducted since the late 1940s have demonstrated that the Great Court occupies the summit of an ancient *tell* – a prehistoric occupational mound

first settled in the early Neolithic, more than 10,000 years ago, and apparently subject to continuous occupation throughout the Bronze Age, Iron Age, Hellenistic, and Roman periods⁵³.

Two massive altars originally occupied the center of the Great Court, their remains uncovered and meticulously reconstructed during the 1950s following the demolition of the Byzantine Basilica that had encroached upon the central and western portions of the courtyard. Of the two, the smaller altar – positioned directly before the monumental stairway leading to the Temple of Jupiter – is the earlier and incorporates elements of an even older cult installation, indicating a continuity of ritual focus at this precise spot⁵⁴.

Figure 19. Isometric reconstruction of the monumental altar of Baalbek. After Paul Collart and Pierre Coupel (1951), *L’Autel Monumental de Baalbek*.

The second, larger structure – commonly referred to as the *Monumental Altar* – was originally conceived as a colossal masonry cube measuring approximately 17 meters on each side. This extraordinary construction represents a tour de force of megalithic engineering. It contained a complex system of triple, double stairways ascending to the roof, and was built from enormous, tightly

⁵³ Van Ess (2014), pp. 28-30.

⁵⁴ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 122-125.

interlocking stone blocks, some exceeding seven meters in length and weighing more than fifty tons. The altar proper was situated on a platform atop the uppermost terrace of this tower-like structure, affording a commanding vantage point over both the Great Court and the Temple of Jupiter beyond.

Numerous soffit blocks belonging to the monumental altar were recovered during the dismantling of the Byzantine Basilica and are today displayed along the outer walls of the sanctuary. In addition, a fragment of a stone scale model of the altar was discovered, providing valuable insight into its original design. There is also evidence to suggest that the exterior faces of the altar tower were either clad – or intended to be clad – in a material other than the limestone core masonry, possibly marble or even bronze, further underscoring the exceptional visual and symbolic prominence of this structure within the ritual landscape of Baalbek⁵⁵.

Flanking the Great Court to the north and south are two water basins, furnished with finely carved balustrades. These installations may have carried symbolic meaning, possibly representing the sources of the two major rivers that rise in the Beqaa Valley – the Orontes and the Leontes (modern Litani) – and thus evoking themes of fertility, renewal, and cosmic order within the ritual choreography of the Baalbek sanctuary.

There is also evidence that a mechanical sawmill was installed within the area of the Great Court during the Byzantine period, after the colonnades had fallen into ruin and the sanctuary as a whole was forcibly converted to Christian use in the late fourth and early fifth centuries CE. This interpretation is supported by the presence of numerous granite column fragments bearing regular, parallel saw marks, indicative of mechanical stone-cutting techniques. Comparable saw marks are attested at other late antique and Byzantine sites known to have employed mechanical saws, including Hierapolis and Ephesus in modern Turkey, as well as Jerash in present-day Jordan⁵⁶. Together, this evidence suggests the systematic reuse and industrial processing of architectural elements from the ruined sanctuary during the Byzantine transformation of Baalbek.

⁵⁵ Paul Collart and Pierre Coupel (1951), *L'Autel Monumental de Baalbek*, Paris: Librairie Orientaliste Paul Geuthner, p. 91.

⁵⁶ Jacques Seigne (2022), "A sixth century water-powered sawmill at Jarash", *ADAJ*, 46, pp. 205-213.

Figure 20. Detail of broken pink granite columns with horizontal saw marks, from the Great Court. © Marco M. Vigato.

The Great Court of the Baalbek sanctuary rests upon massive substructures traversed by a system of three cryptoporticuses: two running east–west along the northern and southern outer walls of the court, and a third connecting these along the eastern side of the platform, behind the Hexagonal Court. Several construction features – discussed in detail below – make it clear that the vaults of these cryptoporticuses postdate the surrounding walls. They appear to have been added only after a significant change of plan that altered the original layout of the Great Court.

Figure 21. Detail of southern cryptoporticus under the Great Court. Notice the different quality of the walls, built of huge megalithic stone blocks, and the comparatively smaller voussoirs of the ceiling. © Marco M. Vigato

The lower outer walls of the Great Court rank among the finest examples of masonry anywhere within the sanctuary. They are constructed from enormous stone blocks, commonly measuring between five and seven meters in length and reaching exceptional dimensions of more than eleven meters long near the corners. The masonry is laid in alternating courses of headers and stretchers, each block carefully finished with drafted margins and exquisitely precise joints. The quality of workmanship is such that the horizontal joints remain virtually perfectly straight along the entire 125-meter length of the court, deviating by no more than a few millimeters.

Figure 22. Detail of the outer walls of the Great Court, looking north, with perfectly straight joints. Notice the use of significantly larger stones in the basement floor compared to the upper walls. © Marco M. Vigato.

Figure 23. Angular stone blocks near the southwestern (left) and northwestern (right) corner of the Great Court, connecting at an angle with the megalithic U-shaped enclosure wall (Podium II) of the Temple of Jupiter. © Marco M. Vigato.

Near the northwestern and southwestern corners of the Great Court, the lower outer walls are physically bonded to the megalithic podium of the Temple of Jupiter through the use of immense stone blocks laid perpendicularly to the axis of the temple podium. This structural interlocking is especially pronounced at the southwestern corner, where the scale and orientation of these transverse blocks clearly demonstrate an intentional integration between the Great Court substructures and the megalithic foundations of the temple itself.

By contrast, the upper exterior walls of the Great Court are constructed from markedly smaller ashlar blocks. Their masonry is considerably less precise, and their unfinished external surfaces clearly distinguish them from the finely executed lower courses, indicating a later and incomplete phase of construction.

The arrangement of the corner blocks of the Great Court platform suggests that its enclosing walls were originally intended to extend further eastward, concealing the angular exterior of the Hexagonal Court, and possibly also westward, where they may have formed a *temenos* or *peribolos* wall surrounding the Temple of Jupiter.

Figure 24. Exposed megalithic foundations near the northwestern corner of the Great Court. © Marco M. Vigato.

Near the northwestern corner of the Great Court, an area of exposed megalithic foundations points to the former presence of a now-demolished structure at this location: Early investigators interpreted these foundations as evidence for an abandoned attempt to raise the floor level around the temple podium. According to this view, the project would have fully concealed the unfinished megalithic podium and allowed the porticoes along the northern and southern sides of the Great Court to continue uninterrupted, ultimately enclosing the Temple of Jupiter on all sides⁵⁷.

⁵⁷ Daniel Krencker (1934), "Forschungen in Baalbek", *Archäologischer Anzeiger*, Archäologische Gesellschaft zu Berlin, 6 February 1934, pp. 266-286.

Closer examination, however, complicates this interpretation. A distinct linear joint marking the western termination of the foundation suggests that the structure was never intended to extend further westward. On this basis, Daniel Lohmann has proposed an alternative explanation: that an annex building once occupied the northwestern corner of the Great Court. This annex may have housed a ramp used during ritual processions or for guiding sacrificial animals up to the level of the temple court⁵⁸.

To the north of the smaller altar and to the east of the monumental altar, several open excavation areas reveal the presence of earlier architectural remains beneath the surface of the Great Court. These earlier structures, tentatively dated to the Bronze Age, consist of a series of parallel rooms that formed part of the original *tell*. Significantly, they do not share the orientation of the later Sanctuary of Jupiter, underscoring their independence from the Roman monumental layout.

Figure 25. Excavations inside the Great Court, near the Monumental Altar, with exposed Hellenistic and Bronze Age stonework. © Marco M. Vigato

⁵⁸ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 81-84.

By contrast, a monumental stairway located east of the altar court has been dated by Daniel Lohmann to the early Roman period, when it likely served as part of the original approach to the sanctuary, ascending to the level of an earlier courtyard. In addition, the remains of several sloping walls have been identified in this area. These features have been variously interpreted as the foundations of towers flanking an earlier propylon, or alternatively as elements of Hellenistic – or even late Bronze Age – fortifications. Notably, all of these structures share the same orientation as the Temple of Jupiter, strongly suggesting that the Roman sanctuary was laid out in deliberate continuity with an earlier architectural axis rather than imposing an entirely new orientation⁵⁹.

Stratigraphic evidence further demonstrates that the foundations of both the small altar and the monumental altar cut deeply into the underlying Bronze Age and Neolithic deposits of the *tell*, reaching down to the bedrock at depths exceeding seven meters below the present floor level⁶⁰.

The Jupiter Temple

Figure 26. 3D reconstruction of the Temple of Jupiter at Baalbek as a massive decastyle peripteros.

⁵⁹ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 111-120.

⁶⁰ Van Ess (2014), pp. 26-30.

In its final architectural form, the Jupiter temple was a massive *peripteros* with 10 columns on the front and 19 along each side. All kinds of superlatives may well apply to this temple. It boasted the tallest columns in antiquity, each 23 meters high, and was built with some of the largest stone blocks ever employed in construction anywhere on earth. It had the colossal dimensions of 85 by 45 meters, double those of the Parthenon of Athens and greater than any other surviving Greek or Roman temple.

Paradoxically, the temple of Jupiter is also the structure that suffered the most the ravages of time and the ignorance of man than any other on the Baalbek acropolis. Of its towering walls, little survives beyond the foundation courses, themselves stripped away in many areas, and only 6 colossal shafts remain standing of the original fifty-four columns that once surrounded the cella.

Figure 27. The six giant surviving columns of the southern peristyle of the temple of Jupiter, each 23 meters high and built of three separate column drums connected by metal clamps. © Marco M. Vigato.

The temple itself rests somehow awkwardly on a colossal artificial platform, 13 meters high, which served to compensate for the difference in elevation between

the level of the plain to the west and the summit of the *tell* with the temple courtyard to the east. We say *somehow awkwardly* because the platform, which we will refer to following the nomenclature proposed by Lohmann as *Podium I*, was clearly designed to support a very different kind of temple.

Several architectural anomalies point to this conclusion: Along the northern and southern sides, the column bases of the Roman temple rest directly on the very edge of the podium, while on the western side they are offset eastward by approximately 1.3 meters⁶¹. More significantly, archaeological evidence indicates that *Podium I* was originally T-shaped⁶². Remnants of massive wing walls have been identified near both the northeastern and southeastern corners of the platform, projecting eastward beyond the line of the later temple. These walls appear to belong to an earlier configuration of the podium and were subsequently dismantled, their stones reused during a later phase when the platform was enlarged through the construction of what Lohmann refers to as *Podium II*.

The Temple Podium

Figure 28. The temple podium (right) as seen from the North side. Notice the northern megalithic enclosure wall running parallel to Podium I in the center of the image. © Marco M. Vigato

⁶¹ Lohmann (2017a), p. 129.

⁶² *Ibid.*, p. 155.

Figure 29. The temple podium as seen from the south side. Clearly visible in the foreground is the southern megalithic enclosure wall, completely encircling the inner Podium I. The columns bases rest on top of Podium I, whereas the outer megalithic wall appears here as a completely free-standing, non-load-bearing structure. © Marco M. Vigato.

Podium I is itself a massive megalithic construction, virtually identical in quality and workmanship to the lower outer walls of the Great Court. It follows the same very regular and aesthetically pleasing alternation of headers and stretchers, which also reach enormous sizes of over 10 meters in length. The blocks have finely drafted margins and precisely cut joints meant to break the monotony of the wall and highlight the horizontal lines of the alternating layers. From these characteristics and the extreme care and investment of labor that was put in their outside finishing, it is evident that the outer walls of *Podium I* were meant to be fully visible before they were covered with layers of packing stones for the construction of *Podium II*.

Podium I is flanked on its southern, western, and northern sides by what, in its present form, can only be described as a colossal megalithic wall. Its basal course alone consists of just thirty-two stone blocks, each exceeding ten meters in length and measuring approximately four meters in depth and four meters in height, with individual weights approaching an astonishing 400 tons.

Independent researcher and author Graham Hancock has rightly pointed out that this enigmatic structure can hardly be called a podium at all⁶³: It does not support anything, for the temple peristyle and cella walls sit entirely on top of *Podium I*, and moreover runs at a constant distance of about 13 meters from *Podium I*, almost embracing and enclosing it, but without ever touching.

Figure 30. The megalithic enclosure wall with the Trilithon stones as seen from the west. © Marco M. Vigato

Figure 31. Detail of the Trilithon stones, each nearly 20 meters long and weighing over 800 tons, on top of the base course of 400-ton stone blocks and partially exposed foundations. © Marco M. Vigato

⁶³ Graham Hancock (2015), *Magicians of the Gods*, New York: St. Martin's Press, pp. 264-265.

It is upon the western stretch of this megalithic enclosure that three even larger stones were laid, together forming the famous Baalbek *Trilithon*. Each of these blocks approaches twenty meters in length and exceeds 800 tons in weight, making them the largest stones ever employed in construction anywhere on earth. Yet, as Graham Hancock has emphasized, these extraordinary megaliths appear to serve no structural purpose whatsoever. They bear no superimposed load, nor do they function as foundations for the Temple of Jupiter, which rests entirely upon *Podium I*, located some thirteen meters further inward.

Moreover, the construction seems to have been left unfinished. The placement of colossal blocks was never continued along the northern and southern sides of the enclosure, nor was a third – and possibly fourth – course ever added that would have brought the height of this outer wall up to the level of *Podium I*.

According to Daniel Lohmann, this outer megalithic wall – which he designates as *Podium II* – represents a later expansion of the temple platform, intended to conceal the earlier and, by that stage, architecturally obsolete *Podium I*⁶⁴. In this reconstruction, the space between *Podium I* and *Podium II* was to be filled with a massive body of packing stones rising to the level of the temple platform, while the exterior face of *Podium II* would have consisted of only three, or possibly four, monumental courses, reaching a total height of approximately thirteen meters. From this perspective, the colossal stones of the *Trilithon* fulfilled no structural function other than to impress through their sheer scale⁶⁵.

The so-called “packing” between *Podium I* and *Podium II* is still partially preserved along the southern side of the sanctuary, rising to the level of the first outer course of the megalithic enclosure wall. On the northern side, by contrast, this material appears to have been almost entirely dismantled and quarried away, surviving only near the southeastern and northeastern corners, where it was retained as a foundation for the Arabic fortifications and corner towers.

The term “packing,” however, is itself misleading. If the intention had merely been to fill the space between *Podium I* and the outer megalithic wall, far smaller stones – or even rubble and earth – would have sufficed. Instead, many of the blocks used in this infill are themselves colossal, surpassed in size only by the stones of the outer megalithic base course. This raises a number of unresolved questions. How, for instance, could such enormous blocks have been

⁶⁴ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 156-174.

⁶⁵ Daniel Lohmann (2017b), “Superlative baulicher Art: Zum Trilithon und der Inszenierung von Größe im antiken Jupiterheiligtum in Baalbek”, in *Groß Bauen*, edited by Klaus Rheidt and Werner Lorenz, Basel: Birkhäuser Verlag, 2017, pp. 155-169.

maneuvered and set into place within the narrow space separating the two podia, unless the construction proceeded from the interior outward rather than as an external encasement? And why employ stones of such extraordinary size and workmanship merely as filling, if they were never intended to carry structural loads or to remain visible?

Figure 32. View of the “Packing” of large stone blocks between Podium I (Left) and the outer megalithic enclosure wall (Podium II – right) along the north side of the temple platform. © Marco M. Vigato.

The unfinished character of *Podium II* and of the megalithic wall encircling *Podium I* on its southern, western, and northern sides is particularly evident in the treatment of the block joints. Around many of these joints, preparatory surfaces survive that clearly indicate the final profile the stones were intended to assume after the removal of their bosses. In several cases, square cuttings – most commonly located within the boss itself – are visible. These holes likely held wooden or metal pegs used during extraction, lifting, or transport from the quarry. Such features are characteristic of unfinished masonry. In a completed structure, the bosses would have been removed and the joint faces dressed flush, eliminating both the peg holes and the preparatory margins from view. Their continued presence on the exposed faces of the megaliths therefore demonstrates that the final finishing phase of Podium II was never carried out.

Figure 33. View of the unfinished stone blocks in the base course of the megalithic enclosure wall along the south side of the temple platform. Notice the peg holes and visible preparations around the corners. © Marco M. Vigato

Figure 34. Close-up of the preparations along the edges of the stone blocks. © Marco M. Vigato

Very little is known about the substructure and foundations of *Podium I* and *Podium II*. A number of early drawings and plans appear to suggest the presence of cryptoporticuses or tunnels comparable to those beneath the Great Court⁶⁶; however, if such features do exist, they have never been accessed or investigated in modern times. Available evidence instead indicates that the foundations of both podia consist of a largely solid mass of masonry, devoid of internal vaults or chambers.

The depth of these foundations remains unknown, but it is almost certainly enormous. The geology of the site is notably unstable, composed of heterogeneous

⁶⁶ See for instance the plan by Louis-François Cassas (1799), reproduced by Lohmann (2017a), p. 17.

sedimentary layers overlying deeply karstified bedrock, conditions that would have required the foundations to be carried down to solid bedrock. At the location of the Temple of Jupiter, the bedrock lies at its greatest depth beneath the entire sanctuary, implying an especially massive and deeply seated foundation system⁶⁷.

A useful comparison is provided by the nearby Temple of Bacchus, whose foundations have been traced to a depth exceeding seventeen meters before reaching bedrock⁶⁸. There is no reason to suppose that the foundations beneath *Podium I* and *Podium II* were any less extensive. On the contrary, the extraordinary scale of the superstructure and the problematic nature of the subsoil strongly suggest that the unseen foundations of the Jupiter sanctuary represent yet another immense – and still largely undocumented – engineering effort underpinning the monumental architecture of Baalbek.

A particularly contentious feature is the presence of a single column drum from the Temple of Jupiter, likely a discarded or unfinished element, embedded within the exposed foundation courses beneath the *Trilithon*⁶⁹. The implications of this find are significant and will be addressed in detail below, in the context of the construction sequence of the Jupiter sanctuary.

On the eastern side, access to the temple was provided by a monumental stairway composed of three successive flights separated by landings. Each flight originally consisted of eleven steps, yielding a total of thirty-three steps leading up to the temple platform. The stairway was constructed from immense stone blocks, into which as many as seven steps were carved directly from a single block. During the Byzantine period, many of these stones were dismantled and reused in the foundations of the Byzantine Basilica.

There is also evidence that an additional two steps were added at the base of the stairway when the floor level of the Great Court was lowered, possibly during the late first or early second century CE⁷⁰. This modification provides further testimony to the evolving layout of the sanctuary and underscores the complexity of its architectural and stratigraphic history.

⁶⁷ Van Ess (2014), pp. 32-25.

⁶⁸ Theodor Wiegand (1923), *Baalbek: Ergebnisse der Ausgrabungen und Untersuchungen in den Jahren 1898 bis 1905*. Vol. II. Berlin und Leipzig: Verlag von Walter de Gruyter & Co., pp. 1-2.

⁶⁹ Lohmann (2017a), p. 135.

⁷⁰ Lohmann (2017a), p. 176.

Figure 35. The monumental stairway on the eastern side of the temple of Jupiter, also formed of enormous megalithic stone blocks, into which up to 7 steps were carved. Some of the blocks are as large as those in the outer megalithic enclosure wall. © Marco M. Vigato.

The Temple of Bacchus

Immediately south of the Temple of Jupiter stands the so-called Temple of Bacchus. Although conventionally described as the “smaller” of the two, this designation is purely relative: the Temple of Bacchus is itself among the largest and most monumental temples of antiquity. Like its larger neighbor, it is a massive *peripteros*, with a front of eight Corinthian columns across the façade. Remarkably well preserved, the temple retains its cella walls to roof height, 19 of the original 42 peristyle columns, and much of the western pediment, making it one of the finest and most lavishly decorated surviving examples of Roman temple architecture.

The huge doorway of the cella is framed by vegetal patterns including depictions of poppies, suggesting that the use of hallucinogens was perhaps part of the rituals celebrated in the temple. Some of the temple’s surviving friezes and decorations have been interpreted as the depiction of Dionysian rituals and processions, hence the temple’s modern attribution to Bacchus, god of wine and ecstasy.

Figure 36. The Temple of Bacchus, one of the best preserved in the Roman world and larger than the Parthenon of Athens..
© Marco M. Vigato.

Figure 37. The enormous doorway of the temple of Bacchus with the 75-ton keystone. © Marco M. Vigato.

The vast six-meter span of the doorway is bridged not by a single lintel – which would have weighed well in excess of 300 tons – but by an ingenious composite system consisting of two horizontal stretchers, each weighing over 100 tons, surmounted by a monolithic relieving keystone of approximately 70 tons. This keystone was re-erected in its original position by German excavators in the early twentieth century after an eighteenth-century earthquake had left it precariously suspended above the entrance. Flanking the main portal are two smaller doors, each giving access via stairways to the temple roof.

The interior of the cella is framed by elegant, fluted Corinthian columns and richly ornamented aediculae. Toward the western end, the floor rises in three stepped tiers to the level of the *adyton*, while a small lateral doorway beside the steps leads to a series of vaulted chambers beneath the *adyton* itself, forming a crypt-like substructure.

Figure 38. The richly decorated interior of the cella of the temple of Bacchus. Notice the person standing under the doorway for scale. © Marco M. Vigato.

The temple rests upon a substantial podium and is approached by a monumental stairway with three landings, constructed from enormous stone blocks into which as many as seven steps were carved. While some podium stones are themselves megalithic – measuring between three and five meters in length –

they appear almost modest when compared with the colossal blocks forming the lower megalithic courses of the Jupiter Temple's podium.

The peristyle colonnades were roofed with massive stone slabs whose soffits were richly decorated with relief busts of female figures personifying the cities of Roman Syria that contributed to the temple's construction.

Figure 39. Foundations under the Temple of Bacchus. After Wiegand (1923), pp. 1-2.

The scale and depth of the temple's foundations was probed in 1904, when German excavators opened a deep test pit near the northwestern corner of the structure, tracing the foundations down to a depth of more than seventeen meters below the level of the surrounding valley⁷¹.

⁷¹ Wiegand (1923), pp. 1-2.

The Construction Sequence of the Jupiter Sanctuary

Figure 40. 3D model of the Jupiter Sanctuary with different construction phases. After Lohmann (2017a). © Marco Vigato.

The existence of different layers of construction at Baalbek has been noticed since at least the 19th century. Even to the first explorers and excavators of Baalbek, it was immediately obvious that the gigantic temple complex was not erected all at once but was in fact the result of a complex stratification reflecting the tribulated history of the region and the long sequence of empires that came to rule over Lebanon and Syria in the course of thousands of years.

Prior to the first systematic German excavations of 1898–1905, the dominant interpretation held that the Roman sanctuary had been superimposed upon an earlier Hellenistic – and before that, Phoenician or even more ancient – sacred site. Writers such as David Urquhart interpreted the colossal remains of the Jupiter temple platform, and especially the gigantic blocks of the *Trilithon*, as vestiges of these earlier phases, if not as relics of a prehistoric or even antediluvian past⁷². The notion of an essentially Oriental origin for the Baalbek sanctuary – Phoenician, Canaanite, or otherwise pre-Roman – persisted well into the twentieth century, partially driven by nationalistic considerations in the wake of Lebanon’s independence.

This perspective stands in marked contrast to prevailing scholarship today. While modern research readily acknowledges the great antiquity of occupation

⁷² Urquhart (1860)

at Baalbek, the sanctuary itself is now generally understood as an overwhelmingly Roman creation: a monumental expression of imperial ideology and technical capability, with little material evidence to support an origin earlier than the late first century BCE.

The tension between the unexplained architectural and engineering aspects of the Baalbek temple complex and the prevailing Roman framework continues to define the central problem in any attempt to reconstruct the true construction history of the Baalbek temple complex.

Theodor Wiegand and the other members of the German archaeological expedition of 1898–1905 were already keenly aware of many of these anomalous construction features that would later form the basis for subsequent theories concerning the construction sequence and architectural evolution of the Jupiter sanctuary. Among their most significant observations was the identification of several straight construction joints within the foundations of the Temple of Jupiter platform, indicating distinct building phases rather than a single, continuous project⁷³. They also drew attention to marked differences in masonry technique between the lower and upper levels of the Great Court and the Propylaea, differences that pointed to changes in workmanship, planning, and perhaps chronology. These early insights laid the groundwork for all later attempts to disentangle the complex stratigraphy of Baalbek and remain central to any discussion of its architectural history.

The Krencker and Krischen Construction Sequence

A first systematic attempt to reconstruct the complete building sequence of the Jupiter sanctuary was undertaken by architect Daniel Krencker between 1929 and 1934. Krencker correctly identified the oldest architectural elements of the complex as lying beneath the colossal platform of the Temple of Jupiter. In his initial reconstruction, he proposed that the outer megalithic wall was originally intended to serve as the foundation for an even larger peripteral temple, measuring approximately 70 by 115 meters and articulated by a colonnade of fourteen columns on the façade and twenty-three along the sides⁷⁴.

Krencker further suggested that the megalithic podium platform turned northward and southward near the temple stairway, connecting with a massive

⁷³ Theodor Wiegand (1921) *Baalbek: Ergebnisse der Ausgrabungen und Untersuchungen in den Jahren 1898 bis 1905*. Vol. I. Berlin und Leipzig: Verlag von Walter de Gruyter & Co., pp. 50-55.

⁷⁴ Daniel Krencker (1929a), “Neue Forschungen in Kleinasien und Nordsyrien im Herbst 1928”, *Forschungen und Fortschritte*, pp. 134-135.

peribolos wall – also constructed of megalithic blocks – that enclosed the altar court on its remaining three sides. A broadly similar reconstruction was later advanced by Friedrich Krischen, who likewise envisaged a colossal temple extending to the edge of what is now designated as *Podium II*, though with a façade of ten rather than fourteen columns⁷⁵.

Figure 41. The first construction phase of the Temple podium, after Daniel Krencker (1934). Notice the left and right-turning megalithic walls at the opposite ends of the podium.

According to Krencker, this ambitious initial design was ultimately abandoned in favor of a smaller temple – namely, the one whose six surviving columns still stand today. In this revised plan, the peristyle of the final temple was set back approximately thirteen meters from the edge of the megalithic podium and consisted of ten columns on the front and nineteen along each side. Only at a later stage, in Krencker’s view, were the surrounding porticoes and exedrae of the altar court added, with the Propylaea and the Hexagonal Court representing the final components of the sanctuary’s architectural development.

The Von Gerkan Construction Sequence

In 1937, an alternative construction sequence for the Temple of Jupiter was proposed by Armin Von Gerkan⁷⁶. Von Gerkan directed his analysis toward the anomalous projections visible on the northeastern and southeastern sides of

⁷⁵ Daniel Krencker (1929b), “Forschungen in Baalbek”, *Archäologischer Anzeiger*, Archäologische Gesellschaft zu Berlin, February 5, 1929, pp. 173-174.

⁷⁶ Armin Von Gerkan (1937), “Die Entwicklung der großen Tempels von Baalbek, in H. Bulle (Editor), *Corolla*. Stuttgart: Festschrift L. Curtius, pp. 55-59.

Podium I, interpreting them as the surviving remains of the later-demolished arms of a T-shaped temple platform. Taking Pompey the Great's conquest of Syria in 64 BCE as a *terminus ante quem*, Von Gerkan dated this initial construction phase to the late Hellenistic period. In his reconstruction, a new and fundamentally different type of temple was subsequently erected during the first century CE atop this earlier podium.

Figure 42. Von Gerkan's (1937) drawing of the T-shaped "Hellenistic" podium (Blue) and megalithic enclosure wall (Orange) under the temple of Jupiter. Coloring by author.

Figure 43. Von Gerkan's (1937) cross-section of the foundations under the Temple of Jupiter. Note how the drawing still incorrectly shows the foundations of Podium I (Blue) as separate from those of the outer megalithic enclosure wall (Orange)

In response to Von Gerkan's proposal, Daniel Krencker returned to Baalbek in 1938 and undertook a targeted excavation in the narrow space between *Podium I* and *Podium II*. The objective was to test the hypothesis of a Hellenistic T-shaped podium by locating its foundations. As anticipated, Krencker uncovered

the continuation of the demolished northern arm of the T-shaped podium extending beneath the later masonry and running directly below the base courses of the outer megalithic wall⁷⁷.

This stratigraphic relationship demonstrated conclusively that the outer megalithic enclosure – later designated by Lohmann as *Podium II* – could not predate the construction of *Podium I*, thereby establishing a clear relative chronology between the two and lending substantial support to von Gerkan’s proposed construction sequence.

Post-War Reconstructions

In the following decades and after World War II, responsibility for archaeological research at Baalbek passed first to the French *Service des Antiquités* and later to the Lebanese *Direction Générale des Antiquités*. Once again, scholarly attention shifted toward the search for the Oriental and pre-Roman origins of the sanctuary. As architectural historian Adolf Hoffmann has observed: “*Until then, the Roman elements and aspects had been stressed; now, the local roots of the cult and its installations were elaborated by the French scholars and yielded completely new insights for the understanding of the whole complex*”⁷⁸.

Much of this research focused on the Altar Court, rather than the temple, which, in true Oriental fashion, was now seen as the true center of cultic practices and ritual at Baalbek. This shift was reinforced by the discovery, excavation, and reconstruction of the monumental altar from within the ruins of the Byzantine Basilica. Lebanese excavations conducted during the 1960s further transformed our understanding of the site by clarifying the long sequence of human occupation beneath the Roman sanctuary. Stratigraphic excavations conclusively demonstrated that the Altar Court had been constructed directly on top of an earlier prehistoric *tell*, thereby confirming that Baalbek had been already inhabited for thousands of years before a Roman colony was established there in the 1st Century BCE.

The Lebanese archaeologist Haroutoune Kalayan, who directed archaeological work at Baalbek throughout much of the 1960s and early 1970s, proposed a

⁷⁷ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 36-37.

⁷⁸ Adolf Hoffmann (1998), “Terrace and Temple: Remarks on the Architectural History of the Temple of Jupiter in Baalbek, in H. Sader, T. Scheffler and A. Neuwirth (Editors), *Baalbek. Image and Monument, 1898-1998*, Beirut/Stuttgart, pp. 279-304.

construction sequence for the sanctuary comprising three distinct phases. The first, corresponding to the prehistoric and Bronze Age occupation of the *tell*; the second involving the construction of a pre-Roman – interpreted by Kalayan as Hellenistic – T-shaped temple podium together with an early Altar Court; and the third encompassing the Roman monumental phase that gave the sanctuary its final architectural form⁷⁹.

Kalayan’s model was further developed in 1980 by the Swiss architectural historian Friedrich Ragette. Like Kalayan, Ragette argued that the sanctity of the site originated in a deep well – approximately fifty meters deep – connected to an underground water source located at one corner of the Altar Court. According to Ragette, the earliest pre-Roman sanctuary consisted of a rectangular, walled temenos centered on the Small Altar and approached from the east by a broad monumental stairway flanked by towers⁸⁰.

Figure 44. Artist’s rendering of the primitive Bronze-Age sanctuary of Baalbek. After Ragette (1980). © Marco M. Vigato.

This reconstruction was based on architectural remains uncovered in a deep trench near the Great Altar, which included fragments of a monumental stairway and portions of a sloping *glacis* wall. Ragette interpreted these features as belonging to an early sacred enclosure predating the Roman monumental phase. In his view, the Hellenistic period – following the conquest of Phoenicia

⁷⁹ Haroutoune Kalayan (1969b), “The engraved drawing on the Trilithon and the related problems about the constructional history of the Baalbek temples”, *Bulletin du Musée de Beyrouth*, XXII, Paris:, pp. 151-156.

⁸⁰ Friedrich Ragette (1980), *Baalbek*, Park Ridge, NJ: Noyes Press, pp. 27-28.

by Alexander the Great – saw the planning of a large Greek-style temple erected atop a twelve-meter-high podium (*Podium I*) on the western side of the courtyard. Construction of this temple, however, was never completed, having been interrupted by Pompey the Great’s invasion and annexation of Syria in 64 BCE⁸¹.

Figure 45. The architectural evolution of the Baalbek temple complex from the late Bronze Age (left), Hellenistic period (center), and Early Roman Imperial period (right). After Ragette (1980).

Ragette further proposed that, during the early Roman imperial period, a new temple was conceived within an enclosure extending approximately three hundred meters in length. A subsequent revision of this plan resulted in the enclosure being completed only between the propylon and the temple façade. To compensate for the abandonment of the enclosure along the remaining sides, a massive megalithic platform – *Podium II* – was designed to surround the temple on its western, northern, and southern sides⁸². In Ragette’s reconstruction, the final appearance of the sanctuary thus reflects a series of interrupted projects and shifting architectural intentions rather than a single, coherent plan.

The Rheidt and Hoffmann Construction Sequence

Among the most recent reconstruction attempts, Adolf Hoffmann (1998) and Klaus Rheidt (2004) proposed a revised architectural sequence comprising one Hellenistic and two Roman construction phases. In their model, the initial Hellenistic phase saw the construction of *Podium I*, complete with its T-shaped lateral arms, oriented toward a raised Altar Court centered on the Small Altar and approached from the east by a monumental stairway⁸³.

⁸¹ *Ibid.*, p. 28.

⁸² *Ibid.*, pp. 30-31.

⁸³ Hoffmann (1998), pp. 279-304

During the Roman period, a decision was subsequently taken to enlarge the temple platform through the construction of the colossal megalithic enclosure known as *Podium II*. This intervention would have replaced the earlier, and by then architecturally obsolete, T-shaped podium with a canonical Roman temple podium of unprecedented scale. The project, however, proved unfeasible – whether for technical, economic, or logistical reasons remains unclear – and was ultimately abandoned, leaving *Podium II* in its present unfinished state⁸⁴.

Figure 46. Artist's rendering of what the final aspect of the sanctuary may have looked like had construction of the porticoes' planned westward extensions been completed according to plan. After Ragette (1980) and Hoffmann (1998).

At this point, Hoffmann and Rheidt suggest that a further decision was made to conceal the unsightly incompleteness of *Podium II*. To that end, an ambitious extension of the Temple Courtyard may have been planned, intended to surround the entire temple with continuous porticoes and thereby form a vast rectangular enclosure approximately 300 meters in length. Foundations uncovered near the northwestern corner of the present Altar Court have been cited in support of this hypothesis. Had it been completed, such an enclosure would have entirely concealed the unfinished megalithic podium and the *Trilithon* wall from view.

⁸⁴ Ibid.

This project, too, however, was ultimately abandoned, and attention shifted instead to the completion of the exedrae of the Altar Court, followed by the Hexagonal Court and the Propylaea.

The above synthesis largely defined scholarly understanding of the construction history and architectural development of the Baalbek sanctuary until the publication, in 2017, of Daniel Lohmann's comprehensive monograph *Das Heiligtum des Jupiter Heliopolitanus in Baalbek*, which fundamentally reassessed the evidence and marked a new phase in Baalbek studies.

Enter Daniel Lohmann.

Through a series of articles and, most notably, in his milestone book on the architecture of the Jupiter Sanctuary, architectural history professor Daniel Lohmann of the Technische Hochschule Köln has provided the most complete and comprehensive survey of the Baalbek temple complex and its architectural evolution to date⁸⁵. Lohmann's work not only offers a detailed and persuasive reassessment of the sanctuary's construction history, but also corrects a number of longstanding misconceptions and factual errors that had accumulated in earlier scholarship – particularly with regard to the interpretation of the megalithic podium and its colossal *Trilithon*

On the basis of a meticulous architectural and stratigraphic analysis, Lohmann identifies four distinct phases of construction spanning the early Roman period through the third century CE. Evidence for a pre-Roman phase is, in his view, confined to limited structural remains uncovered beneath the level of the Altar Court.

The pre-Roman period

Excavations conducted since the 1960s within the area of the Great Court have revealed the presence of a pre-existing *tell*, or occupational mound, with evidence of continuous human habitation extending back at least 10,000 years to the Pre-Pottery Neolithic period⁸⁶. This earlier *tell* was partially preserved within the later Roman enclosure walls. Stratigraphic excavations carried down to bedrock near the Small Altar and along the eastern side of the courtyard have exposed a complex sequence of occupation layers, together with substantial

⁸⁵ Lohmann (2017a)

⁸⁶ Van Ess (2014), pp. 26-30.

masonry remains that may be interpreted either as fortifications or as the boundaries of an earlier sanctuary⁸⁷.

Among the earliest monumental features identified is a sloping *glacis* (or *talus*) wall. Proposed dates for this structure range from the Bronze Age (second millennium BCE) to the Hellenistic period. The *glacis* connects with a masonry wall built of yellow sandstone blocks of equal height, as documented by Daniel Lohmann⁸⁸. Ceramic material associated with this wall points toward a Bronze Age date⁸⁹, a conclusion already anticipated by Friedrich Ragette, who favored a dating in the second-millennium BCE⁹⁰. This interpretation has been however challenged by Holger Wienholz, who suggested instead that the *glacis* wall may represent a Hellenistic fortification dating to the Ptolemaic period (ca. 274–200 BCE)⁹¹. An alternative possibility still is that the structure formed part of the *temenos* (walled enclosure) of an earlier sanctuary.

Of particular significance is the fact that this *glacis* wall shares the same orientation as the Temple of Jupiter – approximately 12 degrees east of true north. This observation complicates Lohmann’s proposal that the orientation of the Roman sanctuary was determined by alignment toward the terminus of a Roman aqueduct conveying water from Ain Jouj to a basin near Hay al Solh, some 600 meters northeast of the propylaea⁹². If Lohmann’s hypothesis of an orientation of the temple towards the terminus of the Roman aqueduct is correct, how could the pre-Roman *glacis* wall share the same orientation as the (supposedly) Roman temple towards a reservoir that did not yet exist?

In response to this objection, Lohmann has acknowledged – at least with regard to the *glacis* wall – that the correspondence might be coincidental⁹³. However, in a personal communication, he further noted that new, as yet unpublished evidence identified by Juliane Schmidt suggests that the aqueduct itself may in fact be pre-Roman, possibly of considerable antiquity⁹⁴.

⁸⁷ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 111-120, 143-144.

⁸⁸ *Ibid.*

⁸⁹ Von Ess (2014), pp. 28-29.

⁹⁰ Ragette (1980), p. 27.

⁹¹ Holger Wienholz (2014), “Geschichte Baalbek in römischer Zeit”, in M. Van Ess, K. Rheidt (Editors), *Baalbek-Heliopolis: 10,000 Jahre Stadtgeschichte*, Verlag Philipp von Zabern, 2014, p. 147.

⁹² Lohmann (2017a), p. 212.

⁹³ Lohmann (2017a), p. 143-144. And personal communication, March 25, 2023.

⁹⁴ Daniel Lohmann, personal communication, March 25, 2023.

Construction Phase I – The “T-Shaped” platform.

According to Lohmann, the earliest phase of the sanctuary comprises the T-shaped temple platform (*Podium I*) and the core of the Small Altar within the Great Court. He further suggests that an early propylon may also belong to this phase, represented by a broad stairway uncovered in deep excavations along the eastern side of the Great Court⁹⁵.

Somewhat paradoxically, the construction technique and masonry style of this early entrance stand in marked contrast to the monumentality of the T-shaped podium and temple terrace. Whereas *Podium I* is built of enormous megalithic blocks with exceptionally precise jointing, the stairway and associated entrance structures are executed in a comparatively far simpler manner, using much smaller stones with noticeably less accurate joints. This discrepancy in scale, workmanship, and technical sophistication within features attributed to the same phase raises important questions about their contemporaneity and functional relationship.

The original T-shaped temple platform – later reused as the foundation for the peristyle of the Imperial Roman temple – measured approximately 95 meters in length and reached a maximum width of 69.3 meters. The two lateral arms forming the extremities of the T-shaped podium projected at right angles from the main podium wall, beginning at a distance of 61.45 meters from its western termination. According to Daniel Lohmann, these arms did not extend beyond the line later occupied by the outer megalithic enclosure to the north and south⁹⁶. Crucially, recent excavations have demonstrated that the foundations of the northern arm disappear beneath the base courses of the megalithic outer wall, establishing unequivocally that this wall – later designated *Podium II* – including the famous *Trilithon* as well as some of the largest stone blocks at the site, cannot possibly predate the construction of the T-shaped platform⁹⁷.

⁹⁵ Lohmann (2017a), p. 154.

⁹⁶ Lohmann (2017a), p. 146.

⁹⁷ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 131-132.

Figure 47. Colorized drawing showing the foundations of the northern arm of the T-shaped Podium I going under the megalithic enclosure wall. After Lohmann (2017a, Plate 14). Coloring by author.

The T-shaped podium itself represents a remarkable achievement of megalithic engineering, surpassed in scale only by the later outer podium wall and the *Trilithon* blocks. It is composed of eleven alternating courses of headers and stretchers, laid with exceptional precision, with an average course height of approximately 1.11 meters. This yields a total visible height of about 12.70 meters, while the foundations extend downward to an unknown – though almost certainly considerable – depth. The upper four courses are notably taller, averaging around 1.29 meters, and incorporate substantially larger blocks. The largest stone within the podium measures approximately eleven meters in length and is estimated to weigh over fifty tons⁹⁸.

The outer faces of these blocks were finished with carefully drafted margins roughly five centimeters wide, a treatment strikingly similar to what is commonly termed “Herodian” masonry of the late first century BCE. Close parallels can be observed at the Temple Mount in Jerusalem, as well as at

⁹⁸ Lohmann (2017a), p. 128.

Hebron and Mamre. Even the characteristic course height of approximately 1.11 meters finds analogues in these Levantine monumental constructions. On stylistic and architectural grounds, Lohmann has therefore suggested that Herod the Great (r. ca. 37–4 BCE) may have been directly involved in the construction of the first monumental platform at Baalbek – or, more plausibly, that master builders and stonemasons trained on Herodian projects in Judea were employed at the site. This stylistic convergence allows Lohmann to date the construction of *Podium I* to the late first century BCE or the early first century CE⁹⁹.

The fully finished appearance of the outer walls of *Podium I* further indicates that they were intended to remain entirely visible above ground level, reinforcing the conclusion that this structure was originally intended as a completed and coherent architectural unit rather than as a hidden substructure.

The construction of this first monumental sanctuary may plausibly coincide with the foundation of the Roman colony of Berytus (modern-day Beirut) in 15 BCE. As recorded by Flavius Josephus, Herod undertook extensive building programs across Syria and Phoenicia in an effort to secure favor with Rome:

“And when he had built so much, he showed the greatness of his soul to no small number of foreign cities. He built palaces for exercise at Tripoli, and Damascus, and Ptolemais; he built a wall about Byblos, as also large rooms, and cloisters, and temples, and marketplaces at Berytus and Tyre, with theaters at Sidon and Damascus.” (Josephus, *Wars*, 1.422).

Although Josephus does not explicitly mention construction at Baalbek (Heliopolis), this omission may be explained by the fact that the site fell within the territorial jurisdiction of the Roman colony of Berytus – one of the cities in which Herod is explicitly said to have sponsored the construction of temples and other monumental works.

In Lohmann’s reconstruction of Phase I, the massive T-shaped temple platform supported a comparatively modest, nearly square temple, while the lateral arms of the podium may have carried two flanking towers. A reconstruction of this early sanctuary must necessarily rely on analogy with other Near Eastern

⁹⁹ Daniel Lohmann (2017a), pp. 145-152. See also: Andreas Kropp and Daniel Lohmann, “Master, Look at the size of those stones! Look at the size of those buildings! Analogies in construction techniques between the temples at Heliopolis (Baalbek) and Jerusalem”, *Levant*, 43, 2011, pp. 38-50.

sanctuaries like the temple of Bel at Palmyra, the temple of Jerusalem, the temple of Baalshamin at Si (Seeia) or the Qasr-el-Bint temple at Petra¹⁰⁰.

It is, however, highly unlikely that this early temple was ever completed – if construction had even commenced at all before the death of Herod the Great in 4 BCE – as no identifiable architectural fragments attributable to such a Phase I temple have been recovered.

Figure 48. Artist's render of construction Phase I of the Jupiter Sanctuary, with the T-shaped "Hellenistic" temple platform. After Lohmann (2017a). © Marco M. Vigato.

In front of this hypothetical temple lay a square Altar Court, centered on the Small Altar and enclosed by a *temenos* wall. Portions of this early enclosure were later incorporated into the foundations of the eastern cryptoporticus¹⁰¹. The relatively unassuming Phase I propylon and its associated stairway appear to have remained in use as the principal entrance to the sanctuary for roughly the next two hundred years, until they were superseded by new and far more monumental Propylaea and the Hexagonal Court in the latter part of the 2nd Century CE¹⁰².

¹⁰⁰ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 146-156.

¹⁰¹ Lohmann (2017a), p. 154

¹⁰² Lohmann (2017a), pp. 194-198.

Construction Phase II – The Trilithon Phase.

Figure 49. Artist's render of construction Phase I of the Jupiter Sanctuary, after the demolition of the northern and southern arms of the "Hellenistic" T-shaped podium and with the new Roman temple on top. After Lohmann (2017a).

According to Lohmann, Phase II marks the most ambitious monumental expansion of the Jupiter sanctuary, encompassing the construction of the megalithic *Podium II* and the placement of the colossal *Trilithon* stones.

At some point during the early Roman Imperial period – most plausibly under Caligula or Nero – a decision was taken to transform the earlier T-shaped *Podium I* into a canonical Roman temple podium of unprecedented scale¹⁰³.

The projected dimensions of this new podium were extraordinary: approximately 69.3 meters in width, 118.4 meters in length, and 13.45 meters in height. In doing so, *Podium II* was designed, according to Lohmann, in such a way as to incorporate and envelop the earlier *Podium I*, which measured roughly 95 meters in length and 48 meters in width along its western side. To achieve this, the projecting arms of the original T-shaped podium were dismantled, and a new megalithic foundation wall was constructed parallel to

¹⁰³ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 164-168.

Podium I along its northern, western, and southern sides, maintaining a consistent offset of about thirteen meters.

This intervention created a U-shaped corridor surrounding *Podium I* on three sides. According to Lohmann, this space was intended to be filled with a massive stone “packing” up to the level of the temple *crepis*, nearly thirteen meters above the surrounding plain. For the exterior facing of this new structure, blocks of unprecedented size were employed – the largest stones ever moved in antiquity. In practice, however, construction progressed no further than the completion of the basal course and the placement of only three blocks of the second course, forming what is now known as the *Trilithon*. At this point, the project was abandoned, leaving *Podium II* permanently unfinished.

In the first course of *Podium II*, only twenty-seven stone blocks were employed to form the entire visible length of the northern, western, and southern sides of the podium, spanning more than 259.5 meters in total. Each block measures on average approximately 9.35 meters in length, 3.89 meters in height, and between 3.0 and 3.5 meters in depth. Assuming a limestone density of 2.7 t/m³, individual weights range between roughly 300 and 340 metric tons¹⁰⁴.

The corner blocks at the northwestern and southwestern angles were even more massive. These corner megaliths measure approximately 10.75 meters in length, 3.89 meters in height, and up to 5.75 meters in depth, yielding an estimated weight approaching 650 metric tons¹⁰⁵.

Two further megalithic blocks were set at right angles to the main podium walls near the northwestern and southwestern corners of the Altar Court. On the northern side, a block measuring approximately 4.72 meters in width and 3.05 meters in height was laid perpendicular to the podium wall, extending northward in parallel with the former T-shaped arms of *Podium I*. This block does not reach the full height of 3.89 meters of the first course of *Podium II* and displays an unusual L-shaped profile, suggesting that it may have been recarved at a later date.

On the southern side, another megalithic block was set at a ninety-degree angle to the southern wall of *Podium II*, where it abuts the lower level of the Altar Court. Measuring approximately 9.50 meters in length and 3.89 meters in

¹⁰⁴ Lohmann (2017a), p. 133

¹⁰⁵ Ibid.

height, this block is essentially identical in scale and workmanship to the other stones forming the basal course of the podium¹⁰⁶.

All stones in the basal course of *Podium II* – with the exception of the two blocks set perpendicularly to the podium near the northwestern and southwestern corners of the Altar Court – exhibit a rough exterior finish, clearly prepared for later carving into the canonical profile of a Roman temple podium. This profile was intended to consist of a lower vertical plinth approximately 1.87 meters high, surmounted by a sloping talus inclined at roughly 52 degrees and rising a further 1.26 meters, followed by the initial 0.76 meters of the vertical shaft that would have been completed by the second course of masonry¹⁰⁷.

The megalithic stone blocks on the northern side are still entirely in the rough, whereas those on the western side beneath the *Trilithon* – and the two westernmost blocks of the southern wall – were already dressed to their final architectural profile

Along the edges of the stones, careful preparatory work is visible in the form of narrow, chamfered margins approximately 1.5 centimeters wide, cut at an angle of about 45 degrees. These drafted edges were intended to accentuate the extraordinarily fine, hair-thin joints between adjacent blocks.

On the northern and western sides of the sanctuary, where the foundations beneath the megalithic podium have been partially exposed, it is possible to observe that they are composed of smaller, yet still substantial, stone blocks. The two uppermost foundation courses measure approximately 1.40 and 1.30 meters in height respectively, while the two courses immediately below are each about 1.20 meters high. As in the superstructure above, these foundation walls are laid in a regular alternation of headers and stretchers.

Notably, the upper foundation courses exhibit the same finely cut joints and high degree of precision seen in the overlying megalithic blocks. This consistency in workmanship suggests that at least the upper portion of the foundations may originally have been intended to remain visible¹⁰⁸.

¹⁰⁶ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 77-78.

¹⁰⁷ Lohmann (2017a), p. 133.

¹⁰⁸ Lohmann (2017a), p. 134

For the second course of the megalithic podium, even larger stones were selected to form the vertical shaft of *Podium II*. Only three of these colossal blocks, however, were ever set in place, all on the western side of the podium, where they together form the structure known as the *Trilithon*. From north to south, the three stones measure 19.33, 19.04, and 19.38 meters in length. Each stands 4.34 meters high and their depth varies between 3.7 and 4.85 meters¹⁰⁹.

In their present state, the estimated weight of these blocks ranges from a minimum of about 825 metric tons to as much as 1,100 metric tons each. These figures place the *Trilithon* stones not only among the largest stone blocks ever employed in construction anywhere on earth, but also among the largest objects ever moved by man

Even more astonishing is the fact that, unlike other megalithic monuments such as colossal statues and obelisks, also weighing in the hundreds of tons, these three stones do not stand in isolation, but had to be erected on top of a megalithic wall also formed of some of the largest quarried stones on earth, and set side by side with joints so thin that, even today, it is difficult to discern with the naked eye where one block ends and the next begins. This level of precision, achieved at such an extreme scale, represents one of the most remarkable feats of stone masonry and engineering in the ancient world.

Only thirteen such stones would have been required to complete the entire visible perimeter of the second course of the megalithic podium. Above this, an even more ambitious third megalithic course appears to have been planned, though never executed. The blocks intended for this uppermost course would have exceeded even the *Trilithon* stones in volume, measuring over 20 meters in length and approximately 5.6 meters in height by 6 meters in depth, with an estimated weight of around 1,600 metric tons each.

According to Lohmann (2018)¹¹⁰, the two colossal megaliths recently identified in the southern quarry at Baalbek were intended for this unrealized third course above the *Trilithon*. By contrast, the famous Hajar el-Hibla stone – lying in the same quarry but of slightly smaller proportions – would have been destined for the same course as the *Trilithon* itself.

¹⁰⁹ Daniel Lohmann (2017b), “Superlative baulicher Art: Zum Trilithon und der Inszenierung von Größe im antiken Jupiterheiligtum in Baalbek”, p. 153.

¹¹⁰ Lohmann (2017b), p. 155.

Figure 50. Likely intended location of the newly discovered megalithic stone blocks recently discovered in the Baalbek quarry (orange) and of the Hajar el-Hibla stone (blue). Adapted from Daniel Lohmann (2017b).

For the construction of the megalithic podium, Daniel Lohmann proposes a date within the Julio-Claudian period, spanning the first and early second halves of the 1st century CE. This chronology rests on a convergence of epigraphic and architectural evidence.

The first element is an inscription discovered on the upper surface of one of the column shafts belonging to the Temple of Jupiter, which provides a terminus within the early imperial period. The second is an incised architectural drawing of the temple's pediment found on the upper face of one of the *Trilithon* blocks.

The first inscription (IGLS 2733) bears a date corresponding to August 60 CE, indicating that construction of the Temple of Jupiter had already progressed to the level of the column capitals and was approaching completion during the reign of Nero¹¹¹.

¹¹¹ Ragette (1980), p. 34

Further evidence is provided by a remarkable discovery made in 1969, when Haroutune Kalayan uncovered an enormous incised drawing measuring approximately 13 by 4 meters etched into the upper surface of the southernmost *Trilithon* block. Executed at near–full scale, the drawing depicts part of the monumental pediment of the Temple of Jupiter, its outlines extending across almost the entire exposed surface of the megalith.

The placement of this natural-scale working drawing on the top of a *Trilithon* stone is of considerable chronological importance. It demonstrates beyond reasonable doubt that the *Trilithon* blocks had already been quarried, transported, and set in their final position at the time when the design of the temple pediment was being laid out. The *Trilithon* thus predates, and served as a working platform for, the construction of the superstructure of the final phase of the Roman temple of Jupiter¹¹².

According to Daniel Lohmann, an additional and potentially decisive element for dating the megalithic podium is the presence of a column drum embedded within the foundations of the western megalithic wall directly beneath the *Trilithon*. Lohmann’s detailed metrological and petrographic analysis demonstrates that this drum matches both the dimensions and the lithology of the column drums used in the Temple of Jupiter¹¹³.

Since no other architectural complex at Baalbek is known to have employed columns of comparable size, Lohmann argues that this drum must represent a discarded or damaged element originally intended for the Jupiter temple itself, subsequently repurposed as a construction stone in the foundations of Podium II. If correct, this reuse would provide a direct and stratigraphically meaningful link between the megalithic podium and the Julio-Claudian building phase of the temple, making it perhaps the strongest – and arguably the only unequivocal – archaeological indicator anchoring the construction of *Podium II* within the early Roman imperial period.

Yet it is also possible that the column drum may instead belong to a later phase of repair or reconstruction, possibly dating to the Arabic or medieval occupation of the site. This possibility, which would significantly weaken its value as a chronological marker for the megalithic podium, will be examined in greater detail later in this study.

¹¹² Kalayan (1969), pp. 151-156. See also Ragette (1980), pp. 33-34.

¹¹³ Lohmann (2017a), p. 135.

Within the Altar Court, Phase II also saw the construction of the monumental eastern stairway leading up to the temple podium. This grand approach was executed in the same megalithic style as the podium itself, using enormous stone blocks into which up to seven steps were carved directly from a single monolith. The stairway ascended in three flights of eleven steps each, separated by two intermediate landings, for a total of thirty-three steps reaching the level of the temple's stylobate.

During Phase II, the Altar Court underwent a radical transformation with the construction of a vast square platform measuring approximately 125 meters on each side. This new terrace incorporated portions of the ancient *Tell* as well as the Small Altar, effectively monumentalizing the cultic core of the sanctuary.

Structurally, the substructures of the Altar Court were linked to the megalithic podium by means of two massive stone blocks set at right angles to the outer wall of *Podium II*, near the northwestern and southwestern corners of the court.

Differences in block size, workmanship, and the precision of masonry joints indicate that during Phase II the Altar Court substructures rose to a height of only about 8.20 meters above the level of the plain. The construction of the upper story, including the surrounding exedras, was therefore completed only in a subsequent phase. The visible substructures are also megalithic, composed of enormous stone blocks measuring up to 6 or 7 meters in length and laid with the same finely executed, hairline joints characteristic of the *Trilithon* phase.

The lower level of the Altar Court contains a complex system of internal rooms and vaulted corridors. Two parallel cryptoporticuses run east–west beneath the court and are connected by a third corridor running north–south along the eastern side. Stratigraphic and architectural evidence demonstrates that the walls and vaults of these spaces were not built contemporaneously. Their layout does not correspond to the walls and exedras of the upper level, indicating successive design revisions. While the walls of the cryptoporticuses are constructed of massive megalithic blocks, the vaults themselves are formed of significantly smaller voussoirs. Moreover, the vaults are not flush with the supporting walls, an awkward configuration that suggests that the walls were originally meant to support a different type of vault¹¹⁴.

¹¹⁴ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 84-94.

On the basis of these anomalies, Daniel Lohmann proposes that the cryptoporticuses were originally conceived as much narrower passages, approximately 3.5 meters wide, and were only later enlarged to their present width of nearly 6 meters¹¹⁵. Such an enlargement would have required the laborious removal of substantial quantities of stone from the existing walls – a task only made possible by the extraordinary size of the blocks employed in the original megalithic construction. This reworking was itself left unfinished, as evidenced by the rough, unfinished surfaces of the walls, in contrast to the smoother finishing of the vaults.

Lohmann argues for a fundamental unity of planning linking the megalithic podium, the Julio-Claudian temple superstructure, and the substructures of the Altar Court. Nevertheless, the unfinished state of *Podium II*, together with the presence of enormous unused blocks still lying in the quarries, indicates that Phase II came to an abrupt halt, most likely sometime in the third or fourth quarter of the 1st century CE.

Construction Phase III

During Phase III, work on the Jupiter sanctuary resumed after the abrupt interruption of the Julio-Claudian building program, but on a markedly reduced technical and material scale. The Altar Court and the temple podium were brought to completion using significantly smaller stone blocks, accompanied by a clear decline in the precision of masonry, the regularity of the courses, and the quality of jointing when compared with the megalithic phases that preceded it. It was also during this phase that the foundations of the Propylaea were laid, inaugurating a new and highly theatrical monumental entrance to the sanctuary.

Lohmann dates this phase, to which also belong the monumental reconstruction of the small and great altar and the construction of the Temple of Bacchus, to the Antonine period (ca. 138-161 CE).

By the early 2nd century CE, the sanctuary of Baalbek had achieved considerable fame throughout the whole of the Roman empire, in large part due to the growing prestige of its oracle. This reputation was notably enhanced by a celebrated prophecy delivered to Trajan, foretelling the emperor's impending death during his return journey to Italy in 117 CE – a prediction later reported by Macrobius¹¹⁶.

¹¹⁵ Lohmann (2017a), p. 87.

¹¹⁶ Macrobius, *Saturnalia* I.23.13–16.

This heightened prestige prompted a new phase of monumental construction at Baalbek during the reigns of Hadrian (117–138 CE) and Antoninus Pius (138–161 CE). This phase would be characterized by a significant reconfiguration of the sanctuary's overall planning, most clearly expressed in the design of the upper level of the Altar Court and in the extensive modifications made to its substructures and cryptoporticuses.

During this phase, the Altar Court appears to have become the principal focus of architectural and ritual activity. Its transformation included the construction of the surrounding exedras, the monumental peristyle, the water basins, and the Great Altar. An enormous logistical effort was required to realize this program, most notably in the transport of more than 186 monolithic granite columns from the imperial quarries at Aswan¹¹⁷. The movement of these columns over such vast distances represents an undertaking of exceptional scale, rivaled within the sanctuary only by the earlier construction of the megalithic podium and the setting of the *Trilithon* blocks.

It is likely that at this time the decision was taken to definitively abandon the completion of the megalithic *Podium II*. By the early 3rd century CE, the architectural emphasis had clearly shifted away from further expansion of the sanctuary toward the completion and embellishment of its visible ceremonial spaces. A coin issued during the reign of Septimius Severus, dated to 211 CE, depicts the completed Temple of Jupiter standing atop a canonical Roman podium. The image suggests that, by this time, the unfinished *Podium II* had either been masked and hidden from sight, or perhaps hastily completed using much smaller stones.

Figure 51. Coin from the reign of Septimius Severus (193-211 CE) showing a completed Jupiter Temple.

¹¹⁷ Rheidt (2014), p. 164.

According to Lohmann, it was at this time that the space between the earlier *Podium I* and the megalithic *Podium II* was filled with a “packing” of stone blocks. This packing may have reached to the level of the temple crepis on the northern and western side, whereas in the south it does not seem to have ever reached above the first base course of the megalithic podium. Much of this infill was later dismantled during the Arabic period, when large quantities of stone were quarried from the sanctuary for reuse in fortifications and other construction projects.

At the same time, the level of the Altar Court itself was lowered. This alteration necessitated the somewhat awkward addition of two extra steps at the base of the monumental eastern stairway leading up to the Temple of Jupiter. The stairway thus acquired its present, irregular configuration of thirteen steps in the lower flight followed by two upper flights of eleven steps each.

Figure 52. Artist's render of construction Phase III of the Jupiter Sanctuary, with the now complete temple podium and propylaea leading into the Great Court. After Lohmann (2017a)

Perhaps the most significant architectural accomplishment of this phase was the construction of the Great Altar, an enormous block of masonry 17 meters wide by 15.8 meters high, standing just east of the center of the Altar Court in an ideal axial alignment with the propylon and the main temple stairway. The altar

rests upon extraordinarily deep foundations that cut through multiple occupational layers of the ancient *tell* down to the very bedrock, certainly requiring enormous effort for its construction.

In its conception and execution, the Great Altar constitutes a masterpiece of Roman megalithic engineering. As emphasized by Professor Rabun Taylor of Harvard University, one of the foremost authorities on Roman construction techniques, the twin tower-altars of Baalbek represent unparalleled achievements in stone construction:

“the two tower-altars in front of the temple of Jupiter at Baalbek are themselves tours de force of stereotomy, each among the most complex organizations of space ever realized in solid stone. Their components are not, like most building materials, small modular units assembled around a void. Within the structure solid and void compete as volumetric equals, each interlocking with the other. Joints and seams cease to correspond consistently to edges; angles are incorporated into the solids themselves. A component block of the altars might comprise dozens of curved and planar surfaces defining both figures and voids and cut to a perfectly conceived analytical plan, their multiplanar faces commingling as snugly as organs in an anatomical model”¹¹⁸.

Such an achievement would have required the use of precise preparatory models and large-scale working drawings, without which structures of this geometric and spatial complexity would have been effectively impossible to realize.

Constructed from massive blocks of white limestone and originally clad in bronze, the Great Altar incorporated three sets of double stairways ascending to the roof, where the sacrificial altar proper was located. In both conception and function, it is therefore more accurately described as a tower monument rather than a simple altar.

This architectural type finds a close parallel in the so-called Tower of Claudius at Qalaat Faqra, which similarly combines monumental mass, axial stairways, and an elevated cult platform. The sheer scale of the Great Altar at Baalbek, its broad access stairways, and its expansive open roof would have allowed for significantly larger gatherings than those accommodated by the Small Altar,

¹¹⁸ Rabun Taylor (2003), *Roman Builders: A Study in Architectural Process*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 33-35.

reinforcing its role as the primary focal point for public ritual and sacrifice within the sanctuary.

Figure 53. The incredibly complex internal structure of the Great Altar of Baalbek. After Collart and Coupel (1951).

At the eastern end of the Altar Court, plans were also laid for a new monumental entrance to the sanctuary. This ambitious scheme envisaged a rectangular forecourt – later replaced by the Hexagonal Court – and a monumental propylon flanked by towers. Construction of these elements, however, was never carried beyond the level of the foundations.

Complementing this unfinished entrance, a large semicircular paved plaza, shaped like a theater, was constructed in front of the propylon at the sanctuary's eastern approach

Construction Phase IV

Phase IV represents the final major building episode in the long architectural history of the sanctuary. This phase encompasses the construction of the Hexagonal Court and the completion of the Propylaea, thereby formalizing the monumental eastern approach to the Baalbek sanctuary. According to Daniel Lohmann, this phase is best dated to the early 3rd century CE, likely initiated around the time of the visit of Caracalla (ca. 211–217 CE),

with final completion perhaps extending into the reign of Philip the Arab (ca. 244–249 CE)¹¹⁹.

Architecturally, Phase IV is marked by a noticeable decline in construction quality and consistency. Earlier architectural elements were frequently reused, a practice particularly evident in the foundations of the Hexagonal Court. Despite the continued use of large stone blocks, the courses vary considerably in height, and the jointing is irregular and markedly inferior in precision when compared even to the foundations of the Propylaea. This uneven workmanship stands in stark contrast to the refined masonry of the earlier megalithic phases.

One plausible explanation for the rough exterior appearance of the Hexagonal Court is that its outer walls were never intended to remain exposed. Lohmann has suggested that they would have been concealed by a planned eastward extension of the northern and southern walls of the Altar Court – a project that was however never realized¹²⁰.

By the late 3rd century CE, large-scale monumental construction at Baalbek had effectively ceased. The sanctuary thus entered a phase of architectural stasis, suggesting that its builders had ultimately come to terms with the idea of its unfinishedness, and with it the impossibility of completing the grandiose vision that had driven its development for more than two centuries.

¹¹⁹ Lohmann (2017a), p. 194.

¹²⁰ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 197-198

Part III – Alternative Theories

Having reviewed the current state of research on the construction sequence of the Jupiter sanctuary, it is now time to step back and critically reassess the various claims and hypotheses concerning the antiquity of the *Trilithon* – specifically the suggestion that it may predate the Roman temples erected above and around it.

Among the many alternative interpretations proposed over the past century, those advanced by Graham Hancock stand out for their scope, internal coherence, and attempt to integrate architectural, epigraphic, and comparative evidence into a single explanatory framework. Whatever one's position on his conclusions, Hancock's work represents the most fully articulated non-orthodox scenario for the origins of Baalbek currently in circulation and therefore merits careful consideration rather than summary dismissal.

In particular, Hancock's arguments as presented in *Magicians of the Gods* (2015) are meant to directly address many of the anomalies identified in the preceding analysis: the apparent lack of structural function of the *Trilithon* within the final Roman design; the unfinished state of *Podium II*; the extreme disparity in scale between the megalithic blocks and the Roman superstructure; and the broader question of why such extraordinary stones were employed at all. For these reasons, several of Hancock's key points will be summarized and examined below against the available archaeological and architectural evidence.

At the core of Graham Hancock's hypothesis lies the proposal that the colossal U-shaped megalithic wall enclosing the Temple of Jupiter – identified by Lohmann as *Podium II* – may not be Roman at all, but instead constitute the earliest architectural element at Baalbek. Hancock frames the problem through a series of deliberately provocative questions:

“Suppose that U-shaped wall isn't Roman at all? Suppose it was already in place before, not after, Herod built Podium I? Suppose, further, that the Tell that antedates Podium I by thousands of years was itself situated where it is because of the prior existence of the U-Shaped megalithic wall? In other words, suppose the U-shaped wall with its immense megaliths was the very first work of architecture to be built on this site, perhaps enshrining some

central feature, some primeval mound, in front of which the Tell later evolved over thousands of years, until the Herodian temple was built on top of it, and then a little later overbuilt by the Temple of Jupiter?”¹²¹.

In this model, the megalithic enclosure would predate not only the Roman sanctuary but also the prehistoric *tell* itself, serving as a primordial sacred structure around which later occupation accreted. The Roman temple complex would thus represent the final monumental overbuilding of a site whose sacred significance extended deep into prehistory.

Hancock acknowledges the presence – first reported by Haroutune Kalayan – of a column drum matching the dimensions of the Jupiter temple columns embedded beneath the *Trilithon*. However, he challenges its value as a chronological marker, arguing that the insertion of this drum need not be contemporary with the original construction of the megalithic wall. Instead, he proposes that it could belong to a much later phase of repair, possibly dating to the medieval Arabic period following one of the many sieges endured by Baalbek¹²².

Central to Hancock’s hypothesis is the stark contrast between the extreme megalithic scale of *Podium II*, comprising the so-called *Trilithon* – built with some of the largest stones ever employed in construction anywhere on earth – and the comparatively more modest masonry employed in the unquestionably Roman components of the sanctuary. From this contrast, he derives a series of interrelated arguments, which may be summarized as follows:

1. The U-shaped megalithic wall surrounding the Temple of Jupiter on its northern, western, and southern sides may predate *Podium I* rather than postdate it¹²³.
2. This wall is structurally independent of *Podium I* and may only be improperly described as a “podium,” since it supports no superstructure. The Roman temple rests entirely on *Podium I*.¹²⁴

¹²¹ Hancock (2015), p. 259.

¹²² Hancock (2015), pp. 265-268, 282-283.

¹²³ Hancock (2015), p. 259.

¹²⁴ Hancock (2015), pp. 264-265

3. There is no clear structural or engineering necessity for employing stones of such extraordinary size in a wall that bears no load other than its own weight¹²⁵.
4. The reused column drum beneath the *Trilithon* cannot be accepted as definitive evidence for a Julio-Claudian date, given the plausible alternative of later reuse during medieval repairs¹²⁶.
5. While it is theoretically possible that Roman engineers possessed the technical means to move the *Trilithon* blocks, there is no explicit literary, epigraphic, or historical testimony attributing their construction to the Romans or to any other known ancient civilization¹²⁷.
6. To these, we may add one final claim, not as much stressed by Hancock as by other authors, that the megalithic podium and *Trilithon* appear to exhibit more advanced weathering and erosion than the securely dated Roman masonry above¹²⁸.

Taken together, these arguments form the basis of Hancock’s claim that the *Trilithon* and its enclosing megalithic wall may belong to a far earlier, possibly prehistoric phase of construction.

Let’s review each one of these claims in detail.

1. The relative chronology of Podium I and II

We shall therefore begin by addressing a fundamental question: is it possible that *Podium II* predates *Podium I* and that, in Hancock’s words, it represents “*a feature that the Romans inherited from a much earlier time*”?¹²⁹

The most compelling aspect of Hancock’s case lies in his observation that the massive U-shaped megalithic wall forming the core of *Podium II* bears no close parallel among any known Roman buildings, either in Rome itself or elsewhere in the Roman world. Rather than engaging in the contentious debate over whether Roman engineers possessed the technical means to execute such a structure, Hancock deliberately grounds his argument in stylistic and architectural considerations.

¹²⁵ Hancock (2015), p. 265

¹²⁶ Hancock (2015), pp. 267-268.

¹²⁷ Hancock (2015), p. 250, 265, 269-273

¹²⁸ See: Andrew Collins, “Baalbek: Lebanon’s Sacred Fortress”, on-line resource: <https://www.andrewcollins.com/page/articles/baalbek.htm>, last accessed February 2, 2026.

¹²⁹ Hancock (2015), p. 201

A second, closely related point concerns the striking lack of any structural integration between Podium I and Podium II. As Hancock notes, the megalithic wall constitutes an entirely independent, exterior construction, “embracing” *Podium I* along its northern, western, and southern sides without ever physically connecting to it¹³⁰. This peculiar arrangement raises an obvious problem of intent and design. From a purely logical perspective, it is difficult to explain why Roman builders would ignore an already existing, vastly more massive and robust megalithic wall as a foundation for the Temple of Jupiter, only to erect, *ex novo*, a separate and monumental basement a few meters inside it – one that neither touches nor meaningfully exploits the pre-existing structure.

It is, however, the archaeological evidence – more than any theoretical or stylistic consideration – that demonstrates beyond reasonable doubt that *Podium II* cannot predate *Podium I*. The key data had, in fact, been uncovered as early as 1937, but remained insufficiently documented and largely overlooked for decades. Only in 2008, with the reopening and systematic re-examination of the 1930s excavations along the northern megalithic wall, in the narrow space separating the two podiums, could this evidence be conclusively confirmed and properly evaluated. In this respect, Hancock can scarcely be faulted for advancing an alternative interpretation. It is doubtful that the relevant findings were accessible to a wider scholarly audience at the time *Magicians of the Gods* was published in 2015, particularly given that the definitive analysis appeared only in German and had not yet entered broader circulation.

In 1937, the German archaeologist Armin von Gerkan was the first to suggest that *Podium I* had not originally been conceived to support the Temple of Jupiter in its present form, but was instead designed for a very different kind of monumental structure. According to his interpretation, the podium was only later reworked and adapted to conform to the canonical requirements of a Roman temple platform. In its earliest phase, this monumental foundation appears to have been T-shaped, with arms of approximately 95 meters in width extending at right angles both northward and southward from a point corresponding to the sixth or seventh column along the long side of the Roman temple¹³¹.

One of von Gerkan’s drawings from 1937 already shows the foundations of the northern T-arm of *Podium I* extending beneath the foundations of *Podium II*. To validate this hypothesis, Daniel Krencker excavated in 1938 in the area

¹³⁰ Ibid.

¹³¹ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 127-132.

between the two podiums on the northern side of the temple, uncovering the foundations of the T-shaped northern arm of *Podium I* exactly where expected, according to von Gerkan's proposed reconstruction.

In 2008, Daniel Lohmann reopened Krencker's excavation, demonstrating that the foundations of the northern T-shaped arm of *Podium I* do indeed extend beneath the base courses of the northern megalithic wall. As Lohmann concludes: "Based on these findings, it becomes evident that beneath the Jupiter temple lie the remains of an older structure, as first proposed by Krencker and von Gerkan"¹³².

Figure 54. Lohmann's reconstruction of the original extent of the "Hellenistic" T-shaped Podium I. Taken from Lohmann (2017a, p. 128)

Lohmann believes that the maximum extent of the T-shaped arms coincided with the northern and southern edges of the outer wall of megalithic *Podium II*, although von Gerkan's 1937 drawing hints at the possibility that the foundations may have extended even farther, at least on the northern side. While this evidence demonstrates that under no circumstances can *Podium II* be older than *Podium I*, it nevertheless leaves open the possibility that *Podium I* and the U-shaped megalithic wall embracing it on the northern, western, and southern sides may in fact be contemporaneous.

¹³² Lohmann (2017a), pp. 131–132

Perhaps a more accurate way of characterizing Lohmann’s findings – at least as far as the northern T-shaped arm of Podium I is concerned – is to suggest that *Podium I* and *Podium II* share the same foundations. There is, moreover, little archaeological evidence to support the idea that the T-shaped wing walls of *Podium I* were demolished during the Roman imperial period. These walls may in fact have remained in place long afterwards and only been dismantled in the Byzantine or Arabic period in order to extract stone blocks for reuse in later construction. It would make little sense for Roman builders to demolish an already existing, carefully laid foundation of massive stone blocks, only to replace it with a stone “packing” intended to achieve precisely the same result.

2. Was Podium II ever a podium?

Hancock’s next observation concerns the fact that *Podium II* can scarcely be described as a podium at all, since it does not support any superstructure above it¹³³. He questions whether the Romans would truly have expended such extraordinary engineering effort – employing stone blocks weighing between 400 and 800 tons – if their sole intention had been merely to conceal the earlier and supposedly “unfashionable” *Podium I*. The resulting arrangement would, moreover, have left the Temple of Jupiter standing somewhat awkwardly upon a vastly oversized platform relative to its dimensions, necessitating the unusual solution of erecting a *crepis* – a feature more typical of earlier Greek and Hellenistic temples – on top of what Lohmann describes as a canonical Roman podium.

By way of comparison, the columns of the nearby Temple of Bacchus stand directly on the edge of their podium, rather than being set 10.7 meters inward, as it would have been the case with the Temple of Jupiter had *Podium II* been completed.

Whether *Podium II* was constructed after, or contemporaneously with, *Podium I*, one geometric relationship remains consistent: the distance between the column bases of the Temple of Jupiter and the outer edge of *Podium II* measures a constant 10.7 meters. By contrast, the distance between the outer edges of *Podium I* and *Podium II* is 10.7 meters on the northern and southern sides, but only 9.4 meters on the western side. It was in order to compensate for this discrepancy that the column bases on the western side of the Temple of Jupiter

¹³³ Hancock (2015), pp. 264-265.

had to be set 1.3 meters farther inward relative to the edge of the *Podium I* platform.

Figure 55. 3D model view showing the offset between the column bases on the western side of the Jupiter Temple and the edge of the Podium I platform. © Marco M. Vigato.

If *Podium II* is assumed to be a Roman construction added after *Podium I*, the most straightforward explanation for this discrepancy would be an attempt to correct the anomalous offset of the western temple façade relative to the edge of *Podium I*. In this scenario, the Romans would have narrowed the western gap in order to regularize the temple's position within an enlarged podium.

An alternative interpretation, however, reverses the logic. The offset of the column bases may instead have been introduced to preserve a constant distance between the temple and the outer edge of the megalithic U-shaped wall. If so, the outer megalithic wall must already have been in place at the time the temple was laid out. This explanation appears more persuasive, since if the sole objective had been to adapt a canonical Roman temple to an earlier platform of unsuitable proportions, the same corrective offset could have been applied more easily on the eastern side, where it could have been resolved by a simple adjustment to the temple's stairway, rather than by altering the alignment of the entire western façade.

The possibility that *Podium II* predates the construction of the Roman temple – and should therefore not be regarded simply as an expansion of *Podium I* – is further strengthened by Kalayan’s discovery of a full-scale architectural drawing of the temple pediment incised on the upper surface of the southernmost block of the *Trilithon*. Lohmann has taken this drawing as evidence that the *Trilithon* itself was being constructed at the same time as the temple. Yet the drawing, strictly speaking, demonstrates only that the *Trilithon* was already in place by the time construction of the temple had reached the level of the column capitals – and quite possibly long before.

Figure 56. Overlay of construction drawings on the upper face of the Trilithon stone blocks with the pediment of the Jupiter temple. Drawing: Lohmann, based on: Kalayan 1969, Fig. 1 (top) and Wiegand 1921, p.58 (right)

This observation leads naturally to a broader question: does the shape and profile of *Podium II*, in fact, conform to that of a canonical Roman podium? At first glance, the preparation marks visible on the stones appear to suggest such an intention. Each block shows traces of a profile typical of Roman podium architecture, consisting of a lower base, an inward-sloping lip, a vertical shaft, and an upper, outward-sloping lip. Significantly, however, these preparations occur at the very edges of the blocks, in positions so fragile that they could only have been made after the stones had been transported from the quarry and set in place.

This is precisely what can be observed along the northern wall and parts of the southern megalithic wall, where the colossal blocks remain largely rough and rectangular – unfinished masses of stone evidently intended to be carved into their final form at a later stage, once the joints had been laid out and the overall design fixed. In this light, it becomes entirely plausible that the Roman builders intended not to construct *Podium II* from scratch, but to rework an already existing megalithic wall, reshaping its outer faces to give it the appearance of a canonical Roman podium. Achieving this would have required nothing more than the removal of sufficient material from each block to impose the desired profile.

Figure 57. View of semi-finished 400-ton stone blocks along the southern side of the megalithic enclosure wall, showing the process by which the stones were shaped in the form of a canonical Roman temple podium. © Marco M. Vigato.

If the megalithic wall was not originally conceived as a podium, then what was it? According to Hancock, it was precisely what it appears to be: a massive U-shaped wall forming part of a vast megalithic enclosure¹³⁴. As we shall see when we turn to the reconstruction of the original appearance of the pre-Roman platform, this hypothesis may carry considerable more weight than it has so far been acknowledged.

¹³⁴ Hancock (2015), p. 259.

3. *The reason for using large stones*

Another argument advanced by Hancock concerns the question of why the Romans would have employed such enormous stone blocks in the construction of a wall that is entirely non-load bearing, intended to support nothing but its own weight¹³⁵. Even more perplexing is the fact that the largest stones are not placed at the base. Instead, the immense *Trilithon* blocks – some weighing between 800 and 1,000 tons – rest atop courses of stones weighing 300 to 400 tons, which in turn sit upon much smaller blocks, in some cases no heavier than 15 or 20 tons. Such an arrangement does not appear to follow any obvious structural logic, unless the sole intention was to impress.

Yet if the goal was merely to impress, why reserve the largest stones for the back and the sides of the temple, rather than the front, where they would have certainly created the greatest impression?

Even today, appreciating the scale of the megalithic podium and the *Trilithon* requires a lengthy circuit around the temple complex. In antiquity, the effect would have been even more muted, since no direct access existed between the level of the Altar Court and that of the temple platform.

One possible explanation is that the placement of the largest stones in the upper courses conferred additional solidity upon the wall by exerting a form of “pre-compression” on the lower levels. This interpretation points toward a very different understanding of the wall’s function. Rather than being designed to support a massive superstructure, the use of such enormous megaliths may have been intended to resist intense lateral pressures.

What, then, could have generated such forces? It is unlikely that they originated from within the enclosure, since much of the interior was occupied by the tower-like Podium I, itself a stable and self-supporting structure. The only plausible source of sustained lateral pressure would therefore have come from outside the wall. The most obvious candidate is water. In this light, the U-shaped megalithic wall may have functioned as a colossal breakwater, designed to shield the inner structure from the periodic and catastrophic floods known to have affected the Baalbek region since antiquity. One particularly striking historical account describes a flood powerful enough to sweep away an entire four-story tower constructed wholly of stone¹³⁶.

¹³⁵ Hancock (2015), p. 265.

¹³⁶ Alouf (1905), p. 65.

Seen from this perspective, the rationale behind the construction of the massive megalithic wall around *Podium I* – and the use of extraordinarily large stones capable of withstanding immense lateral forces – becomes considerably more intelligible.

4. The column drum in the foundations of the Trilithon.

Perhaps the only archaeological element that can be securely dated and that might therefore point to the precise epoch of construction of the *Trilithon* and the megalithic U-shaped wall surrounding *Podium I* is a column drum from the Roman Temple of Jupiter found embedded in the foundations beneath the *Trilithon*.

Figure 58. The column drum in the foundations of the Trilithon. From Lohmann (2017a, p. 135)

Hancock does not dispute the provenance of the fragment, acknowledging that it indeed comes from the Temple of Jupiter¹³⁷. What he questions instead is its chronological significance. In his view, the column drum may have been inserted into the foundations as part of a later Arabic repair, and would therefore have no bearing on the original construction date of the *Trilithon* or the

¹³⁷ Hancock (2015), p. 281.

megalithic podium itself. Hancock draws attention to the way the fragment protrudes conspicuously from the foundation courses beneath the *Trilithon*, standing out, as he puts it, “*like a sore thumb*”¹³⁸. While it is true that the block is neatly dressed and precisely cut, the same can be said of numerous ashlar and column fragments that were clearly reused during the construction and repair of the Arabic fortress.

Hancock further asks why the Roman builders would have resorted to the use of a discarded column fragment in the foundations of their temple when they presumably had an ample supply of regular stone blocks at their disposal. To this question one may add another: why is this column drum the only apparently reused architectural element within the entire stretch of foundations beneath the megalithic wall?

An additional and particularly striking feature of the column drum is its noticeably darker coloration, a characteristic also observed by Hancock¹³⁹. Given that the stone is of the same type as the surrounding ashlar, one would expect it to display a similar surface appearance had it remained buried within the foundations for the same length of time. Instead, its darker, oxidized patina strongly suggests prolonged exposure to the elements. Such an appearance would be entirely consistent with a fragment derived from a fallen column following the destruction of the temple. Numerous comparable column fragments embedded in the Arabic fortifications, or scattered throughout the Altar Court, exhibit the same darkened surface and weathered patina – features that can only result from long-term exposure.

In a private communication with Hancock, Lohmann argued that if a stone had been removed from the wall and replaced by a column drum, the stones above it would necessarily have collapsed¹⁴⁰. This objection, however, does not take into account the structural logic of a wall constructed with alternating headers and stretchers. In such a system, it is entirely possible to remove a stretcher without causing the headers above it to fall, since each header spans several rows of stretchers that would continue to support its weight.

¹³⁸ Ibid.

¹³⁹ Hancock (2015), p. 283.

¹⁴⁰ Hancock (2015), pp. 282-283.

Figure 59. Drawing showing the principle behind the construction of a wall formed of alternating rows of headers and stretchers. Even if the stone highlighted in red is removed, the blocks above will not fall.

The most plausible explanation, therefore, is that the column drum was inserted into the wall beneath the *Trilithon* during the Arabic period, likely as part of an effort to reinforce the foundations following one of the many sieges endured by the fortress of Baalbek over the course of its thousand-year history.

5. The silence of literary sources.

This argument rests less on the apparent absence of literary references to Baalbek in the pre-Roman period – a question already addressed earlier in this presentation – than on the fact that no Roman emperor, architect, or patron ever appears to have claimed responsibility for the construction of the *Trilithon*. As Frederik Ragette observed with characteristic clarity:

*“The real mystery of Baalbek is the total absence of written records on its construction. Which emperor would not have wished to share the fame of its creation? Which architect would not have thought to inscribe his name proudly on one of the countless blocks of stone? It is as if Heliopolitan Jupiter alone takes all the credit”*¹⁴¹.

¹⁴¹ Ragette (1980), p. 119.

Setting aside the possibility of a *damnatio memoriae*, it remains deeply puzzling that not a single inscription or literary source makes explicit reference to the construction of the *Trilithon* – especially when one considers the wealth of surviving accounts describing the transport and erection of far smaller monuments, such as obelisks, in Rome and elsewhere in the Roman world.

Several examples exist from other parts of the Baalbek temple complex to show that the ancient builders and patrons were certainly not shy when it came to taking credit for the completion of important parts of the sanctuary¹⁴². The question is: Why not the *Trilithon*?

6. *The rate of erosion on the stones.*

Several alternative researchers have drawn attention to the heavily weathered surfaces of the *Trilithon* stone blocks and of the stones forming the outer megalithic wall – particularly on the northern side – as evidence for their greater antiquity than the comparatively fresher Roman masonry visible elsewhere at the site¹⁴³. While this argument may carry a degree of plausibility, estimating rates of stone erosion is notoriously problematic and can rarely provide either an absolute or even a reliable relative chronology.

Moreover, it remains unclear to what extent the observed weathering is genuinely the result of age, rather than a consequence of the unfinished state of the *Trilithon* and the megalithic wall, which leaves the blocks with a rougher, less worked appearance. Many of the unquestionably Roman preparations around the joints of the megalithic blocks appear remarkably fresh, with sharp angles and clearly visible tool marks. This stands in marked contrast to the outer faces of the same blocks, where the “boss” surfaces display little or no evidence of finishing or tooling.

By comparison, even some of the unfinished blocks still lying in the quarry exhibit clearly defined tool marks, sharp edges, and relatively smooth surfaces. In their case, the comparatively good state of preservation may be explained by the fact that these stones lay partially buried for much of their existence, and were therefore shielded from prolonged exposure to weathering and erosion.

¹⁴² See for instance the inscriptions on the column bases of the propylon and the various dedicatory inscriptions in the Great Court.

¹⁴³ See: Andrew Collins, “Baalbek: Lebanon’s Sacred Fortress”, cit.

Figure 60. Heavily weathered megalithic stone blocks on the northern side of the megalithic enclosure wall. Note the different coloration and erosion rate compared to the blocks forming Podium I in background. © Marco M. Vigato.

Figure 61. The huge Hajar-el-Hibla stone in the quarry of Baalbek, showing similar weathering and discoloration on its exposed surface. © Marco M. Vigato

The Myth of the Megalith

Unlike some authors who assume that the construction of the *Trilithon* – and the movement of stone blocks weighing well in excess of 1,000 tons – must have exceeded the capabilities of Roman engineering, Hancock adopts a more nuanced position. He readily acknowledges that the *Trilithon* could be Roman, while remaining open to the possibility that it may instead be the work of an earlier culture. As he puts it:

*“Still...let’s accept that it can be done, that similar things have been done, and of course, for the evidence is before our eyes, that it was done at Baalbek. The only question that matters, therefore, is whether it was the Romans who did it, or whether they, and the cultures that preceded them here going back 10,000 years or more, found the U-shaped megalithic wall already in place and fitted their structures into its embrace”*¹⁴⁴.

Hancock points to numerous historical examples demonstrating that the transport of extremely large stone blocks was not beyond ancient – or even early modern – engineering capabilities. Among these is the Lateran Obelisk, originally weighing approximately 413 tons, which was transported from Karnak to Rome in 357 CE during the reign of Emperor Constantius II. Similarly impressive is the 327-ton obelisk of Caligula, shipped from Egypt to Rome aboard a specially constructed vessel so large that it was later deliberately sunk to form part of the breakwater of the Port of Claudius, with a lighthouse erected on top of it. From a later period, Hancock also cites the celebrated transport of the 1,250-ton Thunder Stone in eighteenth-century Russia, hauled over seven kilometers on ice and bronze ball bearings before being floated to Saint Petersburg to serve as the pedestal for a statue of Peter the Great.

By comparison, the stone blocks forming the lower megalithic course of Podium I weigh approximately 470 tons, while each of the three *Trilithon* blocks weighs at least 800 tons in their present state, and would have approached 1,000 tons prior to the removal of the outer “boss.” Even larger megaliths remain in the quarry about one kilometer away, the largest of which weighs an estimated 1,650 tons.

¹⁴⁴ Hancock (2015), p. 276.

Roman builders at Baalbek also demonstrated extraordinary feats of lifting, not merely horizontal transport. Numerous stone blocks weighing tens of tons – and in some cases over 100 tons – were raised to heights exceeding 20 meters to form the architraves, friezes, and pediments of the Temple of Jupiter. The architrave blocks alone weigh over 60 tons each, with at least one corner block estimated at over 100 tons, or as much as 360 tons according to some calculations¹⁴⁵. Likewise, the lateral lintel blocks above the main doorway of the Temple of Bacchus, each weighing over 120 tons, were lifted to a height of more than 18 meters using hoisting machines, pulleys, and capstans¹⁴⁶. All of these achievements are unquestionably Roman.

There can therefore be little doubt that Roman engineers were capable of moving and positioning blocks of enormous size. As Hancock himself concedes:

*“The Romans were incredibly accomplished builders, and they were absolutely capable of moving and placing monstrously huge and heavy blocks of stone. If there is an argument for a lost civilization to be made at Baalbek then it can’t be based on the block weights, or on naïve, ill-informed notions about what the Romans could or couldn’t do, because in the realm of building, the evidence all around me confirms they could do pretty much anything they chose to”*¹⁴⁷.

Accepting, then, that the movement of the Baalbek megaliths lay within the reach of Roman engineering, the question shifts from whether it *could* be done to *how* it was done.

One of the earliest systematic attempts to answer this question was proposed in 1977 by the French engineer Jean-Pierre Adam, in a now classic article published in the journal *Syria*. Adam initially considered the possibility that the *Trilithon* blocks were dragged on wooden rollers by oxen, but quickly rejected this hypothesis on practical grounds: moving a single *Trilithon* stone on level ground would have required an estimated 825 oxen, for which there was just not enough space¹⁴⁸.

¹⁴⁵ Hancock (2015), p. 250; Ragette (1980), p. 107; Christian and Barbara Joy o’Brien, *The Shining Ones*, Cirencester: Dianthus Publishing, 2001, p. 272

¹⁴⁶ Klaus Rheidt (2022), “Large Stones, Big Challenge?”, in E. A. Dumser and D. Borbonus (Editors), *Building the Classical World*, pp. 170-188.

¹⁴⁷ Hancock (2015), p. 250.

¹⁴⁸ Jean Pierre Adam (1977), “A propos du Trilithon de Baalbek”, *Syria*, 54 (1-2), pp. 31-63.

Adam instead proposed the use of capstans powered by human labor. A capstan is a vertical-axis rotating machine that multiplies pulling force through the use of horizontal bars and wound cables. In his reconstruction, a capstan equipped with six bars could be operated by 24 men exerting a combined force of 480 kilograms. Using the lever principle, and with four hemp cables wound around the drum, this force could be multiplied to generate a traction of over 13 tons per capstan after accounting for friction. Six such machines, operated by 144 men, would thus provide a combined pulling force of approximately 78 tons – sufficient to move an 800-ton stone block supported on wooden rollers on a plane¹⁴⁹.

Fig. 18. — Trilithon de Baalbek. Phase finale du transport.

Figure 62. Transportation of the Trilithon blocks with the use of capstans. Drawing by Jean-Pierre Adam. (1977), p. 60.

For the final placement of the blocks, however, Adam recognized that rollers posed a serious problem: once the stones reached their intended position, the rollers would have to be removed from beneath them. To address this, he proposed replacing the rollers with a lubricated sliding surface, possibly using wet clay. This method would require a much greater horizontal force – on the order of 533 tons. Adam calculated that this could be achieved using sixteen capstans, each equipped with eight bars and operated by a total of 512 men,

¹⁴⁹ Ibid., p. 56

producing a combined force of approximately 557 tons¹⁵⁰. The model thus offered a technically coherent solution for both the transport and final positioning of the *Trilithon* blocks.

Further support for the use of capstans was provided by a 2015 article by Jeanine Abdul Massih, who identified a circular wear mark compatible with capstan use during excavations near the quarry in 2014¹⁵¹. Abdul Massih also reconstructed the extraction process, suggesting that the natural stratification of the nummulitic limestone dictated the height of the megaliths. Trenches were cut around and beneath each block, ropes anchored to prevent slippage, and rollers inserted beneath the stones once separation was complete. The road linking the quarry to the temple was then graded to match the bedding level of each course, eliminating the need for vertical lifting. The numerous square or rectangular holes visible on the stones and in the quarry mark the insertion points for pegs or pins used to secure hauling ropes¹⁵².

Figure 63. Machine and scaffolding used for raising and lowering the Trilithon blocks, according to Ragette (1980), p. 118

¹⁵⁰ Ibid., p. 61.

¹⁵¹ Abdul Massih, Jeanine (2015), "The Megalithic Quarry of Baalbek - Sector III the Megaliths of hajjar al-Hibla", *Journal of Eastern Mediterranean Archaeology and Heritage Studies*, vol. 3, No. 4, 2015, pp. 314-329.

¹⁵² Ibid., p. 325.

A major difficulty with Adam’s reconstruction, however, lies in the extremely limited space between *Podium I* and *Podium II*. If *Podium I* indeed predates *Podium II*, there would have been insufficient room on the narrow terrace between them to accommodate the large number of capstans required for the final positioning of the *Trilithon* blocks. Friedrich Ragette’s alternative proposal – using lewis, pulleys, and scaffolding to lower the blocks into place – faces similar spatial constraints¹⁵³. Moreover, no lewis holes exist on the upper faces of the *Trilithon* blocks; only square peg holes are present, identical to those found on unfinished stones in both the podium and the quarry.

To address these objections, Lohmann and Rheidt have proposed an alternative method involving sandbags¹⁵⁴. In this model, once a block reached the construction site, its weight was transferred to lateral sand baskets using ropes and beams inserted through the rectangular peg holes. The block was then lowered gradually by releasing the sand in a controlled manner. As the stone descended, its lower and lateral faces could be carefully prepared to ensure a precise fit with adjacent blocks. The removal of the boss would have erased all traces of the peg holes in the process.

Figure 64. Rheidt’s proposed lifting method for the Trilithon stones. From Rheidt (2022), p. 182.

As Rheidt notes, the thirty-two stones transported and installed in the podium of the Temple of Jupiter “*appear to have caused no insurmountable problems for the master builders.*” Indeed, the bosses were not even removed prior to transport – an omission that would have significantly reduced their weight – indicating that all finishing was deliberately left to the building site, where the joints were carefully articulated to emphasize the monumental scale of each block¹⁵⁵.

Several factors likely explain why such enormous stones were employed at Baalbek. The absence of adequate subsoil foundations, the need for seismic

¹⁵³ Ragette (1980), pp. 118-119.

¹⁵⁴ Rheidt (2022), pp. 181-182.

¹⁵⁵ Rheidt (2022), p. 175.

resistance, and the sheer efficiency of quarrying large blocks from homogeneous stone beds all played a role. As Jean-Claude Bessac has argued, megalithic construction in Lebanon was facilitated by favorable geological conditions and could, paradoxically, have proved more economical than a comparable small-blocks construction¹⁵⁶. For example, to match the volume of a single 60-ton block measuring $3 \times 7 \times 1$ meters would require 378 brick-sized stones, necessitating far more quarrying, cutting, and material loss¹⁵⁷. Even accounting for the preparation of ramps and terrain, megalithic construction may have been 25–33% less labor-intensive than conventional masonry¹⁵⁸.

At Baalbek, conditions were especially favorable: the quarry lay less than 900 meters from the temple and at a slightly higher elevation. By contrast, the transport of the 186 monolithic granite columns of the Great Court – each weighing seven tons – from Aswan required a journey of some 1,800 kilometers by river, sea, and mountain routes exceeding 1,100 meters in elevation¹⁵⁹.

In the end, none of this proves that the Romans *did* in fact build the *Trilithon* – only that they *could* have done so. The question therefore remains. If Roman engineering capability alone cannot decide the issue, we must once again examine the construction sequence of *Podium I* and *Podium II* to determine whether it would in fact have been possible, as Lohmann suggests, to erect a megalithic structure of the scale of *Podium II* outside and around a pre-existing *Podium I*.

The complexity of moving large stones

Jean-Pierre Adam (1977) and others have shown that, through the use of capstans and the coordinated labor of hundreds of men, it was technically possible to move stones as large as the Baalbek *Trilithon* across flat ground or up moderately inclined ramps. As noted in the previous chapter, however, such reconstructions often overlook the additional and very real constraints imposed by the construction sequence of the Jupiter temple platform and by the presence of pre-existing structures.

¹⁵⁶ Jean Claude Bessac (2010), “Le mégalithisme antique au Proche-Orient : idées reçues et données Nouvelles”, *Syria*, 87, pp. 173-190.

¹⁵⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁵⁹ Rheidt (2022), p. 170.

The principal objection to the use of capstans lies in the extremely limited space available between *Podium I* and *Podium II* for the installation and operation of dozens of such devices. A useful comparison is provided by the celebrated operation carried out by Domenico Fontana in 1586, when the 327-ton Vatican obelisk was moved from the ruins of the Circus of Nero to its present position in Saint Peter's Square, a distance of roughly 250 meters. Fontana employed 900 men, 140 horses, and 44 winches¹⁶⁰. Contemporary engravings vividly convey the enormous scale of the undertaking, with almost the entirety of Saint Peter's Square filled with capstans, ropes, ramps, and wooden scaffolding.

Figure 65. The transportation and erection of the 327-ton Vatican obelisk in Saint Peter's Square, Rome, in 1586, in an engraving by Niccolò Zabaglia (1743).

Saint Peter's Square, however, is an immense open space – approximately 360 meters long and 240 meters wide – entirely unlike the confined conditions at

¹⁶⁰ Domenico Fontana, *Della trasportatione dell'obelisco vaticano et delle fabbriche di nostro signore Papa Sisto V*, Rome, 1590. See also: Ragette (1980), pp. 118-119.

Baalbek. There, the distance between *Podium I* and the outer edge of the megalithic enclosure wall is less than 10.75 meters, leaving only a narrow corridor less than six meters wide between the two. Even if one accepts that the *Trilithon* stones could in principle have been moved using capstans, it is simply inconceivable that the hundreds of men and dozens of winches depicted in Fontana's engravings for the transport of a much smaller obelisk could have been accommodated within such a cramped and restricted space.

Figure 66. The cramped, almost claustrophobic space between the Trilithon (bottom left and center) and Podium I (right). Notice the enormous stone blocks allegedly part of the “packing” used to fill the space between the two podia, and part of a column shaft from the temple of Jupiter. © Marco M. Vigato

This spatial constraint alone would appear to rule out the idea that *Podium I* could possibly predate the outer megalithic enclosure (Lohmann's *Podium II*), since such a sequence would have made the installation of the megalithic enclosure wall practically impossible. At the same time, the archaeological evidence suggesting that *Podium I* and the outer enclosure share the same foundations renders the opposite scenario – namely that *Podium II* predates *Podium I* – equally implausible.

The only remaining possibility is that *Podium I* and *Podium II* were conceived and constructed contemporaneously, as parts of a single, unified project. Only

under this scenario would there have been sufficient space to maneuver the enormous stones of the megalithic enclosure. If *Podium I* was being raised at the same time as the outer wall, it would have provided an ideal, expansive platform for anchoring the capstans required to move the blocks. Each capstan would have needed to be firmly secured, and few anchoring points could have been more suitable than a massive megalithic platform, level with the enclosure wall and measuring roughly 50 by 100 meters. With an area of approximately 5,000 square meters, such a platform may have offered just enough space to accommodate the dozens of capstans and hundreds of workers required for the task.

Once the first megalithic course had been laid, it is possible that a different technique was adopted for positioning the upper courses. To achieve a perfect fit between adjacent blocks, each stone may have been lowered vertically into place rather than dragged horizontally by means of capstans – a method first suggested by Ragette¹⁶¹. This would also explain why, at this stage, the *Podium I* platform appears to have stood higher than the outer enclosure wall.

Such a sequence would further account for the differing patterns of peg holes observed on the stones. While the blocks of the lower course display numerous peg holes along their sides, the *Trilithon* blocks exhibit peg holes only on their upper faces. These holes most plausibly mark the points at which ropes were attached to maneuver the stones. Peg holes located on the upper faces, rather than the sides, suggest that the blocks were not merely dragged horizontally, but were at least partially suspended and possibly lowered vertically from a higher position. A similar technique may also have been employed for some of the stones in the lower course, both to reduce friction and to ensure exceptionally tight joints.

A possible reconstruction of the process is therefore as follows. Each block was first brought close to its intended position using capstans anchored to the megalithic platform, positioned at or slightly above the level of the course being laid. The platform was then raised sufficiently to allow the erection of a wooden scaffolding around the stone, enabling it to be suspended vertically by means of pegs inserted into its upper face – without requiring true lifting. With the stone thus suspended, the rollers beneath it could be removed. To ensure a perfect fit, the scaffolding may have incorporated metal bearings or rails allowing limited horizontal movement, so that adjoining faces could be repeatedly brought

¹⁶¹ Ragette (1980), pp. 114-119.

together and adjusted until all irregularities were eliminated. Only then would the block have been lowered carefully into its final position. The same procedure could have been repeated for the upper courses, with the inner platform rising in tandem with the enclosure wall.

One potential objection to this reconstruction concerns the peg holes themselves. If these were indeed used for suspending the stones, they appear too small, irregular, and unevenly spaced to have housed lewis irons capable of lifting or supporting such immense weights. In some cases, the holes are not even square, but circular. If so, a different suspension method must have been employed – perhaps the sand-bagging technique proposed by Lohmann and Rheidt¹⁶² – allowing the stones to be lowered in a controlled manner while the rollers were removed and the joints refined.

It is also possible that, after the three *Trilithon* stones had been set in the second course, a decision was taken to abandon further construction of the enclosure wall and to concentrate instead on completing the inner temple platform. Such a decision would have rendered the continuation of the enclosure wall impracticable, since the increased height of the inner platform would have eliminated the space and level support needed for additional capstans.

A final unresolved issue concerns the mysterious saw marks visible on some of the stones. Friedrich Ragette is among the few scholars to have addressed these marks in any detail. He suggests that the Romans may have employed a form of quarrying machine, as indicated by concentric circular impact patterns observed on certain blocks – marks too large to have been produced manually. These suggest a cutting tool mounted on an adjustable lever, capable of striking the stone with great force, with swinging radii of up to four meters¹⁶³.

By contrast, the evidence of mechanical sawing visible on some of the granite columns of the Altar Court is almost certainly of later date. Such marks are best explained by the operation of a Byzantine stone sawmill at Baalbek, comparable to those attested at Jerash, Hierapolis, and Ephesus around the same time¹⁶⁴. Installed after the temples had fallen into disrepair, this sawmill would have been used to recycle valuable granite columns into paving slabs, likely destined for churches and palaces in Constantinople.

¹⁶² Rheidt (2022), p. 182.

¹⁶³ Ragette (1980), p. 115.

¹⁶⁴ Seigne (2022), pp. 205-213.

Part IV – A Novel Construction Scenario

A question of foundations

Since the earliest German excavations at the end of the nineteenth century, it has been clear that the key to understanding the origins of the Baalbek temple complex lies not in its spectacular superstructures, but in the careful and systematic study of its foundations. Already by 1937, archaeologists had recognized that the massive podium of the Temple of Jupiter incorporates the remains of an earlier building – commonly referred to as *Podium I* – beneath its platform. On stylistic grounds, and by comparison with so-called “Herodian” masonry of the late first century BCE and early first century CE, this earlier structure is generally assigned to the Late Hellenistic or Early Roman period¹⁶⁵. Such a dating, however, remains hypothetical until it can be confirmed by absolute methods, such as radiometric dating or optically stimulated luminescence (OSL).

Evidence gathered by Krencker and von Gerkan, and more recently confirmed through excavation by Lohmann, demonstrates conclusively that the construction of the megalithic *Podium II* cannot predate *Podium I*. Although Lohmann has sought to interpret *Podium II* as a later, monumental expansion of *Podium I* during the Roman imperial period, the considerations presented in the previous chapter regarding the movement of the *Trilithon* blocks point to the logistical impossibility of transporting stones of such enormous size around a pre-existing structure. The only plausible conclusion, therefore, is that *Podium I* and *Podium II* must be contemporaneous.

The archaeological evidence shows that *Podium II* shares, at least in part, the same foundations as the northern – and almost certainly the southern – arms of the originally T-shaped *Podium I*. The foundations upon which both *Podium I* and *Podium II* rest are therefore the most critical element for understanding the evolution and construction sequence of the temple complex. Paradoxically, they are also the least studied. Aside from the limited excavations already mentioned, remarkably little is known about their true extent and configuration. What is clear is that the foundations are solidly built of stone down to bedrock and incorporate exceptionally large blocks, as indicated by early German plans. Yet precise measurements of individual stones and course heights are lacking. Compounding the problem, the foundations of the temple *cella*, exposed during

¹⁶⁵ See: Lohmann (2011), pp. 38-5 and Lohmann (2017a), pp. 146-152.

excavations between 1898 and 1905, were subsequently reburied to facilitate visitor access, placing them beyond further scrutiny¹⁶⁶.

To support the immense weight of the platform above, the foundations had to reach extraordinary depths. Arthur Segal, author of one of the most comprehensive studies of Roman sanctuaries in the Near East, describes their depth as “astonishing”¹⁶⁷. A pit excavated by the German team near the southwest corner of the Temple of Bacchus revealed foundations exceeding 17 meters in depth¹⁶⁸. Beneath the *Trilithon* and the northern megalithic wall of the Temple of Jupiter, the foundations may be deeper still, as suggested by geophysical surveys using seismic and electrical resistivity methods (von Ess, 2008)¹⁶⁹. These findings reflect the highly irregular nature of the underlying bedrock, marked by deep fissures and ravines that the ancient builders were compelled to fill with massive stonework in order to create a level construction surface.

All major temple structures at Baalbek appear to rest directly on bedrock including the Small and Great Altars, whose foundations exceed seven meters in depth and remain partially exposed in the eastern excavation trench of the Altar Court¹⁷⁰. A close parallel can be drawn with Jerusalem, where the foundations of the massive platform of the Haram al-Sharif on the Temple Mount descend to equally extraordinary depths, particularly near the southwest and southeast corners.

In both cases – Baalbek and Jerusalem – the volume of stone invested in the foundations far exceeds that used in the visible buildings above. This is especially striking given the assumption that these foundations were never meant to be seen, but to remain entirely buried. Such an assumption, however, may be open to question. At Jerusalem, portions of the foundations below the ancient Herodian street level display the same finely dressed stone courses as the walls above ground, suggesting that they were originally visible and became only later buried by accumulated debris¹⁷¹.

¹⁶⁶ Lohmann (2017a), p. 24.

¹⁶⁷ Arthur Segal (2013), *Temples and Sanctuaries in the Roman Near East*, Oxford: Oxbow Books, p. 131.

¹⁶⁸ Wiegand (1923), pp. 1-2.

¹⁶⁹ Van Ess (2014), pp. 32-25.

¹⁷⁰ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 122-125.

¹⁷¹ Leen Ritmeyer (2006), *The Quest: Revealing the Temple Mount in Jerusalem*, Jerusalem: Carta, pp. 20-60.

Figure 67. A view of the western wall of Jerusalem's Temple Mount, with the Herodian street in the foreground. The masonry style and construction technique, employing alternating rows of headers and stretchers (up to 10 meters long), is identical to that of Podium I of Baalbek's Jupiter temple. Deep shafts excavated along the base of the wall show that the same finished and dressed masonry continues for several meters below the Herodian street level. © Marco M. Vigato.

A similar pattern may be seen at Baalbek. Lohmann has noted that the first exposed courses beneath the megalithic podium exhibit the same careful jointing and dressed margins as the megalithic courses above, implying that at least part of the foundations may originally have been intended to remain visible¹⁷². This observation carries significant implications for the chronology of construction. The positions of the entrances to the cryptoporticuses indicate that the Roman ground level was broadly comparable to that of today, and that the deep foundations beneath the northern megalithic wall and the *Trilithon* were only re-exposed when a defensive moat was dug around the complex after its conversion into a fortress during the medieval period.

It would make little sense to construct finely dressed stone foundations if they were never meant to be seen, yet the evidence suggests that during the Roman period the courses immediately beneath the megalithic podium lay below ground level. Does this imply that these foundations were already ancient by the time the Roman temple was built, and became only gradually buried by centuries of soil accumulation?

¹⁷² Lohmann (2017a), p. 134.

On the southern side of the complex, the Roman ground level – measured from the base of the Roman doorways – stood at least 1.55 meters above the base of the megalithic wall¹⁷³, and this calculation accounts only for the visible blocks above ground. Lohmann attempts to explain this discrepancy by positing the existence of a stairway at the base of the wall, yet no archaeological evidence for such a feature has ever been identified. If the Romans were indeed the builders of the megalithic podium, the decision to conceal part of it below ground level would be puzzling – particularly if, as often assumed, the aim was to impress through monumentality.

Figure 68. Different views of the excavated foundations under the Parthenon of Athens, showing similar “Herodian” ashlars to those used at Baalbek and Jerusalem and the same construction technique employing alternating rows of headers and stretchers – evidence that this style of masonry was already in use centuries before the assumed construction date of the Baalbek and Jerusalem temples. From Martin Luther D’Ooge, *The Acropolis of Athens* (1909). Courtesy: Deutsche Archäologische Institut.

Taken as a whole, the foundations of the Baalbek temple platform emerge as the most enigmatic and least understood component of the entire complex. It is therefore striking that both academic and so-called alternative researchers have devoted relatively little attention to them, focusing instead almost exclusively on the spectacular architecture visible above ground. Yet it is precisely beneath

¹⁷³ Lohmann (2017a), p. 80.

the surface, in these colossal and largely unexplored foundations, that the most important clues to Baalbek's origins may yet lie.

An alternative construction sequence for Podium I and II

In light of the evidence discussed above concerning the temple's foundations, it is possible to propose an alternative construction and chronological sequence for *Podium I* and *Podium II*, differing from that suggested by Lohmann.

This alternative scenario assumes that *Podium I* and *Podium II* were erected synchronously, and that *Podium II* was originally conceived not as a podium at all, but as a free-standing megalithic enclosure – or girdle wall – surrounding *Podium I* on three sides, and possibly on all four. Only much later, during the Roman period, would the decision have been taken to adapt this enclosure wall as the outer foundation of a greatly enlarged podium for the Roman Temple of Jupiter, constructed atop *Podium I*.

Excavations by Krencker and von Gerkan established that the original *Podium I* was T-shaped, with two wing walls extending northward and southward from a point located between the sixth and seventh columns of the Roman temple, facing the Altar Court. Lohmann was able to trace the foundations of the northern T-arm beneath the base courses of the megalithic enclosure wall. Above ground, an approximately five-meter-wide section of the northern T-arm is preserved up to the level of the temple *crepis*, one course below the column bases of the Roman temple. On the southern side, several stone courses of the southern T-arm likewise lay exposed above the level of the enclosure wall.

This evidence demonstrates that neither the northern nor the southern arms of the original T-shaped *Podium I* were entirely demolished. Whether their partial dismantling occurred during the Roman or the later Arabic period remains uncertain. If it took place in Roman times, however, it would have been illogical to demolish a perfectly serviceable and solidly built platform only to replace it with a loose stone “packing” rising to the same height.

Even more revealing is a drawing by von Gerkan, which shows that the surviving masonry of the northern T-arm directly abuts – and effectively backs – the inner face of the northern megalithic wall. In Lohmann's reconstruction of the building sequence, the wing walls of *Podium I* must first have been removed to make room for the placement of the enormous base-course blocks

of *Podium II*. Yet von Gerkan’s drawing clearly indicates that the surviving portions of the T-arms of *Podium I* physically connect with the rear of the megalithic enclosure stones from the inside.

Figure 69. Enhanced details of Von Gerkan’s (1937) drawing showing the foundations of the Jupiter Temple. Podium I is shown in dark blue with the northern T-arm in light blue. The megalithic enclosure wall (Podium II) is shown in orange. This is evidence that the T-arms of Podium I were not demolished to allow for the construction of Podium II, and in fact remained in place through the Roman reconstruction. After Von Gerkan (1937) – Digitally enhanced.

Figure 70. The same sector of the Podium shown in 3D view, with the surviving portion of the northern T-arm of the “Hellenistic podium” extending towards the megalithic enclosure wall.

Figure 71. A photograph of the same area showing the surviving masonry from the northern T-arm of the “Hellenistic” podium. The very idea that the giant 400-ton stone blocks of the outer megalithic enclosure (bottom left) could have been moved and placed in direct contact with the northern termination of Podium I, in such a tight and compressed space, completely strains credibility. A far more likely scenario is that the megalithic enclosure wall and the T-shaped Podium I were both constructed at the same time. © Marco M. Vigato.

If the transport and placement of 300-ton blocks within a corridor barely ten meters wide between *Podium I* and *Podium II* would already have posed immense challenges, the notion that this could have been accomplished directly against, and in contact with, a pre-existing wall strains credibility. The only scenario that plausibly provides sufficient maneuvering space for the largest stones is one in which *Podium I* and the outer megalithic enclosure were planned and constructed at the same time.

What emerges from this reconstruction is a structure very different from a canonical Roman or Hellenistic temple podium. The original complex may have consisted of a vast T-shaped megalithic platform approximately 95 meters long and 47.8 meters wide at its narrowest point, with the two T-arms branching off some 61.3 meters from the western end, giving the platform a frontal width of 69.2 meters. If the T-arms extended farther north and south – as suggested by the placement of enormous megalithic blocks perpendicular to the enclosure wall near the Altar Court – then the total width of the platform would have approached its full length of 95 meters.

This immense platform would have been enclosed on three sides by a monumental girdle wall constructed of even larger megalithic blocks, possibly intended to protect the structure from catastrophic flooding – an interpretation consistent with the extraordinary dimensions of the stones employed. The enclosure wall may originally have consisted of at least two, and possibly three, colossal stone courses, with the *Trilithon* forming part of the middle course on the western side.

Figure 72. Tentative reconstruction of the possible intended final aspect of the pre-Roman, T-shaped megalithic platform under the Jupiter Temple of Baalbek. Only the first course of the megalithic enclosure wall and part of the second course on the western side were completed. © Marco M. Vigato

Nothing is known about the superstructure that this platform was intended to support. It may have remained unfinished, or it may have been entirely dismantled when the Romans undertook the construction of the Temple of Jupiter. It is also possible that, when the enclosure wall was repurposed to enlarge the podium, stones from the earlier structure were reused in the massive “packing” that fills the space between *Podium I* and the outer wall. As already noted, this packing contains some exceptionally large blocks that may originally have been destined for an even more ambitious project.

Figure 73. General layout of Jupiter Sanctuary with T-shaped platform and megalithic enclosure wall. © Marco M. Vigato

The overall plan of this hypothetical structure bears a striking resemblance to that of Egyptian temples, particularly those of the Ptolemaic period. Both its proportions and layout recall temples such as that of Horus at Edfu or Hathor at Dendera – monuments dating to the third through first centuries BCE, yet themselves rooted in much older architectural traditions. In this context, the long-noted association between Baalbek-Heliopolis and the Egyptian Heliopolis takes on added significance, as do Macrobius’ reference to the cult statue of Baalbek being brought from Egypt and Lucian’s description of the sanctuary as “Egyptian”.

Figure 74. Layout comparison of Baalbek temple platform and Great Court (right) with the layout of the Ptolemaic Egyptian temple of Edfu. Both temples follow a similar T-shaped layout, with a girdle wall encircling the temple in such a way as to only leave a narrow corridor between the two. © Marco M. Vigato.

The poor state of preservation of several elements of the complex – especially on the eastern end of *Podium I*, where entire sections were repaired or rebuilt in Roman times – suggests that the original construction was already in a state of decay when the Romans initiated their monumental redevelopment in the first century CE.

Ultimately, much of the persuasive force of Lohmann’s argument for an early Roman date for *Podium I* rests on the presence of drafted-margin masonry closely resembling the “Herodian” stonework of late first-century BCE and early first-century CE buildings in Israel and Palestine, including the Temple Mount in Jerusalem and the megalithic enclosures of Hebron and Mamre. The western wall of the Temple Mount itself contains blocks weighing over 450 tons, and possibly as much as 525 tons¹⁷⁴.

Figure 75. Drafted masonry in the fortress on Tall-e-Takht in Pasargadae, Iran, showing the same kind of finishing as the outer walls of Baalbek Podium I and Jerusalem’s Temple Mount. This structure in Pasargadae is believed to date to the reign of Cyrus the Great (559-530 BCE), showing that “Herodian” masonry was already in use throughout much of the Middle East centuries before the Roman and Hellenistic period. © Alain Vigato.

Yet drafted-margin masonry has a far longer and more complex history. It appears already in the Bronze Age Levant and again in the Persian period, for

¹⁷⁴ Ritmeyer (2006), p. 32.

example at Pasargadae. Its presence alone cannot therefore serve as definitive chronological evidence for dating the Baalbek temple platform. It is also possible that drafted margins were added at a later stage, perhaps to regularize or aesthetically enhance surfaces that had already suffered damage or weathering. Lohmann himself acknowledges that in several areas the faces of the stones were reworked, an intervention he attributes to the need to improve the connection between *Podium I* and the packing behind the enclosure wall¹⁷⁵.

In conclusion, Lohmann may well be correct in assuming that both *Podium I* and *Podium II* may indeed be Roman in origin. Yet the alternative cannot be dismissed: *Podium I* may have been contemporaneous with the megalithic enclosure and significantly earlier than the Roman temple built upon it. Until the foundations themselves can be dated by absolute methods, the question must therefore remain open.

Open Questions and Anomalies

A number of significant anomalies in the design and construction of the Baalbek temple complex remain insufficiently explained by Lohmann's reconstruction. Taken together, they point to unresolved issues that may lend further support to the possibility of a pre-Roman origin for *Podium I* and the megalithic enclosure wall that surrounds it.

1. The problem of the very large "Packing" stones between Podium I and II

Both Lohmann's reconstruction and the alternative scenario proposed here agree that the space between *Podium I* and the outer megalithic enclosure wall (Lohmann's *Podium II*) was ultimately filled with a massive "packing" of stone blocks. Where the two interpretations diverge is in the timing and purpose of this filling. In our view, the packing was not an original construction feature, but a later intervention, introduced when the Romans decided to expand the temple platform all the way to the enclosure wall.

Under this scenario, the Romans would have encountered an already existing T-shaped *Podium I* surrounded by an unfinished megalithic enclosure. Planning to erect an even larger and more ambitious temple – possibly a dodecastyle peripteral structure rather than the decastyle temple ultimately built – they would have filled the gap between *Podium I* and the enclosure wall with large

¹⁷⁵ Lohmann (2017a), p. 130.

Figure 77. Enormous “packing” stones on the back side of the Trilithon. There is no logical explanation for the use of such enormous blocks in what was meant to be a mere non-load-bearing filling layer between the two podia. © Marco M. Vigato

Most anomalous of all is its composition. The packing contains some exceptionally large stone blocks, particularly on the southern side and behind the *Trilithon*. The use of such massive stones for mere infill makes little sense unless they were already available on site. The most plausible source is therefore a demolished megalithic structure that once stood atop *Podium I*. If so, the presence of these blocks within the packing strongly suggests that the enclosure wall was already standing before the Roman temple was constructed.

2. The difference in stone lengths east and west of the Knicklinie

Lohmann notes that east of what he calls the *Knicklinie* – the point where the northern arm of *Podium I* meets the enclosure wall – the stone blocks become markedly shorter. Whereas blocks west of this line reach lengths of up to 13 meters, those to the east are typically only 2–3 meters long. A similar pattern likely existed on the south side, where the smaller stones east of the *Knicklinie* were more easily quarried away in the Arabic period.

Figure 78. Location of the “Knicklinie” on the visible northern face of Podium I. Notice how the size of the blocks and accuracy of the joints diminishes significantly to the left of the “Knicklinie”. © Marco M. Vigato.

One possible explanation is that this eastern section of wall was never intended to be visible, forming part of the core masonry of the massive T-arms of *Podium I*. Another possibility is that this portion of the wall belongs to a later construction phase than the western megalithic portion.

3. The eastern limits of the megalithic enclosure

While the megalithic enclosure wall can be traced almost continuously along the north, west, and south sides, its eastern extent beneath the Roman Altar Court remains unknown. The grand stairway of the temple is itself built from enormous stone blocks, into which multiple steps were carved. It is not inconceivable that these stones once formed the eastern side of the megalithic enclosure.

Figure 79. Wiegand's drawing of the foundations under the temple of Jupiter. Notice the enormous size of some of the stones forming the back of the eastern temple stairway, some of which nearly as large as the stones in the outer megalithic enclosure wall, of which the place now occupied by the stairway may have represented the original eastern termination prior to its Roman transformation. From Wiegand (1921), vol. 1, Plate 19.

4. The angular blocks at the eastern termination of Podium II

Figure 80. Enormous 400-ton stone block placed perpendicularly to the megalithic enclosure wall to the south of the Jupiter Temple platform. A similar block may have existed on the north side. © Marco M. Vigato

At the point where the enclosure wall disappears beneath the Altar Court, two enormous blocks are set perpendicular to it on the north and south sides. On the south side, one of these blocks survives intact over a length exceeding 10 meters. Their placement likely determined the western boundary of the Altar Court. Von Gerkan interpreted them as elements of a massive *temenos* wall enclosing an earlier, smaller Altar Court at a lower level¹⁷⁸.

5. The megalithic foundations near the northwest corner of the Altar Court

Figure 81. 3D model view of the megalithic foundation near the northwest corner of the Altar Court. These may belong to a planned westward extension of the Altar Court that would have completely surrounded the Jupiter Temple with porticoes, completely hiding and concealing the megalithic podium and enclosure wall from sight. © Marco M. Vigato

A further enigma is presented by a foundation of large megalithic blocks extending westward from the northwest corner of the Altar Court. Krencker and Ragette interpreted this as evidence for a planned western extension of the court, intended to encircle the Temple of Jupiter with porticoes and conceal the unfinished *Trilithon* podium. Lohmann instead proposes that it supported a small annex building, perhaps containing a stair or ramp connecting the court to the plain below¹⁷⁹. Since the foundation does not extend further west, any grand portico plan must have been abandoned early, and there is no evidence of a corresponding structure on the south side.

¹⁷⁸ Von Gerkan (1937), pp. 55-59

¹⁷⁹ (2017a), pp. 81-84.

6. *The large stone foundations at the bottom of Kalayan's well*

Exploration of Kalayan's well revealed four massive stone courses beginning about seven meters below the Roman Altar Court and extending down to the bedrock at nearly twelve meters depth¹⁸⁰. Above this level, the well shaft is lined with small stones bonded with mortar; below it, the shaft continues directly into bedrock to a depth of 50 meters. These deeply buried stone courses, consisting of huge ashlar comparable in height to those of *Podium I*, cannot belong to any known Roman structure. Their proximity to the temple stairway raises the possibility that the megalithic platform extended farther east beneath the Altar Court than previously assumed.

7. *The enlargement of the northern and southern cryptoporticuses*

Lohmann observes that the lower walls of the northern and southern cryptoporticuses are rougher and narrower than the vaults above, indicating different construction phases. The corridors were originally significantly narrower and later widened by cutting back the walls – by as much as 70 cm on one side and 40 cm on the other in the south, and from 6 to 3.5 meters in the north¹⁸¹. This was possible only because of the extraordinary thickness of the walls. Moreover, the original plan appears to have called for flat roofing rather than vaulting, as evidenced by surviving monolithic lintels. Lohmann also notes that the cryptoporticuses were once subdivided by partition walls, later removed – an arrangement difficult to reconcile with their interpretation as simple passageways.

8. *The unexplored chambers underneath the Hexagonal Court*

Blocked doorways on the exterior of the Hexagonal Court suggest the presence of chambers beneath the upper exedras and colonnades. These spaces remain unexplored and are shown only hypothetically in most plans of the sanctuary¹⁸². Their investigation could provide crucial insights into the construction sequence of this part of the complex.

9. *The missing cryptoporticus around the Jupiter Temple*

¹⁸⁰ Lohmann (2017a), p. 142.

¹⁸¹ Lohmann (2017a), pp. 87–88.

¹⁸² Alphonse Gosset, ca. 1911. See: Lohmann (2017a), p. 28.

Figure 82. Drawing by Louis-François Cassas (1799) showing a U-shaped tunnel or cryptoporticus running around the podium of the temple of Jupiter and a transversal passageway with two subterranean chambers running through the entire length of the podium. After Lohmann (2017a), p. 17.

A drawing by Louis-François Cassas (1799) depicts a fourth cryptoporticus beneath the Altar Court and a U-shaped cryptoporticus surrounding the Temple of Jupiter. With no direct archaeological evidence confirming the drawing, Cassas may have interpreted the space between *Podium I* and the enclosure wall as just such a structure. Given the extensive reworking observed in the existing cryptoporticuses, the idea is not entirely implausible. Indeed, a hollow cryptoporticus would have provided a far more efficient means of enlarging the platform than the massive stone packing observed today.

The metrology of Baalbek

One line of inquiry that may help clarify the identity of Baalbek’s builders concerns metrology – that is, the system of measurement employed in the design and construction of the Temple of Jupiter and its associated structures. In principle, identifying the units of measurement used could provide valuable clues as to the cultural and chronological context in which the complex was conceived.

Surprisingly few systematic studies have been devoted to the metrology of the Baalbek sanctuary, and those that do exist have produced results that are often contradictory and ultimately inconclusive. This is due in part to the lack, until relatively recently, of precise measurements of the principal architectural

elements, and in part to the complex's poor state of preservation and the many phases of modification it has undergone over time.

Three principal sources report markedly different conclusions based on metrological analysis of the Jupiter sanctuary: the work of the French architect Frederik Ragette¹⁸³, drawing largely on Kalayan's measurements and observations; an independent statistical study by Christian O'Brien¹⁸⁴; and the more recent analyses proposed by Daniel Lohmann¹⁸⁵.

Ragette, noting the apparent absence of repeating linear modules in the temple's layout, argues that the design logic of the sanctuary was governed less by fixed linear units than by proportional relationships¹⁸⁶. In his view, the builders prioritized geometric constructions over arithmetic multiples of a standard measure. Ragette concludes that many of the temple's dimensions reflect what he terms a dynamic progression, derived from the geometric relationships between the sides and diagonals of squares – a system closely related to the Golden Ratio¹⁸⁷:

“Although the Romans used the foot as the linear unit of measurement (29.7 cm), the great importance which was attached to geometric relationships in the field of design suggests that sequences of measurements were derived from geometric construction rather than linear layoff... The proportions between sides and diagonals of squares were particularly popular and often developed in sequences... This kind of relation was called a dynamic progression”¹⁸⁸.

Ragette further reports an observation by Haroutoune Kalayan, who identified markings of small squares measuring 51.44 cm – equal to 29.7 cm multiplied by $\sqrt{3}$ – and concluded that classical proportions at Baalbek were governed by geometric rules rather than by simple modular repetition¹⁸⁹. Kalayan found that, aside from horizontal measures, nearly all vertical dimensions are multiples of $\sqrt{2}$ or $\sqrt{3}$, with a margin of error of less than one percent¹⁹⁰. Notably, the measure

¹⁸³ Ragette (1980), pp. 101-103.

¹⁸⁴ O'Brien and O'Brien (2001), p. 273.

¹⁸⁵ Lohmann (2017b), pp. 56-57.

¹⁸⁶ Ragette (1980), pp. 101-103.

¹⁸⁷ Ragette (1980), p. 102.

¹⁸⁸ Ibid.

¹⁸⁹ Ibid.

¹⁹⁰ Ibid.

of 51.44 cm is strikingly close to the Egyptian Royal Cubit, famously employed in the construction of the Great Pyramid.

A very different interpretation is offered by the independent researcher Christian O'Brien. Using statistical methods, O'Brien claims to have identified two distinct quanta of measurement within the sanctuary – one associated with the megalithic platform, and another with the unquestionably Roman structures. He writes:

*“Now, the foundation platform on which the Trilithon rests is not only entirely different in style from other parts of the complex, but it has a different quantum of measurement”*¹⁹¹.

According to O'Brien, the quantum governing the megalithic podium corresponds to a unit of approximately 52.3 cm – virtually identical to the Egyptian Royal Cubit and remarkably close to Kalayan's 51.44 cm. By contrast, the quantum underlying the Great Court and other Roman elements measures approximately 58.3 cm, close to two Roman feet. O'Brien argues that this dual metrology, combined with the cyclopean character of the podium, aligns the foundation platform more closely with Egyptian pyramids and Mesopotamian ziggurats than with Roman architecture, suggesting a construction date as early as, or earlier than, the third millennium BCE¹⁹².

Daniel Lohmann, by contrast, maintains that the Roman foot – measuring approximately 29.6 cm – was the unequivocal unit of measurement used throughout the Baalbek complex¹⁹³. While it is certainly true that several dimensions can be expressed as whole numbers of Roman feet, Lohmann's argument becomes less persuasive when applied specifically to the megalithic podium and the *Trilithon*.

Lohmann gives the height of the outer megalithic podium as 3.89 meters for the base and 4.34 meters for the shaft, which he equates to 13 and 14 Roman feet respectively¹⁹⁴. Yet these figures are clearly approximate. Using a Roman foot of 29.6 cm, the actual conversions yield 13.14 and 14.66 feet. Only by adopting a unit of approximately 29.93 cm does one obtain clean values of 13 and 14.5

¹⁹¹ O'Brien and O'Brien (2001), p. 273.

¹⁹² Ibid.

¹⁹³ Lohmann (2017b), pp. 156-157.

¹⁹⁴ Ibid., p. 156

feet – closer to the Phoenician or Egyptian foot of roughly 30.0 cm than to the Roman standard.

A similar issue arises with the average length of the megalithic blocks in the lowest course of *Podium II*, which Lohmann gives as 9.53 meters, or about 32 Roman feet¹⁹⁵. In fact, this converts to approximately 32.2 Roman feet, while division by the Egyptian or Phoenician foot yields an equally imperfect but comparably close value of 31.77 feet. The same ambiguity appears when considering the overall length of the podium between the *Trilithon* wall and the western edge of the Altar Court. Lohmann’s measurement of 95.48 meters translates to approximately 322.6 Roman feet, rather than the neat figure of 320 feet, while conversion into Egyptian feet produces an equally unsatisfactory result.

Taken together, these figures do not provide conclusive evidence that the Roman foot – rather than an Egyptian or Phoenician unit – governed the metrology of the megalithic podium. At best, they suggest that no single linear unit can be identified with certainty for the entire Baalbek complex, and that different measurement systems – or a geometry-based design logic – may have been employed in different construction phases.

As the table below illustrates, the difficulty lies precisely in this ambiguity: the metrology of Baalbek resists reduction to a single, coherent linear standard, leaving open the question of whether its most monumental elements belong fully within the Roman architectural tradition, or reflect a deeper and more ancient tradition.

<i>Measure (in meters)</i>		1	0.296	0.308	0.300	0.444	0.462	0.525
Measure description	Source	Meters	Roman Feet	Greek Feet	Phoenician Feet	Roman Cubits	Greek Cubits	Egyptian Cubits
Trilithon - Blocks lengths	Lohmann (2017b), p. 153							
North	<i>Ibid.</i>	19.33	65.30	62.76	64.43	43.54	41.84	36.82
Middle	<i>Ibid.</i>	19.04	64.32	61.82	63.47	42.88	41.21	36.27
South	<i>Ibid.</i>	19.38	65.47	62.92	64.60	43.65	41.95	36.91
Trilithon - Blocks height	<i>Ibid.</i>	4.34	14.66	14.09	14.47	9.77	9.39	8.27
Podium 2 - Length	<i>Ibid.</i>	118.4	400.00	384.42	394.67	266.67	256.28	225.52
Podium 2 - Width	<i>Ibid.</i>	69.3	234.12	225.00	231.00	156.08	150.00	132.00
Podium 2 - Height of base course	<i>Ibid.</i>	3.89	13.14	12.63	12.97	8.76	8.42	7.41
Jupiter Temple - Length	Lohmann (2017a), p. 126	85.02	287.23	276.04	283.40	191.49	184.03	161.94
Jupiter Temple - Width	<i>Ibid.</i>	44.98	151.96	146.04	149.93	101.31	97.36	85.68
Stairway - Width	Lohmann (2017b), p. 153	47.4	160.14	153.90	158.00	106.76	102.60	90.29
Propylon - Length	Lohmann (2017a), p. 60	72.66	245.47	235.91	242.20	163.65	157.27	138.40
Propylon - Width	<i>Ibid.</i>	13.8	46.62	44.81	46.00	31.08	29.87	26.29
Altar Court - Length	Lohmann (2017a), p. 71	125	422.30	405.84	416.67	281.53	270.56	238.10
Altar Court - Width	<i>Ibid.</i>	120	405.41	389.61	400.00	270.27	259.74	228.57
Monumental Altar - Length	Lohmann (2017a), p. 123	20.15	68.07	65.42	67.17	45.38	43.61	38.38
Monumental Altar - Width	<i>Ibid.</i>	21.15	71.45	68.67	70.50	47.64	45.78	40.29
Small Altar - Length	<i>Ibid.</i>	9.87	33.34	32.05	32.90	22.23	21.36	18.80
Small Altar - Width	<i>Ibid.</i>	8.35	28.21	27.11	27.83	18.81	18.07	15.90

¹⁹⁵ *Ibid.*

Conclusion

After more than a century of archaeological investigation, the origins of the Baalbek temple complex remain elusive. Despite extensive excavation and study, many fundamental questions concerning the chronology, purpose, and cultural context of the sanctuary still elude explanation. In this concluding chapter, we have sought to summarize the principal lines of evidence presented throughout this work that point toward a pre-Roman origin and a more complex architectural evolution of the site.

1. A pre-Roman sanctuary.

In spite of arguments to the contrary advanced by German scholars, there is substantial evidence that Baalbek functioned as an important sanctuary long before the Roman period. The original etymology of the name Baalbek – deriving from the Phoenician *Baal-Nebek*, “Lord of the Source,” rather than the later and erroneous Arabic interpretation “Lord of the Beqaa” – and its association with the sources of the Orontes and Leontes rivers suggest that the site was already sacred during the Ugaritic period, in the second millennium BCE. This identification aligns Baalbek with the cult of the god El and situates it within a much older religious tradition.

2. Heliopolis of the North.

The importance of Baalbek in the Hellenistic period is underscored by its Greek name, *Heliopolis* – “City of the Sun.” It is difficult to reconcile such a portentous name with the idea that Baalbek was merely a minor village of little consequence. Even more striking is the geodetic relationship between Baalbek and the Egyptian Heliopolis, a correspondence that by itself points to a deep antiquity and symbolic significance of the site.

3. Triparadeisos.

There is a strong possibility that Baalbek was known in the Persian and early Hellenistic periods as *Triparadeisos*. Peace treaties and political settlements in antiquity were commonly concluded at major sanctuaries, and the Treaty of Triparadeisos – determining the division of Alexander’s empire among the Diadochi – would almost certainly have been signed at a site of exceptional religious and symbolic importance.

Baalbek, more than any other candidate, fulfills the geographical, historical, and cultic requirements of this enigmatic location.

4. **Baalbek as the lost temple of the Emesenes.**

Baalbek's remote position between the Lebanon and Anti-Lebanon ranges would not have supported a large urban population for much of its history. It is therefore best understood as an extra-urban pilgrimage sanctuary rather than a conventional city temple. The silence of many historical sources regarding such an important sanctuary may be explained if Baalbek was in fact the long-lost temple of the Emesenes, frequently cited in ancient literature but never conclusively identified archaeologically. The association of Emesene royalty with the Roman monumentalization of Baalbek, together with philological links between Elagabal (Heliogabalus) and Baal Helios, strongly supports this identification.

5. **Legendary traditions.**

While legendary and pseudo-historical traditions must be treated with caution, their sheer abundance cannot be ignored. Numerous late antique and early Byzantine sources attribute an immense, even antediluvian antiquity to Baalbek, associating it with the Flood, Nimrod, the Nephilim, and the Tower of Babel. Although the attribution to Solomon can safely be dismissed as the product of a false etymology, the persistence of these traditions suggests the survival of local memories pointing to a long pre-Roman past already regarded as remote by late antiquity.

6. **Simultaneous construction of *Podium I* and *II*.**

Archaeological evidence clearly indicates multiple construction phases at Baalbek. It is implausible that a sanctuary of such antiquity and importance would have left virtually no archaeological traces prior to the Roman period. The most likely explanation is that the Romans monumentalized an already existing sacred site. The foundations demonstrate conclusively that *Podium II* cannot predate *Podium I*, since the latter's foundations extend beneath those of the outer enclosure wall. Practical considerations concerning the transport and placement of the megaliths further suggest that *Podium I* and *Podium II* were constructed synchronously. The isolated column drum beneath the *Trilithon* is best explained as the result of a later repair, while the extraordinary depth of

the foundations – reaching at least 17 meters near the Temple of Bacchus – and the fact that they were at least in part meant to be visible, points to an earlier and possibly more ambitious construction stage.

7. The original sanctuary as T-shaped.

Excavations between the two podia show that *Podium I*, and possibly the entire early platform, was originally T-shaped. This configuration bears a closer resemblance to Egyptian temple layouts – particularly those of the Late Dynastic and Ptolemaic periods – than to canonical Greco-Roman temples. The wide frontal arrangement recalls the position of hypostyle halls, while the massive enclosure wall may have served both to define sacred space and to protect the sanctuary from catastrophic flooding. Any reconstruction of this pre-Roman temple must remain tentative, given the extent of later demolition and rebuilding.

8. The transportation of the megaliths.

The *Trilithon* stones raise two fundamental problems: how stones weighing over 800 tons were transported, and how they were set in place with such extraordinary precision. While various methods involving capstans, traction, and ramps have been proposed, all require vast open spaces and massive anchoring platforms. Far more challenging is the precision of placement, with joints so fine as to be barely visible. Achieving such accuracy would almost certainly have required suspending and carefully lowering each block – an operation that would challenge even modern engineering.

9. The project unfinished.

The Baalbek complex is conspicuously unfinished. The enormous stones still lying in the quarry, some exceeding 1,600 tons, show that whatever the original architects of Baalbek set out to build remained incomplete. Either they reached the limits of their technical capabilities, they ran out of time or resources, or fell victim to some unknown cataclysm that stopped them on their tracks. It is possible that a third megalithic course was planned above the *Trilithon*, and that the enclosure wall was intended to extend further east, perhaps forming the foundations of monumental pylons or propylaea in the area of the present Great Court.

10. The Roman transformation.

Finally, the Roman transformation of Baalbek profoundly altered – and largely erased – the earlier sanctuary. In adapting the pre-existing megalithic platform to a canonical Roman podium, the Romans filled the space between *Podium I* and the enclosure wall, reusing older masonry as packing. They may even have contemplated fully encircling the temple with porticoes, a plan that would have concealed almost all traces of the earlier structure. The construction of the major Roman monuments extended over nearly three centuries and was itself never fully completed. Subsequent Byzantine and Arabic modifications, including the conversion of the site into a fortress, further obscured the evidence.

In sum, while Lohmann’s reconstruction of the Baalbek sanctuary as a wholly Roman creation remains possible, it is far from proven. An alternative interpretation – one that sees the Roman temples as the culmination of a much longer architectural and religious history – better accommodates the archaeological, logistical, metrological, and historical anomalies discussed in this study. Until the foundations of the complex can be systematically explored and dated by absolute methods, the true origins of Baalbek must remain an open question – but one whose answer likely lies deep beneath the monumental stones themselves.

The future of Research

Only a detailed investigation of the foundations beneath the Temple of Jupiter may ultimately resolve the question of the sanctuary’s pre-Roman origins. Such an investigation could be carried out either through the excavation of a limited number of deep test pits at critical architectural junctions between successive construction phases, or through non-invasive geophysical methods such as seismic or electrical resistivity tomography. These techniques have already proven effective in a wide range of archaeological contexts, including the reconstruction of the architectural evolution of the Castillo pyramid at Chichén Itzá, where traditional excavation would have entailed an unacceptable risk of damage to the monument¹⁹⁶.

Outlined below are several proposals for future research which, with minimal or no disturbance to the ancient structures, could yield substantial new information on the architectural development of the Baalbek temple complex.

¹⁹⁶ René E. Chavez, Andrés Tejero Andrade, Denisse L. Argote Espino, and Esteban Hernández Quintero (2018), “Karst Detection Beneath the Pyramid of El Castillo, Chichen Itza, Mexico, by Non-Invasive ERT-3D Methods”, *Nature, Sci Rep*, 8, 15391.

1. ***Clearing the northern “moat” between the megalithic podium and the northern megalithic enclosure wall of the Temple of Jupiter.***

A systematic clearing of this area from accumulated soil and debris would expose the original foundations of both the temple platform and the outer enclosure wall. Previous investigations have shown that the foundations of the temple platform extend beneath the lowest stone courses of the enclosure wall, but their full extent remains unknown. Such an intervention would clarify whether a continuous stone foundation exists only beneath the T-shaped walls of the original platform, or whether it extends farther west beneath the northern and western enclosure walls. Of particular interest would be the precise nature of the structural connection between the foundations of *Podium I* and the lowest courses of the enclosure wall.

2. ***Determining the northern and southern extent of the T-shaped walls of the original temple platform.***

While the maximum western extent of the T-walls can be established with reasonable certainty – owing to the presence of clearly visible angular seams in both the northern and southern walls – their maximum extension to the north and south remains unknown, though it is likely constrained by the position of the outer megalithic enclosure wall. Targeted test pits along the northern edge of the enclosure wall could establish whether the foundations of the T-walls terminate at this boundary or extend beyond it. An equivalent investigation on the southern side would be equally informative.

3. ***Probing the depth of the foundations beneath the Trilithon.***

A test pit excavated along the outer face of the *Trilithon* would help determine the true depth of the foundations at this critical point, which is likely to represent the deepest section of the entire platform. Such an excavation would also help confirm whether the foundations extend directly to bedrock, as appears to be the case elsewhere in the complex.

4. ***Re-exposing the core masonry of the Temple of Jupiter’s podium.***

During the first German excavations of 1898–1905, the core masonry beneath the Temple of Jupiter was left fully exposed. These

foundations were later reburied by the French and Lebanese antiquities authorities in the mid-20th century to create a level terrace atop the podium. Re-exposing this core masonry would offer a rare opportunity to study the internal structure of *Podium I*, which is known to consist of very large stone blocks arranged in alternating courses of headers and stretchers. Wiegand and the early German excavators already noted the presence of parallel joints and seams within this core, suggesting a more complex construction sequence than the relatively uniform stonework of the outer walls alone would imply.

5. *Investigating the eastern foundation near Kalayan's well.*

Among the most intriguing results of recent investigations of Kalayan's well is the discovery of massive megalithic foundation blocks located southeast of the Jupiter temple stairway, at approximately the same elevation as the base of the enclosure wall and the podium. In the absence of any visible ancient structures above ground in this area, it is conceivable that these foundations belong to a planned eastern extension of the megalithic platform. The only other visible indicators of such an extension are the two enormous blocks set perpendicularly to the northern and southern enclosure walls near the point where the enclosure disappears beneath the floor of the Great Court.

All of these investigations would involve relatively limited interventions, requiring modest financial resources and causing no significant alteration to the ancient structures. Yet together they have the potential to substantially advance our understanding of the construction history of the Baalbek sanctuary and to clarify, perhaps decisively, the question of its possible pre-Roman origins.

Figure 83. The temple of Bacchus at sunset, as seen from the Jupiter temple. © Marco M. Vigato.

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